

An analysis of innovation barriers in the Bangladeshi Public Sector and how leadership approaches can influence them

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“We shall not cease from exploration, and at the end of all our exploring will be to arrive where we started and know the place for the first time.”

– T. S. Eliot

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Abstract

Aim – The study aims to examine in detail the external and internal challenges regarding service delivery innovation in Bangladeshi public sector organisations, to understand how leadership or managerial behaviour impacts them and to recommend some leadership/managerial strategies to alleviate those challenges.

Design/methodology/approach – Using a qualitative Case study approach, the study collected data from respondents involved in three government projects through semi-structured, open-ended interview questions which were then examined using thematic analysis.

Findings- The research discovered that despite some challenges faced by the projects, they are all fully operational. Key internal and external challenges were identified that created delays in various phases of the projects. A significant impact of leadership has been identified in dealing with the challenges.

Research limitations/future scop of research – As there is a large number of public sector organisations in Bangladesh, all of the observations made by the three units of analysis may not produce identical or similar results. There is a need for more large-scale future studies including a wide range of government organisations in the future to gain a better understanding of the reality and findings. Additionally, a more in-depth analysis of the personal traits of the managers could be introduced in a future study using a mixture of methods.

Practical implications – The dual style leadership suggestion will help the public sector managers to decide what methodologies and tactics to apply in future challenging cases, as well as establish a public sector leadership framework to foster innovation in partnership with the current researcher and any future researchers.

Originality/value– This study is the first to bring together public sector innovation challenges and leadership strategies to tackle them in the context of Bangladesh using a Case Study approach.

Key words: Innovation, Public sector innovation, Case Study, Bangladesh, Leadership, Dual Leadership Style

List of Abbreviations

a2i	Access to Information
BCC	Bangladesh Computer Council
BCS	Bangladesh Civil Service
BDT	Bangladeshi Taka (Currency)
BIDA	Bangladesh Investment Development Authority
BMD	Bangladesh Meteorological Department
BOB	Bay of Bengal
BRD	Business Requirement Development
CA	Content Analysis
C2C	Citizen-to-Citizen
C2G	Citizen-to-Government
DDM	Department of Disaster management
DMP	Dhaka Metropolitan Police
DNCC	Dhaka North City Corporation
DSCC	Dhaka South City Corporation
FDI	Foreign Direct Investment
GDP	Gross Domestic Product
GIS	Geographic Information System
GNI	Gross National Income
GoB	Government of Bangladesh
ICT	Information and Communication Technology
IVM	Interactive Voice Message
NGO	Non-Governmental Organization
PMO	Prime Minister's Office
SMS	Short Messaging Service
SSI	Semi-Structured Interview
SRSD	System Requirement Structure Development
SWC	Storm Warning Centre
SWAT	Special Weapons and Tactics

SWPC Special Women Police Contingent

TA Thematic Analysis

TC Tropical Cyclone

UNDP United Nations Development Program

USAID United States Agency for International Development

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Chapter 1. Introduction

1.1 Introduction:

Different people from diverse sectors, such as business executives, policymakers, and public managers, are becoming increasingly interested in innovation (*Damanpour et al., 2009*). In the public sector, a growing number of people believe that innovation may help improve service and problem-solving capabilities (*Damanpour & Schneider, 2009; Walker et al., 2011; Walker & Boyne, 2006*). Marketable invention is described as the process of taking an idea and turning it into a new product, service, solution, or business model that can be sold to customers. At the same time, governments strive to increase their responsiveness to citizens' needs when considering bigger societal processes and concerns (*Mulgan, 2009; De Vries, Bekkers & Tummers, 2016*). In this context, innovation is viewed as a "magical idea" (*Pollitt & Hupe, 2011*) that is used to frame the necessary transformation of the public sector to increase not only its efficacy and efficiency but also its credibility (*Bekkers et al., 2011*). Managing innovation entails formulating a vision and plan, putting in place the mechanisms that will make it a reality, and fostering the organisational conditions and culture that will allow ideas to emerge and be implemented. Management books and academic literature on innovation have long focused on creativity, innovation strategies, development processes, knowledge management, and examining companies, as well as innovative cultures. However, leadership conduct has changed to some extent and many studies and practitioners have identified it as one of the most vital, if not the most crucial catalyst for the creativity of an organisation.

Public sector organisations must respond effectively to changing conditions in the difficult and continuously changing competitive environment. They need to hire, retain or train people who can deliver profitable service to citizens and manage it successfully, especially for managerial positions. Each stakeholder evaluates business performance differently: the owner wants a return on investment, employees anticipate a higher quality of life at work, customers expect a product at a reasonable price, and so on. Managers must consequently know how to manage effectively; they must choose a suitable leadership style, but most importantly, they must ensure that the organisation's performance is continually improved. It's a good idea to look for a management method that helps to link innovation to operational goals while also assisting in incorporating continuous improvement of everyday activities into the plan. The current study emphasizes understanding the state of public sector innovation in a developing country like Bangladesh and what are the constraints of taking innovative measures in transforming the

service delivery to citizens. The study also aims to identify the leadership impact in tackling the obstacles to develop some recommendations for the public sector management practice in Bangladesh to facilitate innovation.

1.2 Background of the study:

In an era of constraints, when public organisations around the world are faced with a more unpredictable operating environment and the challenge of doing more with less, innovation has become critical to providing effective services to citizens (*Bernier, Hafsi, and Deschamps 2015*). An idea, activity, or project that is viewed as new by an individual or other unit of adoption" is what innovation refers to (*Rogers, 2003*). Innovations differ from inventions in that they must be put into practice, and they differ from continual improvement because risk-taking and bureaucratic discretion run counter to traditional public administration concerns with control and responsibility and may result in failure, abuse of citizen rights, favouritism, or corruption, innovation has been questioned as a legitimate role of public management (*Terry, 1993*). Unauthorized innovation (for example, skunkworks ventures that do not follow standard protocols) is sometimes regarded as inappropriate (*Halachmi, 2002*). More regulations, limits, and constraints that limit government servants' permissible behaviour are frequently considered a remedy in the case of performance shortcomings, rather than innovation (*Kelman, 2008*). However, due to fluctuations in public policy and interests, public organisations must adapt regularly (*Ricard et al. 2017*). Innovative methods can aid public sector organisations in dealing with change and stakeholder expectations, as well as give the government legitimacy as a provider of public benefit in that they transcend beyond modest tweaks and modifications (*Moore, 2014*).

The revolution has altered how businesses operate in recent decades, with new business models spawning new markets. Developed countries have used research and development, human capital development and talent management, improved manufacturing skills, and the concentration of high-tech public companies to accelerate economic growth. Bangladesh's government has also taken steps to implement a number of modifications in service delivery systems within traditional administrative levels by deploying contemporary ICT (Information and Communication Technology) technologies in various e-service centres across the country. The general public, particularly service recipients, is pleased with the services offered. As a result, the services provided by entrepreneurs have been justified in terms of consumer satisfaction. It is impossible to have strong governance in today's digital era without a well-

developed e-service delivery system. Bangladesh's current government has taken steps to promote digital service delivery to achieve political consensus, develop the necessary human resources, and encourage the use of ICT at various levels of government by enacting appropriate policies and strategic plans (*Hassan, 2013*).

Bangladesh, which has a population of around 170 million people, is one of Asia's fastest-growing economies, with an annual GDP growth rate of around 6% for the past two decades (*IMF, 2020*). It ranks third in the worldwide RMG market, behind China and Vietnam, with USD30 billion (83 per cent of total export revenues) in 2018 (*Hossain, 2018*). By 2025, an extra 11 million jobs are predicted to be created as the country grows (*Byron, 2020*). With 97 per cent mobile phone coverage (166 million) and 58 per cent internet penetration (100 million), connectivity has achieved its pinnacle (*BTRC, 2020*). As a result of this, start-up activity has increased as local and global enterprises emerge with new business models and innovations to meet unmet needs across the country. Bangladesh's government has also launched national and regional initiatives, such as boot camps, hackathons, co-working spaces, accelerators, and incubator programmes, in recognition of the importance of fostering innovation and entrepreneurship as a vital driver of economic growth (*Haque & Mourshed, 2020*).

Despite all the efforts, In 2019, a report revealed some startling statistics concerning Bangladesh's innovation condition. It was quite upsetting to realize that Bangladesh is Asia's least inventive country and Bangladesh is placed 116th out of 129 nations in the Global Innovation Index 2019. In terms of innovation, the country ranks at the bottom of the list among Southeast Asian countries (*Haque & Mourshed, 2020*). Therefore, there arises a requirement to understand the barriers to innovation in Bangladesh, and specifically in the public sector; to improve the situation. The Bangladesh government has taken some initiatives in recent years as part of making a service delivery revolution in the country, known as their vision 2041 (*Haldar, 2018*). The later section will take about this innovation development in detail and the current research will take three examples of this innovation activity to investigate public sector innovation challenges and leadership impact to overcome them.

1.3 Bangladeshi Public Sector and Innovation:

Bangladesh's political system has gone through many changes. After a few years of democracy, the military ruled for nearly a quarter-century. Bangladesh established a fully functional democratic structure for the first time in 1990. Except for an expansion in the number of ministries, divisions, departments, and statutory organisations, the nature and role of

bureaucracy in both pre-democratic and post-democratic periods remained nearly identical (*Ahmed, 2002*). The environment in which public sector organisations operate has traditionally solely included the domestic economic, political, and social context in which the organisation is located. Public organisations are increasingly frequently confronted with global dangers and possibilities that affect their operations and views, according to the report by Welch and Wong (*2001*). The effectiveness of a public organisation is largely determined by how a domestic political institution responds to global influences and interacts with the bureaucracy.

Bangladesh's government is divided into two levels: national and municipal. There are 64 administrative districts, followed by a tiered system of local government that includes single-tier urban authorities made up of 11 city corporations and 329 municipalities, as well as a three-tiered rural local government system made up of 64 districts, 492 sub-districts, 4,573 union parishads, and three hill districts. The range of functions for which each type of authority is accountable varies greatly, from public health and hospitals, education, and social welfare for city corporations and municipalities to development projects, public libraries, and roads for Upazila and union parishads (*Clfg. org, 2017; pmo.gov.bd, 2018*).

People living in rural and urban areas of Bangladesh typically face various types of obstacles when attempting to obtain public services from the age-old traditional bureaucratic public service delivery systems, and in most cases, they must go through several intermediaries (middlemen) to obtain services at a higher transaction cost than necessary. As in many underdeveloped countries, governmental institutions in Bangladesh struggle to identify and respond to residents' demands. Overly convoluted and top-down bureaucratic systems, characterised by change-resistant attitudes and over-centralization, offer considerable hurdles for rural individuals seeking public services and information (*Aziz, 2020*). The Bangladeshi government has recently undergone several restructuring initiatives to improve the capacity, effectiveness, and standard of the services. Despite these reforming attempts, the public's perception of government employees and the level of service they offer is still largely unfavourable. According to several surveys, the public views the government as being over-centralised, unaccountable, inefficient, overpaid, coercive, unethical and rent-seeking. Individual interactions with officials resulted in needless harassment, anticipatory anxiety in determining simple problems, impolite and arrogant conduct, keeping citizens waiting for long periods before attending to their requirements, frequent absence from office, inability to maintain appointments, ignoring requests for re-evaluation of an issue, unwillingness to correct mistakes, and making unreconstructed approaches for financial benefits (*Zaman & Sarker,*

2021). According to various surveys, individuals are generally dissatisfied with the level of service they receive, and public workers who provide these services are frequently criticised for their work performance. Hence comes the need of providing the service digitally to remove the obstacles in between. Traditional and low-value-added activities predominate in Bangladesh's services sector. By reducing the intermediary obstacles that impede efficiency the objective would be to create more competitive service marketplaces by including more innovative solutions (Mujeri & Mujeri, 2021). In a developing country like Bangladesh, where transparency and accountability of public officials is a key issue; transforming the services digitally has the potential to change how the government interacts with its constituents, corporations, and other governmental entities to increase accountability, empower citizens, improve service delivery, and boost efficiency (Rashid & Safie, 2018).

Long regarded as a development laboratory for issues such as poverty reduction, public health, and environmental management, the country has now firmly included public service delivery in its innovation priority areas. The creation of over 5,000 one-stop shops across the country, the world's largest online government portal, a \$10 million Service Innovation Fund to enable whole-of-government and whole-of-society systems to co-create unique solutions to development challenges, and a market-driven state-of-the-art architecture to expand and intensify digital financial inclusion are just a few examples of large-scale public service delivery innovations under the a2i (*a2i.gov.bd,2017*).

1.4 The rationale of the study:

Government innovations have steadily been launched in Bangladesh to assist policymakers to reach certain targets or objectives, improve state services to citizens, strengthen the country's economic growth, and solve different socio-economic and political issues that affect the government and the people. Indeed, countries that are still developing, their ability to generate and integrate innovations is critical to their success. Bangladesh's government has been under pressure to respond to citizens' requests as well as the growing complexity and change in global contexts. Bangladesh has had eight different regimes since 1971, each with its own set of political systems and governing methods. Every government has adopted a different approach to sociopolitical progress, administrative reform, and economic stability. However, more often than not, these innovations failed, obstructing the construction of effective governance and the country's overall progress (*Ferdousi & Qui, 2013*). As a result, to increase technological infrastructure, human capital, and economic performance, as well as strengthen innovation

capacities in the changing modern environment, Bangladesh must implement creative methods, strategies, and policies.

The technological aspects of e-governments have received a lot of attention, as evidenced by the technical readiness assessment of Bangladesh for e-government implementation. Many government and non-government organisations have carried out numerous project-based studies for the assessment of technical factors. However, the government, as well as "e", have a significant role in the success of e-government. Digital service delivery is crucial for assuring greater openness, accountability, and transparency in the government system, as well as for the development of the economy and society. Developing human resources, connecting citizens, delivering services to people's homes, and expanding ICT-based business prospects are the four main areas of concentration for Bangladesh's digitization process. However, in a developing nation, simply giving the technology is not sufficient. Guidance and education are required to ensure that the technology is adopted by the end users (Waughen et al., 2015).

Again, the overwhelming emphasis on the technological factor creates a genuine gap in research on Bangladesh's non-technical environment, including political desire, vision and strategy, management capabilities, etc. concerning the implementation of digitalisation of government services. There is a severe lack of evaluation of non-technical aspects that contribute to technology transfer adoption. Professor Richard Heeks gave one specific example about the national databank initiative in Bangladesh. Bangladesh's Planning Commission took the initiative to make official statistics available to government ministries, non-governmental organisations (NGOs), and general stakeholders for government and public usage. However, this project was a complete failure (Rashid & Safie, 2018; Aziz, 2020). Professor Heeks (2009) highlighted the key causes of failure as a lack of human resource practice, a lack of leadership, and a poor government-supplier relationship. The experience of the Bangladesh Garments Manufacturers and Exporters Association (BGMEA) in implementing the National Portal for Garments Industry is another example of a technical and financial capability failing to achieve the desired success due to non-technical barriers such as lack of trust and engagement and lack of creative problem-solving. For developing nations looking to strengthen democratic institutions and boost public trust in government agencies, digital innovation is crucial however, it is hard to streamline complex bureaucracies without causing some form of disturbance along the way, thus the initiative to build that infrastructure can only happen with leadership from the top (Chowdhury, 2020).

As mentioned by the authors above and considering the specific failed cases, the government sector innovation challenges which are technical, as well as non-technical need to be further investigated and potential strategies, need to be recommended to mitigate them. Additionally, the majority of the research on public sector organisations in Bangladesh has focused on administrative reform, barriers to public sector growth, political corruption, and a lack of political leadership. In Bangladesh, almost no one recognises the importance of competent managers in various public sector organisations (*Rahman, 2015; Mohammad & Islam, 2014, Aziz, 2020*). Since its inception as a nation in 1971. Bangladesh has had a variety of governments, each of which has attempted to construct the public administration in their way, resulting in a confusing notion of managerial leadership and a lack of innovative motivations in the country (*Ferdousi & Qui, 2013, Binxkin & Pradhan, 2017; Zaman, 2021*). As a result, the public sector's overall management lacks inventiveness in decision-making and service delivery. Furthermore, several journalists and social researchers agree that the government has attempted certain creative steps but development is slow and hampered on multiple levels and is not widely celebrated among the service users (Abedin, Ferdaus, Shah & Sayem (2021). The overall lack of emphasis on non-technological factors as well as the facts gathered from failed cases creates a gap in literature and practice to investigate which factors may cause hindrance in digital service delivery government projects and how leadership can be utilised to overcome them.

1.5 Aim of the Study:

The study aims to examine in detail the external and internal challenges regarding service delivery innovation happening in public sector organisations, to understand how leadership or managerial behaviour impacts them and recommend some leadership/managerial strategies to alleviate those challenges.

1.6 Research Objectives:

- to investigate the current state of innovative approaches/projects taken by the government organizations
- to identify the successful and failed features of innovation projects
- to analyze the internal and external catalysts that promote or demote innovation
- to identify the impact of current leadership and decision-making approaches for the

innovation projects

- to recommend leadership approach(s) to overcome the challenges of innovation

1.7 Research Questions:

-What is the current state of innovative approaches/projects taken by government organizations?

- What were the successful or failed features during the projects?

- Which are the internal and external catalysts that promote or demote innovation?

- How did the existing leadership approaches impact the innovation process?

- What will be the recommended leadership approach to overcome the challenges?

1.8 Research Method:

The researcher will use the qualitative case study method to perform in-depth investigations of the innovation situation of the Bangladeshi public sector which is a complex phenomenon as there is not much information available on them. This method entails a thorough investigation, using observed data gathered over different cases to provide an analysis of the phenomenon's context and processes. These characteristics of the case study method allow the researcher to concentrate on the behaviours, attributes, actions, and interactions of individuals (*Brewer & Hunter, 1989*). Case study is the most suited technique as the researcher has slight control over occurrences and the focus is on current phenomena in a real-life environment (*Yin, 1994*).

1.9 Outline of the study:

The next chapter will critically analyze the existing literature to develop a conceptual framework for the study. Following the chapter, the research design for the current study will thoroughly discuss and justify all the aspects of research- the philosophy, the methods, the data collection, and the analysis process. The chapter next will focus on the whole process of data collection and analysis which will be followed by the results and findings. The final chapter will give concluding remarks on the study to build future platforms in the field of innovation and leadership research in the Bangladeshi Public sector and expect to give a suggestive framework or recommendations for the problems identified in the study.

Figure 1.1: Outline of the study

Chapter 2. Literature Review

2.1 Introduction:

Innovation is a mandatory process that is required for all sorts of organizations in the current world as it is changing every day, without new ideas and vision, the organization will not sustain itself in the competitive market (*Drucker, 1990*). Managers of both the public and private sectors have taken innovation as a topic of great interest nowadays. According to Borins (*2001*), private sector organizations are changing the way of business with the assistance of innovation- launching new products, transforming production processes, and many more. This Schumpeterian way of innovation is creating a constant desire to be creative and making managers either go with the creativity flow or consider the ill-fate of the business. It's either innovate or die for them. McDonald (*2007*) acknowledged that the public sector too, needs unique innovative measures to gain a competitive advantage and the public sector leaders feel the same amount of pressure. Light (*1998*) suggested that public sectors should be well prepared to embrace the innovation and change process that comes along with that for it to be a common practice. The capability to innovate is a must for the long-term sustainability of the public sector and the experimentation and utilization of resources wisely should be a key concern for the leaders (*Gummer, 1989; Kanter & Summers, 1987*).

To strongly embrace the difficulties that come with the changing environment; the public sector of any country should be powerful and trustworthy as they play a major role in shaping a country's economic and social standards. To fulfil the need for constant creativity, these organizations have to go through major changes and the employees find it hard to see through the transition. An effective leadership approach creates a bridge among all levels of employees and management and therefore, directly impacts the loyalty and creativity of the employees (*Hyatt, 2007; Gill, Levin & Pitt, 1999; Kickul & Liao-Troth, 2003*). The objective of this chapter is to discuss the different aspects of Innovation in public sector organizations to understand how different factors enhance the culture of innovation in the public sector. Furthermore, it will discuss the impact of leadership behaviour/decision-making dynamics on public sector innovation. Lastly, the chapter will critically discuss the existing research about public sector innovation and leadership in Bangladesh to highlight the research gap and significance of the current research.

2.2 Innovation- a brief definition:

The concept of innovation is rather complex and has been examined by various researchers from separate academic points of view. Public sector innovation thus has no universal definition and shares some level of characteristics with organizational innovation based on process change, change in services, and method of doing business to gain maximum efficiency. Drucker (1974) has mentioned the process of innovation as the equipment of improved capabilities and an increase in utility. He mentioned in his work that innovation needs to be market-oriented and act continuously to respond to the changing environment. To be sustainably innovative, the system needs to address the problem and at the same time, create new opportunities for further creativity. The gap between innovation and invention has been pointed out to the lack of proper conditions to implement it commercially, making the difference between the two fairly distinctive (Fagerberg, 2004). As to Schumpeter (1934), radical innovations help shape the world whereas incremental innovations fill in the change process continuously. Again, Drucker (2001) in his later edition of work presented three conditions for successful innovation- Firstly, continuous effort, research, and a creative mindset are necessary. Secondly, Innovators must focus on their strengths to gain an advantage, and thirdly, the innovation should bring about significant changes in the behaviour and life of users or the general public in terms of the public sector.

The academic literature represents various definitions of innovation, from various perspectives by revealing key features. Rogers and Kim (1985) as stated in Smith, Glor & Brodtrick (2001) have emphasized the concept of originality, other researchers have described it as a different approach that varies from organization to organization where it is introduced. Thompson (1965) defined innovation as a whole process starting from idea generation, acceptance of the idea, and implementation of the idea into services, products, or processes in a practical situation. Some had described it to be the exact synonym of creativity (Jacques & Ryan, 1978) and one group acknowledged the concept of newness but denied it to be related to revolutionary changes (Merritt, 1985).

2.2.1 Innovation in Public Services:

Scupol and Zanfei (2016) defined public sector innovation as a new or considerably improved form of public services, method of communications, processes, or organisational systems for the supply and introduction of such services. This definition differs from the Oslo Manual's standard definitions of innovation, which were designed with the business sector in mind,

notably privately owned industrial businesses. According to Windrum (2008), the public sector shares many similarities with the private sector in terms of process and organisational innovation, however, some public services may be more complex.

Tannenbaum (1999) defined innovation at the government level as a way of formulating satisfactory policies and regulations to attract foreign investment, inspire and create a culture of creativity and new ideas; integrate new technological aspects in service delivery by supporting small-medium enterprises and innovators. Some countries follow the traditional way of including innovation by simply changing or reforming their old bureaucratic policies to new ones whereas others focus on fighting to establish transparency or re-evaluate their old process. Although innovation in the private sector is getting more attention among most published works, public sector innovation, in any way or form, requires equal attention and offers a variety of perspectives in accomplishing targets. Kamarck (2004) has mentioned in his work that the innovation process can be reinventing the government, increasing the capacity of state resources, or modernizing the existing process and described it as new public management.

In innovation theories, public sector organisations and their inventive actions are undesirable visitors. On the one hand, various studies emphasise the importance of public services as enablers and accelerators of other economic agents' innovation processes. Some public services (administrative agencies) provide a regulatory foundation for the private sector's innovation dynamics. Others (public research laboratories, universities) primarily support foundational and applied research. For instance, in system and network theories, public services occupy a central place from this dual perspective of support and contribution (Freeman, 1987; Lundvall, 1992; Nelson, 1993; Edquist, 1997, 2005). They play a key role in the "triple helix" paradigm (Etkovitch and Leydersdorff, 2000), which describes knowledge generation processes through hybrid networks that connect universities, businesses, and government agencies. On the other hand, the dynamics of innovation within government organizations remain mostly unexplored "black boxes" in these models and have received little attention, particularly in economic literature. Even theories specifically addressing service innovation often ignore the unique nature of public sector innovation. When public services are discussed in theoretical models, it is usually in a very oblique fashion, or solely to highlight their limitations in comparison to market services.

Again, Vigoda-gadot et al (2005), talked about the concept of organisational innovation from a fuzzy concept viewpoint and provided a broader definition of modern innovation in bureaucracies. He pointed to the factors that can escalate managerial reformation in the post-public phase. Alberti and Bertucci (2006) in line with Vigoda's work, looked at the innovation process, capacities, resources and project environment for the successful implementation of the project and adaptation by the public sector officials as well as the service users (citizens). They argued that the efficiency of innovation and new changes incorporated into practice depends on many factors which are, in fact, tangible in nature like collaboration and cooperation of different parties involved.

Another source of the empirical gap may emerge when innovation is taken into account in public services. It's about how the invention works. Indeed, in the absence of profit, the product of public services is defined as a total of expenses, therefore the focus is on innovations that aim at efficiency rather than effectiveness. Public services are regarded as effective when they are efficient, as Potts (2009) correctly points out. As a result, the performance difference is inextricably related to the innovation gap. In the public sector, innovation has long been viewed as a cost-cutting strategy at the detriment of other performance goals. However, public service performance can take numerous different forms in addition to cost reduction and production increase. Interpersonal interactions, trust, empathy, inclusion, equality, and justice are thus related to innovation and value creation in public services. The pursuit of these performance levels may direct public-sector innovation in specific directions.

Congenial working environments and cooperative labour management are important in the globalised competitive world, according to Hossain (2002), Bhattacharya (1998), and Murayama and Yokota (2009). To keep their competitive advantage, businesses must adapt to advances in technology and other sectors. If companies can efficiently attract and keep the best and most innovative workers available, they will survive and expand to their highest level of performance (Arthur, 1994; Collins & Smith, 2006; Delery, 1998; Youndt, Snell, Dean and Lepak, 1996; in Martinez, Vela-Jimenez & De-Luis-Carnicer, 2008).

There is no indication that public-sector employees are less innovative than private-sector employees (Rainey, 1999). Some studies have shown that people who work in the private sector are more innovative because they are motivated by competition, whereas others believe that people who work in government organisations are less innovative. After all, the nature of their work makes them risk-averse to jeopardising public funds or failing in terms of individual

political affiliation However, it may be claimed that public organisations have a higher level of innovation potential because they don't have to worry about losing "competitive advantage" by sharing ideas, information, and knowledge (*Hartley, 2014*).

The knowledge-based world requires the government to be more proactive and innovate more to create a more progressive mass as well as meet the constantly changing demand of the state. To summarize, government innovation or regeneration of the public administration is a key to effectively facing the national and international challenges and creating strong governance. The public sector of any country includes different public institutions that impact the everyday lives of the people directly and indirectly. From political governing bodies to implementing and structuring laws, and providing various social and public services like education, health, and security- the institutions are offering essential services that are vital to upholding the entrepreneurial democracy.

If an action saves money but harms a part of the population, it should not be classified as an innovation. To do so is to describe creativity from the bottom up. Furthermore, the development of public value must be supported by proof that innovation is likely to succeed. In the public sector, the costs of an unsuccessful invention are likely to be much higher than in the private sector. When innovation fails in the public sector, a part of the public is likely to suffer as a result. Creating, designing, and implementing practical innovations that benefit the public is what public sector innovation entails. These concepts must be at least to some extent new (rather than adjustments); they must be adopted and implemented (rather than solely existing concepts), and they must be practical. Innovation, by this definition, is similar to but distinct from invention and entrepreneurship.

A recent study shows that Public sector services can account for Innovation and entrepreneurship in public services for a significant part of all economic activity. In most developed nations the public sector accounts for around 20 per cent of employment and around 15 per cent of national GNP. For instance, the UK public sector includes 40% of GNP, around 20% of the total employment, and 30% of professional employment. As the importance of the public sector can not be neglected in terms of productivity, employment, and social well-being, research in public should be more varied and widespread. Very few studies take into account both the innovative initiative in public and private sector organizations but Earl (*2002,2004*) is an exception. Her study was conducted on a sample of public and private organizations in Canada for the period 1998-2000. The findings from the study suggested that around 80% of

the public sector organizations have had creative changes in management style or structure whereas only 38% of the private sector organizations had done something similar. The role and duties of public sector organizations are very diversified in terms of innovation. Public and private sector organizations interact in the vast majority of service sectors in Europe and the USA as well as developing countries in Asia and South America. The duties include social and personal services, health and education, medical facilities, telecommunication, transportation, and the production of various goods and services.

Baumol's (1976) literature debated the impact of the service economy to determine the growth and productivity of a nation known as the *assimilation– demarcation–synthesis debate*, which argues about the nature of the innovation in public service delivery and the roles of the organisations as important mediums of commercial development. Although the objective of innovation studies is to understand the factors that work behind driving innovation and the connection between social and economic change, the absence of the topic of public sector innovation in the literature has created a gap. The important dimensions of public sector innovation have been left out of early pieces of literature and therefore, failed to address the necessity of it facilitating the growth of a country.

2.2.2 Types of government Innovation:

To develop a clear understanding of the various forms of innovation that are found in the public sector, the classification of public service innovation is presented in the works of Windrum and Coach (2007) as mentioned in Windrum (2014). It classifies government innovation in 6 ways-

- a) Service innovation
- b) Service delivery innovation
- c) Administrative and organizational innovation
- d) Conceptual innovation
- e) Policy innovation
- f) Systemic innovation.

Service innovation can be defined as introducing a service or product or improving an already existing one. The range of innovations may include changing the entire service or product or changing some parts of it to gain maximum advantages. It is quite similar to product innovation in the manufacturing goods sector and is the traditional focus of innovation-related studies.

Service delivery Innovation, on the other hand, is the involvement of new or changed conducts of delivering to the customer or interacting with them to supply various/specific public services.

The inclusion of new ideas or change management which impacts the organizational structure and system through which staff offer services in a certain way and support other members can be defined as innovation of administration and organization. For the last 20 years, the idea of New Public Management has grown a lot of interest among researchers and managers to reform the management of public sector organizations. The idea, although not new, still acts as a major force in innovation and change management in government institutions.

Conceptual innovations are very important for organizations that work to fulfil the social and economic objectives and requirements of the general public. This type of innovation can be defined as the development of new perspectives that challenge the existing product development process, services, and organizational forms. Conceptual innovation can happen at all levels of the organization and introduce new missions, objectives, and strategies.

Policy innovations can be defined as the intention to change the existing thought and behaviours associated with a policy or belief system (*Sabatier, 1987, 1999*). At the ministerial level, policy innovation can be of two forms- incremental innovation; a policy analysis by the government, and radical innovation- which results from conceptual innovation. As per the work of Galsbergen (*1994*), policy innovations are linked with three types of learning – how policy instruments can be improved to achieve set objectives, conceptual learning followed by shared understandings of a problem to decide on a course of action to overcome them and finally, social learning based on the learning of the accurateness of the policy factors, the rules of change and interaction based on new perspectives of social governance.

Systemic innovation is referred to as the new and improved ways of interacting with other organizations and the exchange of knowledge. The interactions have taken a different direction over the last 20 years, mostly as a result of the lack of proper regulation and an increase in competition and partly because of resource constraints in public administration. Besides, consumer choice has become more sophisticated over time and more and more services are being outsourced nowadays.

From a different angle, Lee, Hwang, and Choi (*2012*) investigated contemporary open innovation practices in the public sector of leading countries (e.g., the United States, Australia, and Singapore) and identified three significant practises: government-led versus community-

led open innovation, a lack of inside out open innovation, and the need for developing an overarching strategic plan in citizen sourcing. In their investigation, Gieske, Buuren, and Bekkers (2016) recognised three dimensions of inventive capability. They assessed the innovative capability of public sector organisations in three areas: connective capacity, ambidextrous capacity, and learning capacity. Other key findings from the study included: that innovation in the public sector is about balancing exploration and exploitation (e.g., innovation and improvement within and between organisations); and the creative capacity of public organisations can be enhanced if a multidimensional approach is taken into account when constructing the building blocks of public innovation processes (Moussa et al, 2018). Although innovation is frequently associated with the concept of performance enhancement, establishing the relationship between innovation and performance can be difficult due to the volatile nature of innovation (Tidd, 2001).

2.2.3 Public Sector Innovation in Developing Countries:

The international environment is becoming more competitive, innovative, and demanding. To be able to benefit from this increasingly globalized environment, developing countries have to improve their skills and innovation capabilities. Developing countries are characterized by socio-political instability, corruption, weak economies, imperfect markets, poor infrastructure, deficient management and technical skills, inadequate public education facilities, and limited government initiatives in support of innovation. It is a common conception, in many developed countries, that the public sector is not entrepreneurial and does not innovate. Public sector institutions are considered conservative, bureaucratic, and slow-moving, and to whatever extent they do change, this is primarily a consequence of changes that occur outside public institutions, that is, as a result of the innovative activities of non-governmental organizations (NGOs) or private sector firms. Innovations developed elsewhere are belatedly adopted by the public sector. This view is frequently tied to the public versus private sector debate (Gago & Rubalcaba, 2007). In this debate public and private services are presented as a discrete choice, that is, either public or private service provision. Given the supposed superior innovative potential of the private sector, the policy should focus on the privatization of public services, thereby ensuring increasing productivity growth and employment, as well as the superior quality of service provision.

According to a study undertaken by the World Bank, two global drivers control innovation in developing countries. The first is that the globalisation process is becoming more intense. This

globalisation, propelled by the technological revolution, is manifested, among other things, by the significance of trade within the global economy. It has also shortened travel time and distance drastically across the world, bringing the most remote to the most vibrant areas. The second global driver is the rapid pace of technological change fuelled by profound scientific breakthroughs in the fundamentals of life, matter, energy, and time. As a result of each of these changes, a new period of growth is forming, steadily displacing the previous one. (*Hoffman, Rodrick & Thee, 2004*).

Other main elements of knowledge-based economies, as described in the WBI four-pillar system, such as educational attainment, the business environment, and information technology, work as disruptors in developing countries' innovation climates. In developing countries, educational levels are poor, which is a major barrier to the development and progression of innovation. There is a direct connection between educational requirements and the various stages of industrial growth. Simple literacy is all that is required of students in the pre-industrial period. More technical and medium-level skills are vital in the industrial phase. A large share of the population with postsecondary education is needed in the post-industrial period, with the rest of the population having at least a basic literacy level (*OECD, 2007*). Fears of short-term detrimental consequences of implementing automation on jobs may be underestimated, particularly if labour and education policies encourage compatibility between skills available in the workplace.

A quantitative empirical study was done by Aljarallah & Lock (*2020*) to gauge Saudi Arabian residents' perceptions of the qualities of long-term e-government. The results of a survey of 442 people were analysed to see how they felt about the importance of long-term e-government services. Verkijika and Wet (*2018*) observed in their study of African countries' e-governance that performance expectancy, social influence, perceived risk, and computer self-efficacy all had a direct impact on attitudes, whereas attitudes, facilitating conditions, government trust, and Internet trust all had a direct impact on behavioural intention to improve the government innovation. Fernando (*2016*) in an attempt to understand the managerial innovation in public universities in western Sri Lanka, did research using the well-known snowballing methodology. A descriptive qualitative analysis was carried out. The study found that innovation is both possible and occurring inside university management. Bhuiyan and Amagoh (*2010*) in their public sector innovation study discovered that Kazakhstan is following the global trend of implementing e-government to improve efficiency, effectiveness, access, quality, transparency, and accountability in the delivery of public services. Decentralization

has been identified as an important technique for bringing governments closer to residents and reacting to their demands. In their exploratory study, Arfeen and Khan (2009) concluded with the dilemma of the Pakistani government embracing e-government as a technology to run their businesses more efficiently, devise and implement better policies, and provide programmes and services more effectively. Yoon (2006) focuses on Korean government innovation methods and techniques. The Korean government has defined five main elements in realising its vision for innovation: productivity, high-quality service, openness, decentralisation, and participation.

It can be seen that most of these studies are either mixed methods, strictly quantitative or take a look at the innovation from the citizen's perspective. The current research aims to take a look at the managerial and employee aspect and try to find out what went on inside the project as well as the external influences which always gets more discussion.

2.2.4 Factors affecting Innovation:

There are quite a few impediments to government innovation, both internal (strategy-related) and external (market-related). Government bureaucracy, a shortage of government assistance, complicated credit policies, and a lack of resources, time, staff, and awareness of available technology are among the major barriers to innovation found by Garsombke and Garsombke (1989). These are the important dimensions for public-sector entities to consider. It's important to learn more about organisational innovation processes such as top-down policy growth, bottom-up initiatives by managers and employees, and lateral adoption and adaptation of best practices (Tidd, 2001).

Government innovation is a multi-layered mechanism that is influenced by both internal (organisational culture) and external influences (stakeholder interests). Resistance to transition, a lack of effective legal framework, a lack of independence, professionalism, and access to information, deference to authority, resource constraints (human or financial), and low regard for government administration are all factors that Alberti and Bertucci (2006) identify as barriers to government innovation. Economic factors (such as high prices or a lack of demand), business factors (such as an absence of trained manpower or knowledge), and legal factors such as regulations or tax rules) may all disrupt innovation.

Intrinsic and extrinsic motivations for creativity have often been separated (Morgan et al., 1993). Prestige, material possessions, monetary and professional assistance, job security, employment prospects, a supportive work climate, and positive job evaluations are examples

of extrinsic motives. The ability to generate new ideas, intellectual challenges, and work satisfaction are examples of intrinsic motivations.

According to Kanter (1984), there are a variety of environmental variables that serve as obstacles to innovation. Bad communication, a shortage of resources, top-down directives, inflexibility with changes, cultivating a culture of inferiority by implying that creativity must be imported to be worthwhile; and, according to another report, workplace politics is a significant barrier. Furthermore, Vigoda-Gadot (2003) identified the following barriers: short-term budgeting and planning issues; weak mechanisms for benefits and recognition to innovate; a culture of market volatility; insufficient risk management and change management competencies; inability to shut down failed programmes or organisations; and restricting cultures or organisational arrangements, despite the availability of technology. Koch and Hauknes (2005), on the other hand, focused on the scale of the company to define limitations, such as the inherent contradiction between organising and innovating.

Lewis et al (2018) mentioned three key factors that impact the innovation capacity of a public sector organisation:

1. innovation drivers – Any organization's ability to innovate is influenced by the environment in which it operates, as well as its internal structures and processes. Previous research suggests that the political and administrative framework, the public sector's legal culture, state and leadership practices, and resource allocations can either spur or stifle innovation.
2. networking – More external networking (which allows access to a broader range of information from outside the organisation) is seen to be positively related to self-rated innovation potential.
3. leadership – senior executives' attributes and competencies, and how they affect change and innovation in organisations and networks.

Tahrira and Jaegal (2012) based their paper on the key barriers discussed by the Regional Workshop on Science and Technology Statistics (2005)-

- *Knowledge factors* include inadequate innovation opportunities; a scarcity of skilled staff, innovative technologies, management solutions, and consumer data; and difficulty locating partnerships.

- *Institutional factors* include bad infrastructure and weak property rights. Infrastructure refers to the physical and organisational frameworks that are required for a government, community, or business to function.
- *Cost factors* -Unnecessary potential risks, a lack of internal funds and external financing, including public sources of funding, and high innovation costs are all cost drivers.
- *Market Factors*-Market dominance by existing firms and unpredictable demand for new products or services are two market factors to consider.
- *Legal Factors*- Lack of appropriate laws, rules, and guidelines are among the legal factors.
- *Political factors* include the absence of democracy and political parties, clashes between political parties, political leaders' insensitive and unempathetic behaviour, a lack of transparent and committed leadership, criminality and corruption among party leaders, and authoritarian state tactics that deter people and opposition parties from constructive involvement.
- *Administrative factors* include- organizational incompetence, a lack of appropriate vision, excessively centralised government policy and resource distribution, civil service politicisation, and complex and obsolete administrative structures are all administrative causes.
- *Social factors* include- social instability and disparity, a lack of education, and non-innovative values and beliefs.

This paper, however, does not acknowledge the internal organizational culture factor. Organizational culture and environment are both widely discussed concepts when it comes to understanding employee innovation. Some scholars use the words "organisational climate" and "organisational culture" interchangeably (*Schneider, 2000; Von Treuer & McMurry, 2012*); however, the two terms are distinct and have been studied separately.

The definition of the notion was not agreed upon by Hofstede, Neuijen, Ohayv, and Sanders (1990). They did, however, identify a few features of organisational culture. Organizational culture is comprehensive, traditionally determined, anthropologically related, socially built, soft, and difficult to modify. Organizational culture, according to Schein (1990), is a pattern of basic assumptions invented, discovered, and developed by a given group as it learns to cope with its problems of external adaptation and internal integration that has worked well enough to be considered valid and, as a result, is to be taught to new members as the correct way to perceive, think, and feel about these problems. Artefacts, values, and assumptions are the three

levels of corporate culture identified by Schein. In their study, Hofstede et al. (1990) discovered that shared perceptions of daily behaviours, not shared beliefs, are at the heart of an organization's culture.

The primary distinction between culture and climate is that culture emphasises common beliefs and viewpoints within an organisation (Cooke & Szumal, 1993), while climate refers to individual work unit opinions that may or may not be shared (James et al., 2008). Tan, Smyrnios, and Xiong (2014) reported that when workers "feel good" about their work environment, they perform better, and leaders can expect innovative and creative behaviour.

As a result, creating a conducive environment for workers to engage in creative actions and innovation is not a choice. The personality of an organisation is reflected in its organisational culture, which includes values, norms, beliefs, and principles that can affect how an individual acts and makes decisions (Yassin, Salim, & Sahari, 2013). Support for innovation was identified as a key factor in fostering a creative environment (Siegel & Kaemmerer, 1978). The positive attitude toward creative ideas, backed up by effective incentive programmes, was defined as the creative environment (Tidd, Bessant, & Pavitt, 2001). As a result, a connection between a company's environment and innovation has been well-founded.

The empirical evidence from a study by Demircioglu & Audretsch (2017) reveals that the likelihood of innovative behaviour is influenced by crucial variables unique to the public sector. Experimentation, responding to underperformers, the presence of feedback mechanisms, and motivation to improve all help to increase the chance of innovative behaviour. Budget limitations, on the other hand, have no statistically significant impact on single innovation projects in their study which was conducted among Australian Public sector organisations. However, several other studies confirm budget limitation as a significant factor in hampering innovation.

Borins (2001) proposes three tactical methods for overcoming innovation barriers, and he recognises the value of providing a formal managerial structure or leadership strategy. A leadership approach can be especially beneficial in reducing the internal change crisis, establishing an innovative organisational culture, and motivating subordinates to innovate more. The later sections will thus discuss the various aspects of leadership and how it impacts innovation in the public sector.

2.3 Leadership and Innovation:

Leadership was one of the key factors that were widely argued to affect organisational and employee creativity (*Osborne, 1998; Shin & McClomb, 1998*). The literature on business innovation, as well as perspectives on public sector innovation, revealed that an innovative culture must be embraced by those in positions of power within every organisation (*Borins, 2001*). Researchers have considered different methods and concepts to explore how leadership promotes creativity to explain the effect of leadership on innovation.

There's a lot of evidence that leadership is crucial for innovation management (*Nadler and Tushman, 1990; Denti and Hemlin, 2012*). Leadership is critical in improving organisational creativity (*Mumford et al., 2002; Amabile et al., 2004*), initiating and supporting innovation projects (*Stoker et al., 2001; Bossink, 2007*), and delivering innovation projects and overcoming resistance (*Mumford as al., 2002; Amabile et al., 2004*). According to Somech (*2006*), business leaders are the major drivers in the organisation, either promoting or inhibiting innovation management. Various leadership styles, according to Bel (*2010*), are likely to have different effects on staff engagement and commitment, which influences the climate for innovation management. Deschamps (*2005*) on the other hand, claimed that inadequate leadership abilities are the most common cause of innovation project failure (*Kesting, Ulhoi, Song & Niu, 2016*).

A few studies have found that employees' creative behaviour is highly dependent on their interactions with others as well as the organization's contextual factors (*Axtell et al., 2000; Zhou & Shalley, 2003*). Leadership has been recommended as one of the key factors for achieving individual and organisational effectiveness and creativity, among all the contextual factors that affect employees' work climate (*Engelen, Schmidt, Strenger, & Brettel, 2014; Wang, Rode, Shi, Luo, & Chen, 2013*).

Transformational leadership, according to Kahai, Sosik, and Avolio (*2003*) and Shin and Zhou (*2003*), facilitates idea generation. Managers can use a transformational leadership model to encourage subordinates to be more imaginative and inventive while finding solutions (*Kahai et al., 2003*) and encourage them to reach their maximum potential (*De Jong & Den Hartog, 2007*).

This leadership style, according to Gumusluoglu and Ilsev (*2009*), consists of original and creative behaviours. Transformational leaders, according to McMurray et al. (*2012*), want to sell their strategy to their staff. According to Kahai et al. (*2003*), transformational leadership

has a detrimental relationship with creativity-related processes and outcomes. Other research has found a connection between transformational leadership and a lack of imagination. (e.g. *Sosik, Kahai, & Avolio, 1998; Wang & Rode, 2010*), while others had different conclusions. However, *Kesting et al (2016)*, discovered significant evidence that different stages and types of innovation place varied demands on leadership. In light of this, transformational leadership isn't the only way to lead innovation; different leadership styles work better with different types and stages of innovation.

In a study of 1,292 members of 136 primary care teams and their managers, *Somech (2006)* found that a participative leadership style is positively linked to team reflection and, as a result, to team innovation. Empowering leadership is another leadership style that shares some parallels with participative leadership and has been linked to creativity and innovation. This focuses on giving staff autonomy and independence while also removing bureaucratic impediments (*Ahearne, Mathieu, & Rapp, 2005; Forrester, 2000*). Leadership and professional attitude, according to *McDonough (1993)* and *Thamain (1990)*, have a significant impact on creative results. It is barely possible to achieve innovative results without immense help from leaders, according to *Reiter- Palmon and Illies (2004)*. Similarly, *Simmons (2011)* observed that innovative procedures and policies that are supportive of innovation promote continuous improvement.

To make accurate predictions about the effect of leadership on innovation, *Rosing, Frese, and Bausch (2011)* proposed that the different elements of the mechanism be considered. *West (2002)* considered innovation and inspiration to be the first and second steps in this complicated method, which is complicated because these steps do not follow a straight linear path. (*Anderson, De Dreu, & Nijstad, 2004; Van de Ven et al. 1999*). The only solution to cope with this complication is to create a comprehensive model of leadership impacts that affect the process (*Mumford & Licuanan, 2004*).

After reviewing numerous studies that show a connection between leadership and employee and organisational creativity/innovation, it can be concluded that leadership has a greater impact on achieving any innovation goal in any organisation.

2.3.1 Defining Leadership

Robert Wright (2004), in his much-acclaimed piece of work, has mentioned the influence of rapid technological and social progression on a child and how it influences his/her upbringing,

cultural background, and interpersonal development (*Stewart, 2006*). The world in the past couple of decades has experienced a remarkable change in the field of leadership. As stated by Peter F Drucker in “Managing in Times of Great Change”, the traditional organizational skeleton was built with the combined idea of rank and power and was perceived to be an achievement of gathering a large number of followers. However, the emerging new economy has paved the way for new leadership; one to be built with mutual understanding and participation. Therefore, the present concept of leadership needs to be analysed from the perspective of time, corporate culture, personality traits, adaptability to change, and economic and social growth.

To understand the concept of leadership in-depth, firstly the core and basic definition of leadership should be taken into consideration. Scholars and business managers all have different versions of leadership. Warren Bennis has connected leadership with the quality of turning a vision into a reality and on other hand, John Maxwell has defined leadership as a quality to influence (*Kruse, 2013*). Yet, as discussed previously, the definition of leadership cannot be confined to these attributes of power, vision, and influence only. Kruse (*2013*) and Hartley & Bennington (*2011*) have analysed all the most known definitions of leadership and explained leadership as a social influential process that can maximize the efforts of the ones involved to achieve the ultimate goal.

In an organisation, he reasoned, a manager can influence subordinates to get the task done, but it requires a person with good leadership skills to actively urge subordinates to be creative and participate in the trip to reach the destination. Because no two people are the same, their attitudes and ideologies will differ. No single definition or style may be considered an absolute. Before delving into the debate over which leadership style is most suited to current organisational management, the theories and leadership styles should be extensively examined.

According to leadership literature, theories have been revised and marginally or significantly updated over time, and hence cannot be regarded as irrelevant. The style of leadership required in jobs requiring a high level of precision, confidence, sensitivity, care, and technical expertise may differ from that required in simple management-oriented portfolios since one size does not fit all (*Dess, & Picken, 2000*). It indicates that scenarios, settings, culture, working environment, new corporate laws and regulations, information overload, organisational complexities, and psycho-socio developments have a significant impact on the leadership

notion, making it more responsive to changing organisational dynamics (*Amabile, Schatzel, Moneta & Kramer, 2004*).

The great men theory became obsolete, as did the growth of organisations. The passage of time has given the coup de grace to another force, the great man, who with intellect and foresight could reign with dictatorial powers as the head of a rising organisation but slowed democratisation in the process. It was also established that a person does not become a leader simply by possessing a certain set of characteristics (*Samad, 2012*). The dynamic between these factors was established in terms of the amount of direction and guidance; socio-emotional support and task behaviour, in performing a task by the level of readiness (commitment and competence) of the followers and relationship behaviour required by the follower's functions and objectives (*Ryan & Tipu, 2013*). The authoritarian leader makes decisions without consulting his subordinates, the laissez-faire leader lets subordinates make decisions and hence has no genuine leadership role other than occupying the job, and the democratic leader consults with his subordinates before making a decision (*Nawaz & Khan, 2016*).

2.3.2 Types of Leadership

Trait Theory:

Traditional scholars believed that born leaders have physical and psychological features that separated them from non-leaders. The assumptions concerning whether leadership traits are inherited or acquired were neglected by trait theories. As per Max Weber, charisma is the most revolutionary force, capable of establishing a whole new orientation through followers' complete personal devotion to leaders whom they regard as having practically otherworldly, extraordinary traits and powers. This early emphasis on intellectual, physical, and personality attributes that distinguished non-leaders from leaders foretold subsequent investigations that claimed only minor distinctions existed between leaders and subordinates (*Burns, 2003*). Trait theory, as an obscure component, fell out of favour as a result of the failure to uncover the features that every single effective leader shared in common.

Contingency Theories (Situational):

According to contingency theories, no individual leadership style is ideal because it is contingent on conditions such as the quality of followers, their position, and a range of other variables. According to this notion, there is no one-size-fits-all method of leadership since the leader must change to the situation's internal and external aspects. Contingency theorists thought the leadership was at the core of the leader-subordinate dynamic, whereas situational

theorists considered the employees were vital in defining it. Although situational leadership focuses primarily on the leader, it emphasises the necessity of concentration in the group dynamic. The situational leadership principle states that a leader's approach should be suited to the maturity of his or her subordinates. (*Bass, 1997*).

Style and Behaviour Theory

The style theory acknowledges the importance of many essential leadership skills that enable a leader to perform an act by drawing a parallel with the leader's previous ability before that specific act and suggesting that each person has a distinct style of leadership with which he or she is most satisfied. One style does not suit all situations, just as one head does not match all persons (*Nawaz & Khan, 2016*).

Yukl (*1989*) developed three different types of leadership. Employees working for democratic leaders showed a high level of happiness, ingenuity, and motivation; they worked with great enthusiasm and energy regardless of whether the leader was present or not; and they maintained better relationships with the leader in terms of efficiency, while autocratic leaders mostly concentrated on outputs in greater quantity. In the past, laissez-faire leadership was only considered important when leading a team of highly qualified and motivated individuals with a proven track record.

Feidler & House (*1994*) described two additional leadership styles stressing the effectiveness of the leadership. These observations imply that attention (concern for people and relationship behaviours) and commencing structure (concern for development and task behaviours) were very critical variables. The factor in question is how much confidence and rapport a leader instils in his subordinates. On the other hand, initiating structure represents the degree to which the leader structures, directs, and determines his or her own and subordinates' positions as they contribute to organisational success, benefit, and task accomplishment (*Nawaz & Khan, 2016; Jaleha & Machuki, 2018*).

Three styles of leaders were suggested by Kert Lewin and backed up by different researchers. autocratic, democratic, and laissez-faire. The autocratic leader makes decisions without consulting subordinates, the laissez-faire leader lets subordinates decide things and therefore takes no real leadership role other than claiming the title, and the democratic leader consults his subordinates before making a decision (*Burns, 2004*).

Process Leadership Theory

Servant leadership, learning organisations, principle-centred leadership, and charismatic leadership are some of the other process-focused leadership concepts, with new ones arising every year. In the early 1970s, Greenleaf pioneered servant leadership. In the early 1990s, there was a revival of interest in servant leadership (*Nawaz & Khan, 2016*).

Transactional Theory:

By the 1980s, leadership theories had begun to deviate from the fundamental perspectives of the leader, leadership background, and follower, toward approaches that concentrated more on follower-leader interactions. Transactional leadership has been defined as a leadership style in which interactions between superiors and subordinates are built through a comprehensive agreement (*House & Shamir, 1993*).

The transactional theory is based on reciprocity, which means that leaders not only control but also influence their followers. Transactional leadership, according to some studies, has a gap between the degree of leadership activity and the nature of the followers' connections. According to Bass and Avolio (*1994*), transactional leadership is a type of contingent-reward leadership marked by an active and productive interchange between leaders and followers, in which followers are rewarded or honoured for fulfilling agreed-upon goals. The manager's recognition for merit growth, promotions, and professional accomplishments could be one of these incentives.

In exchange for exemplary work, positive reinforcement, merit pay for promotions, enhanced efficiency, and civic engagement could all be offered. Instead, the leaders may focus on making mistakes, delaying responses, and deferring decisions. This approach is known as "management by exception," and it can be classed as either passive or active transactions. The distinction between these two types of transactions is determined by the timing of the leaders' appearance. The leader in the active form maintains a close eye on the results and attempts to intervene before things go awry (*Avolio & Bass, 1997*).

Transformational Theory

Transformational leadership differs from previous and current theories in that it implies engaging followers in processes or behaviours linked to personal factors against the company and a path that will produce a superior social dividend (*Ahmed, Ullah & Khan, 2016*). Both the follower and the leader's motivation and morality are increased by transformational leaders

(House & Shamir, 1993). Transformational leaders are thought to "engage in relationships with followers based on shared values, beliefs, and goals." This has an impact on the success that leads to the achievement of the target.

According to Bass, transformative leadership tries to encourage followers to reorganise their demands by raising self-interests and striving for higher-order goals. This hypothesis backs up Maslow's (1954) higher-order need theory. Transformational leadership is a route that focuses on a leader's values, ideals, and attitudes to illuminate their behaviour and ability to lead change. According to the findings, followers and leaders set their personal interests aside for the greater welfare of the group. The leader is then urged to consider the aspirations and suggestions of followers in order to inspire and motivate others to take on leadership roles (House & Aditya, 1997). Transformational leadership is further distinguished by the ethical components of leadership, which are highlighted in long-established leadership theories.

The ability to recognise the need for reform, garner others' commitment and support, create a vision that supports implementation, and entrench the transition are all characteristics of transformational leaders (Bums, 2003). By making their work worthwhile and demanding, these leaders respect their subordinates as individuals and aim to increase their consciousness, values, and skills. These leaders give the sense of having a clear and optimistic future vision. They are visionaries who seek to prod their followers toward higher and more universal objectives and aspirations by appealing to their better natures (MacGregor & Bums, 2003; as stated by Nawaz & Khan, 2016).

Theory X and Theory Y

In the 1960s, Douglas McGregor argued that a manager's leadership style was dictated by his or her conceptions of human nature. He defined two broad schools of thought, which he labelled theory X and theory Y, based on his study. According to Theory X, humans have an innate dislike of work and must be regulated and guided to achieve goals. As a result, autocratic and oppressive leadership styles emerge.

Again, a job, according to Theory Y, is a natural part of life that provides people with a sense of fulfilment. Respect and appreciation will inspire employees to offer their maximum. As a result, management/leadership frameworks are more consultative and participatory development. Although both types of management could be successful, McGregor argued that theory X management could lead to a lack of motivation and low standards of achievement,

while theory Y management could result in greater productivity and performance (*Nawaz & Khan, 2016*).

Leadership Styles:

Leadership is one of the most widely observed but little understood phenomena on the planet (*Burns, in Abbasiyaliya, 2010*). Researchers have suggested a variety of leadership styles over time since no one style of leadership can be considered universal. A successful or effective leader encourages, motivates, and guides efforts to help accomplish community or organisational objectives, despite the many different types of leadership. Ineffective leadership, on the other hand, does not contribute to organisational success and may even hinder the achievement of organisational goals. Effective leadership, according to Naylor (*1999*), is a product of the spirit, and an effective leader must be visionary, enthusiastic, artistic, versatile, motivating, inventive, brave, imaginative, experimental, and a change initiator (*Amanchukwu, Stanley, & Ololube, 2015*).

Rensis Likert

How authority was exercised was the subject of early theories regarding management and leadership style. Rensis Likert identified four distinct types based on research conducted at the University of Michigan in the 1950s-

- exploitative/authoritative – the leader has no faith or confidence in his subordinates, governs by enforcing directives, and motivates by intimidation and retribution.
- benevolent/authoritative – the leader has faith in his employees but treats them in an authoritarian and demeaning way.
- consultative – the leader expresses trust and faith in subordinates, soliciting their views and suggestions while maintaining decision-making authority.
- participative – the leader has full faith in his subordinates, listens and responds to their suggestions, and includes them in goal-setting. According to Likert's research, consultative and collaborative management styles are more effective, but he failed to consider the scope in which management was carried out.

The Tannenbaum Schmidt Leadership Continuum

Robert Tannenbaum and Warren H Schmidt made early contributions to the existing literature on leadership styles in the 1950s. They looked at the extent of how much power or influence

management has over his or her employees, as well as how much flexibility they have to operate on their own. They suggested a seven-stage 'leadership continuum,' going from a scenario in which the manager makes all decisions to the point in which the manager allows team members to make decisions individually within predetermined limits. Tells, persuades, demonstrates, consults, asks, shares, and involves are the seven types listed. They additionally mentioned that a good manager would be able to assess the team's strengths and switch between points on the scale as required (*Amanchukwu, Stanley, & Ololube, 2015*). As the manager's abilities grow, they will decide how much more freedom to give to the staff while still maintaining overall responsibility for the job.

The managerial grid

Robert R Blake and Jane S Mouton described two drivers of managerial behaviour while working in the 1950s and 1960s: consideration for getting the job done and compassion for the future involved. They used a nine-by-nine grid to illustrate how an individual manager's style is influenced by their level of concern for these two factors. This showed five basic management styles:

1. Impoverished management – There was no regard for the mission or the participants. This style consists almost entirely of going through the motions and doing just enough to get by.
2. Authority-obedience –Concern for the challenge is high, but concern for people is low. This is a commanding style, similar to the conventional 'command and control strategy, but it does have the potential to affect human relationships.
3. Country club leadership –Concern for people is high, but concern for the mission is low. This is seen as supportive – it can build a warm and welcoming work atmosphere, but at the expense of getting the job done effectively.
4. Team management – Concern for both tasks and people is strong. This is thought to be the most powerful style with the greatest potential for success.
5. Middle-of-the-road management – consideration for tasks and people is mild. This achieves a task-performance balance, but it is more likely to maintain the status quo than to achieve notable success.

2.3.3 Leadership in the public sector

Administrative leadership research (literature focused on leadership in public-sector bureaucratic contexts) has lacked the volume and integration of mainstream leadership study (

Van Wart, 2003). According to Doig and Hargrove (1987) and Terry (1995), there may be some notion that administrative leadership somehow doesn't (or should not) exist to a significant degree in the public sector due to a belief in a largely instrumental style to leadership. Furthermore, bureaucracies may be directed by tremendous factors beyond the control of administrative leaders, rendering their contributions inconsequential.

Two major streamlines of public sector leadership theory have been discussed by Kettl (2000) in Lemay (2009). One perspective in the traditional approach differentiates the political and administrative dimensions of leadership in Public sector organizations. According to this theory, administrative leaders are quite limited and there is a hierarchical dilemma going on between the bureaucratic and administrative position holders. This perspective is seen more prominently in the literature regarding the public sector. Specifically, in the public sector leadership research in developing countries (*Barrientos, 2002*). Kettl (2000) argued that to uphold the morality of democracy, the public sector leaders must exercise their leadership practices under the consideration of political leaders despite them having a strong influential capacity (*Cook, 1998; Van-wart, 2003*).

Another perspective suggests that public sector administration is not limited to a certain role and can work independently without much interference from the politically elected members. The public sector organizations play an influential role in the formation of the economy and therefore the leaders are quite determinative and may be considered a threat to the democracy and elected members. Some scholars prefer leadership that can be separated from public policies (*Cook, 1998*). The managers or organizational leaders are considered guardians of public goods and services. The elected political members must encourage a standard for the leaders which is transparent and responsible and take a step back from taking the organizational decisions as the managers have more experience handling organizational difficulties.

It can be observed from the discussion that many scholars are arguing that both political leadership and organizational leadership cannot function together as both have a dominant decision-making approach and when it comes to the public sector a strong approach is needed. However, Lynn (2001) has mentioned that despite their differences, they can not replace each other, and both of their existence are necessary for the public sector to run smoothly. It can also be noted that most of the existing literature on leadership in the public sector only focuses on either of the perspectives but very few acknowledge the practical situation and necessity of suggesting a way through which political and organizational leadership compliments each other

and does not overshadow. Again, these two perspectives can not be taken as the only ways to understand public sector leadership as leadership has taken quite a dynamic approach in recent times as mentioned previously.

2.3.4 Public sector leadership impact on Innovation:

As stated in Lewis et al (2018), in the public sector, the link between leadership and innovation has yet to be fully defined. Much New public management research on innovation has emphasised the importance of individual entrepreneurship in driving change (Walker et al, 2011), whereas the Network Governance or New Public Governance version emphasises 'co-creation as a means of generating innovation through new government–society relationships, particularly to solve complex issues (Ansell and Gash, 2008; Klijn and Koppenjan, 2016). The ability of senior administrators and politicians to lead in the public sector appears to be linked to innovation. Effective mixtures of politicians and top administrators are also likely to be vital for innovation.

Dumay, Rooney, and Marini (2013) conducted a cross-sectional analysis using semi-structured interviews to gather empirical data on the role of senior managers in enabling and resourcing innovation. It was conducted among 27 senior executives from Australia's top public-sector firms. The study also suggested the need for expertise to be developed to identify the form of innovation that is allowed and match it to an appropriate strategy.

Although most public sector leadership studies have discovered that CEOs and boards of directors frequently make strategic decisions about the implementation of technologies, they have also discovered that many innovations originate from the bottom up (Kanter, 1988, 2001). In a series of papers, Hesselbein et al. (2001) demonstrated that private-sector researchers and practitioners agree on the value of bottom-up technologies and provide recommendations on how organisations should promote them. In the public sector, on the other hand, traditional wisdom dictates that almost all creativity comes from the top (Wilson, 1989).

Borins (2001) examined three types of government innovations using quantitative surveys and case studies to assess the relationship between the three types of innovation and the influence of leadership on them. They are political responses to emergencies, organisational turnarounds orchestrated by newly established department leaders, and bottom-up innovations pioneered by front-line public servants and middle-level managers. Quantitative findings from public sector innovation awards show that bottom-up innovation is much more frequent than

conventional thinking implies. In a crisis, effective political leadership necessitates a broad quest for facts, broad consultation, and a sceptical review of a variety of options.

According to his work, a successful leadership turnaround must restore political trust, reach out to stakeholders and customers, and persuade disgruntled employees that progress is achievable and that their efforts to improve will be rewarded. He argued that through advising staff, instituting formal and informal recognition for innovators, encouraging innovators, shielding innovators from control-oriented central agencies, and actively advocating bottom-up innovations that have proven efficient and have universal appeal, political leaders and agency heads may build a positive atmosphere for bottom-up innovation.

According to Osborne and Plastrik's (2000) research on creative non-profits and small public sector organisations, an executive leader's support is critical for fostering an innovation culture within the organisation. Leaders can promote an innovative culture, be innovators, and build an organisational framework that promotes innovation (Peters & Waterman, 1982; Van De Ven, 1986).

To put it another way, leaders can evolve by implementing new programmes and laws that legitimise innovation. The importance of showing honesty, being more transparent, and being concerned with ethical protocols is heavily emphasised in leadership studies (Trevino & Nelson, 2014). Furthermore, some of the essential leadership characteristics include standing up for what they believe in, communicating directly, meaningfully, and transparently, developing trusting relationships with all stakeholders, and ensuring they do not misrepresent or mislead others in any contact (Stanwick & Stanwick, 2003). As a consequence, it is expected to have a positive impact on individual results and perspectives.

Boal and his co-researchers created a conceptual structure that highlighted the role of strategic leadership in fostering innovation. Strategic leaders, according to Boal (2007), promote processes that help strengthen, endorse, and cultivate innovation and creativity among employees and subordinates. Consequently, strategic leaders, according to Boal & Schultz (2007), foster an atmosphere of learning and innovation, as well as improve the efficiency and commitment of subordinates, to improve service delivery.

An innovative culture must be encouraged by those in positions of authority inside any firm, according to research by Moussa et al. (2018). He suggested that public institutions are under intense pressure all the time to add greater value to their communities. It is therefore imperative for public services to incorporate vital leadership behaviours and styles for managing and

fostering innovation due to the term's complexity, particularly in the government. Regarding the unique function of senior managers, Damanpour and Schneider (2006) contend that these individuals have an impact on innovation adoption through resource management and strategic decision-making. As a result, top managers can have a significant impact on innovation, either for or against it, especially if decision-making authority is concentrated in their hands (*De Vries, Tummars, and Bekkers, 2018*).

In a recent study conducted on the public sector innovation in Indonesia using the desk research method and case studies, it was identified that in Indonesia, innovations in the public sector were greatly influenced by leadership. The researchers concluded that when a crisis or a shift in an organization's direction occurs, leaders are found to innovate. Leaders also establish priorities and visions to help them decide what kinds of solutions will be used to address these challenges (*Kusumasari et al, 2019*). This study examined the importance of leadership in public sector innovation in COVID-19 management using a systematic review approach (PRISMA) and synthesised 23 publications from 23 different Asian nations. According to available statistics, public sector innovation and the function of each country's leaders have been proven to be highly interdependent. It is discovered in the study that different leadership philosophies can affect how much innovation is used and whether a strategy response is successful or unsuccessful, which supported a similar argument presented in a study conducted by Sazzad, Rajan and Demircioglu (2021).

Lan & Hang (2018), in their study of the public sector management reformation in Vietnam, substantiated that traditional public administration places a strong emphasis on task-oriented leadership. Task-oriented approaches, however, are insufficient in the modern public administration context to meet the high demands of the populace and to innovate the way the public sector offers its services; instead, they call for leaders who are concerned not only with their tasks but also with their followers, the organization's strategy, creative decision making, encourage innovation and build future development directions. Another recent study conducted by Khan, Hussain and Al-Ghazali (2020) supported a positive connection between leadership style and innovative employee behaviour. Therefore, there's a scope of research on proposing a new leadership framework that will be sustainable and can adapt to changes in the context of developing nations like Bangladesh.

Kuldosheva (2021) conducted a study to understand potential barriers to Government innovation in post soviet Uzbekistan by conducting surveys. He identified that the successful

implementation of the digital reforms in the public sector is being hampered by obstacles, both institutional and infrastructural, a lack of experience in creating online public services with high-end user value, as well as other underlying causes like the structure of the economy and the overall income level along with geographic and demographic conditions and an ineffective governing style of the managerial authority. However, he concluded that face-to-face or one-to-one interviews with government representatives could provide a more comprehensive picture of the current institutional landscape and e-government difficulties. Therefore, there is room for more in-depth research to better understand the underlying reasons why some digital efforts are successful while others are not, as well as how management style affects these outcomes.

An interesting approach to leadership and its impact on Public sector service delivery was taken by Franklin and Plimmer (2019) while they discussed how a poor leadership strategy can harm the service overall. Their paper identifies problematic leadership behaviours, including micromanagement, managing up rather than down, a lack of career and personal support, and reactive management, based on interviews with 26 New Zealand public managers and employees as well as two focus groups. These callous actions don't hurt others dramatically or usually on purpose, but they do demonstrate disrespect for subordinates. The knowledge obtained from the focus groups and interviews sheds light on how public sector environments might foster incompetent leadership that impedes employee growth and hinders innovation in the workplace. Another similar study has been conducted by Aravena (2019) in the public sector organisation of Chile and found a negative impact of an incompetent leadership approach on employee performance and organizational culture. Both these papers create further scope for the current research to investigate as there is a gap in the research on public sector innovation and how leadership is having an impact be it positive or negative in the context of developing countries and specifically Bangladesh.

2.4 Review of literature in Bangladeshi Public sector context:

Bangladesh is an emerging economy and recently, many studies are being conducted to understand the various aspects of government organizations and how they can innovate. Being a developing country, Bangladeshi citizens currently largely depend on the private sector or NGOs for service delivery because of the ease of access. Slowly, the public sector is taking the initiative to provide better, cheaper, and more efficient services to the people. Therefore, researchers are taking an interest in various innovative approaches by the government.

Shaheen et al (2012) have analyzed the importance of innovation in the food industry by the government. The paper looks into ways to mitigate the crisis when the government decided to bring the market under its direct control which again relaxed the open market system. Under the severe crisis of fertilizer conditions prevailing in Bangladesh, opportunities remain for the expansion of organic farming to reduce the use of chemical fertilizers.

Zaman (2015) discussed the government-owned one-stop information access point (a2i) and it is creating a new door for service delivery to citizens. This article provides a brief overview of the access to an information system which is partly implemented in the country at the moment and plans to offer some services which would normally take a long time and frequent visits to different local government institutions. In a recent joint study with the World Bank, Faguet (2007) examined the institutions and service delivery models responsible for combating hunger, mortality, disease and discrimination. It proposes some policy reforms and strategies to achieve the human development goal in Bangladesh with the assistance of the private sector and NGOs.

A recent paper by Mondal, Kemp and Pachova (2010) identifies some of the barriers that need to be overcome for the successful development of the renewable energy technology sector and the betterment of rural livelihoods. It does so through a critical review of policy and institutional settings, as well as present status and lessons learnt from a pilot demonstration of several RET projects undertaken by different organizations.

Dr Salahuddin (2010) in his recent government policy formation report has highlighted the service delivery innovation challenges in rural areas of Bangladesh. He mentioned that advocates of decentralization in developing countries argue that bringing government closer to the people will make it more responsive and hence more likely to develop policies and outputs which meet the needs of ordinary citizens — the majority of whom are ‘the poor. The evidence for this proposition is systematically compared across a selection of African, Asian and Latin American countries, concluding that responsiveness to the poor is quite a rare outcome, determined mainly by the politics of local-central relations. Positive outcomes are mainly associated with a strong commitment by a national government or party to promoting the interests of the poor at the local level.

Adam et al (2013), talked about the policy reform to innovate the healthcare sector of the country. Azam (2007); Tahmin & Khan (2012); Sharif & Kumar (2012) have all analysed the complications and opportunities of e-government initiation. Khalid (2011) has emphasized

innovating the education and examination system to improve the education level in the rural areas of Bangladesh and Menon (2002) talked about the importance of innovation in waste management in the Dhaka City Corporation area.

It can be observed that most of the studies discuss policy reforms and regulations or talk mostly about technological transformation only. They capture the real situation in terms of understanding what is going wrong and how it can be improved; but there's no current study in the context of the Bangladeshi public sector that talks about how innovation occurs at the service or product level, what non-technological internal and external barriers they go through before implementation and how leadership can impact/ mitigate the issues with the process and successful implementation. This current study hopes to analyze that.

One notable work was conducted by Tahrnia and Jaegal (2012) where they focussed on the challenges of government innovation and proposed some strategies to overcome them. This work, although captures a similar concept to the current study, fails to acknowledge the internal challenges of any public sector organization and only focuses on the external factors. Again, the strategies recommended are solely based on secondary research, so it does not capture the real-life dilemma of the sector managers or employees. The current study hopes to fulfil this gap.

Another study by Bhuiyan (2011), discovered that different government agencies' eService initiatives are dispersed, and there are currently no linked services, resulting in repetitive work for most government information systems. He stated that, while the use of E-services has increased, their long-term viability will be a challenge in Bangladesh if infrastructure issues (lack of internet connectivity, insufficient power supply) are not addressed concurrently. If suitable legal frameworks (e.g., electronic payment, electronic ID) cannot be established, the maturity level of E-services would stay stagnant. However, this study was almost done 10 years ago and thus needs a fresh approach to investigating the current state of the innovation in public service delivery which the present research is looking to fill the gap.

The researchers of Tilburg University and Radboud University, funded by the British Department for International Development (DFID), recently completed another similar study for developing countries, including Bangladesh for the period 2013-2017. The goal of the project was to learn about the factors, institutions, and policies that can boost business innovation and product development, particularly in manufacturing small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs). The study was divided into two categories or themes: 'Innovation Systems'

and 'Finance for Productivity Growth.' The project's joint quantitative and qualitative research methods, which include corporate surveys, randomised control trials (RCTs), and case studies, are key elements of the research. According to the results, the majority of the interviewed organization owners and managers implemented new products, procedures, and technologies in various ways to develop and extend their business operations. The majority of innovation is motivated by consumer demand. The business climate in Bangladesh is challenging, according to most of the SME owners and managers interviewed. Quite a few of them have a negative impression of the government's rapid changes in policies and regulations. These reforms are unclear, and SME owners must navigate the regulations on their own.

The current research takes inspiration from this work with a case study approach and innovation research in the public sector as the research conducted by Tilburg University and Radboud University, funded by British Department for International Development (DFID) took the private sector organisations into account only. Furthermore, the economic and market viewpoint is the primary subject in the British study whereas the current study aims to provide managerial solutions.

The research regarding the Bangladeshi leadership style is mostly political at the moment. 95% of public sector-related research is about the reformation of the public sector (*Zahan, 2006; Ferdousi & Qui, 2013; Sarker, Binxin & Pradhan, 2017*) and Corruption, governance, and E-Governance (*Mahmood, 2010; Zafarullah & Siddique, 2001; Sarker, 2006*). Some leadership research can be found but those are limited to the educational Sector (*Sperandio, 2005*), Private investment in the public sector (*Haque, 2013*), tourism and hospitality (*Ali & Parvin, 2010*) or challenges in the public sector leadership (*Mohammad & Shahrer, 2014*).

Again, most of these researches conducted are based on purely secondary data sources and very few of them conducted interviews and surveys. This current study wishes to use different methods to analyze the situation. The article by Mohammad and Sharrer (*2014*) reviewed the current leadership practices in public sector organizations of Bangladesh and concluded that the existing political interference and corruption are the major impediments to developing strong leadership personnel other than political leaders. Lack of proper training and absence of monitoring are also affecting the growth of leadership practice. This study, although it creates a platform for further research like this current one, it fails in terms of reliability as it only observed the situation from secondary data sources and thus failed to capture the real picture.

A recent study by Alam, Rahman, Teicher and Van Gramber (2017) looks at the issues of public sector leadership in Bangladesh from the context of being a developing country. By evaluating data acquired through interviews with 87 middle and senior public workers, they used a qualitative research design to investigate how people perceive leadership. Hierarchies, high centralization, political patronage, and an overall intolerance to change, according to the findings, presented problems for leadership to be effective. This study created a lot of scope for the current research and encouraged the researcher to investigate more into the matter to find out solutions for improving the existing practices, This paper did not take into account the aspect of the public sector innovation process and how the identified factors of leadership impact them. The current research is looking to fill the gap by bringing these two dimensions of the topic together.

Hernandez (2019) in his paper discussed key barriers to digitalizing services in Bangladesh however it primarily focuses on Internet usage and mobile phone ownership connectivity constraints and therefore, does not include any non-technological challenges of digital innovation. Furthermore, the discussion is an overall analysis of Bangladesh and does not specifically address the public or private sector. This study creates substantial scope for the current study to fill the gap by considering non-technological factors contributing to the outcome of innovation projects in the public sector.

Panir, Xiaolin & Zijun's (2019) study substantial contribution to the understanding of how knowledge management and innovation are integrated with ICT. This study provides some insights into how knowledge might be creatively managed in public sector organisations in a digital context. However, it does not consider the barriers to integrating ICT into public sector service delivery and creates a scope for further research to identify key challenges that public sector organisations may encounter throughout the transformation and the present research aims to fill this void.

Zaman (2021) in his most recent policy reform paper explores the implications for practitioners and academics establishing programmes for public sector managers to implement citizen-centric innovations, such as capacity-building training programmes. This paper although, presents some stimulating ideas about training bureaucrats and public sector managers to behave more emphatically and drive innovation, does not take into account the factors that are hindering the successful delivery of innovation and whether or not the recommended training programme has got the features to accommodate specific leadership

requirements to tackle the challenges in various phases of innovation projects. It thus presents a gap in the literature to look into possible leadership frameworks that may be included in the programme to overcome innovation barriers in the public sector which is the key objective of the current research.

Abedin, Ferdous, Shah & Sayem (2021) discovered using principal component and correlation analysis that people's easy accessibility promotes citizen empowerment by eliminating the information gap, delivering high-quality services at an affordable cost, and reducing time-cost-visit. This paper is a recent attempt to fill the gap in researching digitalized public services and how it's effectively improving user experience but like many previous pieces of research, it is only taking account of the user experience and their perspective on what worked for them. It does not discuss anything about the challenges the project encountered before implementation and the current study aims to fill the gap.

Chowdhury (2020) in his study, elaborates on the necessity of leadership to build strong democratic establishments to increase public faith in government bodies and transform processes digitally. He concludes that it is difficult to streamline complicated bureaucracies without causing some type of disruption along the way, thus the initiative to develop that digital infrastructure can only happen with top-down leadership. Here, in his study, he discusses the importance of leadership from the top down but does not take a detailed approach on the potential side effects of only taking the top-down approach or does not take into account any other leadership approach. Thus the limitation creates further curiosity in this area to identify whether the top-down approach is best suitable for generating public sector digital innovation in Bangladesh and the current study is wishing to fill this gap in the literature. This paper wishes to look into the overall impact leadership has on innovation projects and how it influences barriers occurring in each phase.

The discussion above gives an overall idea of the key pieces of literature surrounding public sector leadership and innovation in the public sector. It can be observed that the research into public sector leadership behaviour from an innovation perspective is few and far between. Some recent studies although manages to address the issue, in comparison with other developing countries to address the connection between public sector innovation and leadership taking a complete qualitative approach is fairly new and thus creates a possibility for further investigation to bring together all these dimensions in one paper. The current research is

looking into contributing to the existing literature by addressing the gap as well as recommending strategies to implement the findings into practice.

2.5 Summary of the Chapter:

The chapter examines important works in the disciplines of public sector leadership and innovation to compile comprehensive information on existing research on innovation, its characteristics, problems, and how leadership influences innovation. Although public sector innovation is a relatively new notion in academia, the researchers agree that it demands similar levels of relevance in innovation research as the private sector. Researchers have recently highlighted public sector leadership as a topic of interest, as public sector organisations continue to become more innovative, and leaders play a critical role in managing and fostering innovation. Bangladesh, being a developing country, has seen some government inventions in recent years, hence research on public sector innovation and the importance of leaders in managing innovation barriers are minimal. The gaps identified below in the existing literature have paved a way for the current research to make contributions and explore new possibilities-

- The majority of public sector innovation research is either mixed-method, entirely quantitative, looked at innovation from the perspective of citizens, or focused solely on external catalysts.
- Tahrmia and Jaegal (2012), focused on external barriers to government innovation and proposed some solutions to address them using secondary research. Internal problems and organisational culture were not addressed.
- Alam, Rahman, Teicher and Van Gramber (2017) look at the issues of public sector leadership in Bangladesh from the context of being a developing country. This paper did not take into account the aspect of the public sector innovation process and how leadership impacts them.
- Chowdhury (2020) discusses the significance of top-down leadership in his study, but he does not go into great length on any possible negative effects of this technique or any other leadership approach.
- Abedin, Ferdaus, Shah, and Sayem (2021) studied the impact of digitising public services on user experience, but like many earlier studies, it solely considered the user experience and their perspective on what worked for them.
- Zaman (2021) offers some inspiring ideas in his most recent policy reform paper about how to train public sector managers and bureaucrats to act more passionately and

promote innovation, but he neglects to consider the factors that prevent innovation from being successfully delivered and whether the suggested training programme has the features to accommodate particular leadership requirements to address the challenges in various phases of innovation projects.

- There is a gap in the research on public sector innovation and how leadership is having an impact, be it positive or negative, in the context of developing countries, specifically Bangladesh. Franklin and Plimmer and Aravena's and Aravena's (2019) research on the negative impact of leadership on public sector innovation creates further scope for the current research to investigate.
- To understand potential obstacles to government innovation in post-Soviet Uzbekistan, Kuldosheva (2021) performed a study utilising a survey. He concluded, nonetheless, that in-person or one-on-one in-depth interviews with government officials could offer a more complete picture of the current institutional environment and e-government challenges. To better understand the underlying causes of why some digital endeavours are successful while others are not, as well as how management style influences these outcomes, more thorough research is needed using in-depth one-to-one interviews.

The following chapter will develop and explore a conceptual framework based on the important variables found in the literature research to better understand the obstacles to innovation, as well as provide some guidelines for data collecting and analysis.

Chapter 3. Conceptual Framework

3.1 Introduction:

According to a study presented by Miles and Huberman (1994); conceptual frameworks can be useful to understand the overall direction of the research as it portrays- What factors/stakeholders will be included in the study, the relationship between the variables based on the literature review, ongoing research or personal experience and provides an opportunity for the researcher to collect rational ideas from the points presented in the framework. The conceptual framework represents a direction for data collection and interpretation. The framework below has been generated to understand the challenges of innovation in Bangladeshi Public Sector service delivery; based on the researcher's point of view, news sources and, a review of existing literature. The framework was under development and continued to develop as the study progressed and the relationships between the proposed factors developed. A final conceptual framework has therefore been formed including all the themes that developed from the review of the literature.

The major components can be presented in the following way:

Figure 3.1: Conceptual Framework (Source: Author)

The conceptual framework can be simply divided into three parts for the sake of discussion-

- Innovation Process
- Internal factors impacting/affecting innovation

- External Factors Impacting/affecting innovation

Figure 3.2: Simplified Conceptual Framework (Source: Author)

3.2 Innovation Process:

The completion of a three-stage process for successful innovation is concept creation, acceptance, and implementation (Shepard, 1967). To date, much of the research has concentrated on the network's ability to produce new ideas (Goes & Park, 1997; Hardy et al., 2003 mentioned in Swan & Scarbrough, 2005). Two key outcomes or expectations serve as a reminder of why public sector innovation is critical.

First, in the public sector, innovation can be described as a novel concept or solution to a problem that challenges conventional wisdom (Light, 1998). According to Becker and Whisler (1967), innovation is described as the initial discovery of a new concept or technique. Similarly, an invention must be an initial pioneering act, as Laurence Lynn describes it (Light, 1998). Second, in the public sector, creativity can serve two purposes: 1) to advance the public good and 2) to generate public value. Whereas in the private sector, an invention needs to be profitable to be worthwhile; in the public sector, innovation must be about doing something worthwhile, argues Paul Light (1998).

The innovation process in Bangladesh goes through many levels of authority before reaching the final stage; the different levels and their impacts will be discussed in the later parts of the chapter. The broader framework of Bangladeshi public policy is provided by the Sixth Five Year Plan (SFYP). One of the plan's main guiding concepts is to meet the goals outlined in

Bangladesh's Vision 2041, which focuses on achieving various degrees of innovations, including the effective delivery of the a2i programme.

The cabinet, ministries, parliament, political parties, bureaucracy, non-governmental organisations and civil society organisations, the commercial sector, the media, and the international donor community are all key stakeholders in Bangladesh's policy formulation process. Innovation is frequently sparked by a prompt or trigger that makes it conceivable, required, or desirable. A crisis, cost difficulties, or political demands can all compel innovation. The major process takes place in Bangladesh's many ministries. They are self-contained administrative units tasked with doing government business in specific, defined areas.

Figure 3.3: Innovation Process at the primary level (Source: Author)

A minister is responsible for the policy matters that concern his or her ministry, as well as the implementation of those policies, for each ministry. It then goes to the cabinet, which is the highest decision-making body. To formulate the project and budget allocation, the national economic council (NEC) and the planning commission participate in the decision-making step. When the project has been accepted by the ministries, it is forwarded to the appropriate government organizations—city corporations or local government bodies—for a small sphere test to determine success or failure.

In recent years, the government has taken various steps to facilitate innovative thinking among the population and at different ministry levels. Awards and showcases have been organised to appreciate the creative projects. According to a storey published on October 21, 2018, by a prominent news source The Daily Star, for innovation to take shape in Bangladesh, BIC (Bangladesh Innovation Conclave) organised the 1st Bangladesh Innovation Award, where 19 top ideas were presented in a big award banquet on October 20, 2018. As mentioned in the source, the award was created to honour the thriving community of innovators – from start-ups to established businesses – as well as their ground-breaking products and ideas. The award

programme aims to boost Bangladesh's economy by recognising creative minds and stimulating innovation inside it by rewarding outstanding innovations from start-ups and veterans alike.

The program marked the opening of four Innovation Centres throughout Bangladesh's four divisions, with the objectives of advancing innovation throughout the country and among its people. Bangladesh Innovation Blog has also started its website. However, there is a wide gap between some of the initiatives and the cultural adoption and reception all across the country.

The main concept of the current research is to understand the challenges of this innovation process and how they can be mitigated. Innovation, according to Van De Ven (1985), is a multi-level and collective achievement. Moreover, numerous social and cognitive processes are interrelated at the levels where innovation occurs. Most innovative ideas are lost in the bureaucratic process. Because Bangladesh is still a developing country, political and bureaucratic complexity play an important influence in any decision. A recent study found, that almost 85% of the decision-making in the public sector is controlled by bureaucrats (e.g.: the cabinet, the planning department, ministers, etc).

Although the bureaucracy level appears to have influenced and evolved the innovation process a more external factor that directly affects the organisation and its strategies as well as the innovation process—the other internal and external aspects cannot be overlooked. Internal factors such as culture, resources, and leadership within the ministry play a significant role in idea generation, whereas external factors such as international pressure, private sector counterparts, political pressures, economic downturn, and target audience acceptance work behind the initial need for any innovation. The next section will focus on the internal cultural, managerial, and employee perspectives followed by the major external perspective of the problem.

3.3 Internal Factors:

At the administrative level, overlap and duplication of functions, oversight of regulations, inconsistent and contradictory rules, inefficient information flow, insufficient inter-agency consultation, inadequate delegation of authority, and delays in decision-making, combine to affect both policy and administrative performance (*Zafarullah & Huque, 1998*).

As mentioned in the previous section, to bring about a change the public sector should invest and innovate more. This section will look at internal complexities an organization goes through

in Bangladesh which affect innovative behaviour. Wright et al (2001) have argued that interaction, behaviours, employees' motivation, organizational culture, resources and effective management practices influence the performance of firms.

3.3.1 Leadership and management practices:

Leadership has two dimensions. The first is task orientation. It includes goal setting, scheduling, directing, coordinating, setting standards, and supervising the performance of workers. The other dimension of leadership is relationship orientation. This deals with empathy, feelings, trust, appreciation, and allowing subordinates to participate in making decisions (Lewis, Goodman & Fandt, 2001).

Leadership is central to organizational culture, which plays a key role as the creator of the culture's underlying assumptions (Reimann & Oedewald, 2002). These sets of behavioural components guide employees' attitudes and behaviours in organizations (Davis, 1984; Denison, 1990; Kotter & Heskett, 1992; O'Reilly & Chatman, 1996 mentioned in Wilson, 2001).

A major impediment to innovation is a lack of systematic administration within ministries and other government agencies. In Bangladesh, according to Tahrira and Jaegal (2012), there is a lack of a unique managerial method, ambiguity about technological priorities, a complicated decision-making process, confusion about policy-making roles, a lack of prompt and effective policy execution, a lack of control and supervision, and lack of control and monitoring discourages public sector firms from acting spontaneously, creates uncertainty for future projects, and has a detrimental impact on the country's innovation climate. A study by Arimato & Kurata (2018) found that the adoption of management methods may be hampered by a lack of understanding of basic management techniques among the public sector managers in Bangladesh. They identified that a manager's leadership qualities, cognition, job security, employee autonomy, and job-related knowledge and skills all influence management techniques. Besides, leaders of public sector organisations in Bangladesh lack a strategic vision, making government innovation and development a challenging task.

3.3.2 Organisational Factors:

3.3.2.1 Organisational Culture:

Organizational culture plays an important role in organizations because it adds customer value, introduces flexibility and change, and sets employees' values (Daft, 2003). Hofstede, Hofstede, and Minkov (2010) described culture as "mental programming" or "software of the mind." It

is shared patterns of thinking, feeling, and acting. Therefore, it is always a collective phenomenon. The patterns of thinking, feeling, and acting differentiate one group of people from others. The patterns of thinking, feeling, and acting come from the unwritten rules of the social game. The understanding of culture given by Hofstede et al. (2010) is similar to that of Pettigrew (1979), who defined it as a “system of such publicly and collectively accepted meanings operating for a given group at a given time” and provides “a general sense of orientation” to the group.

As mentioned by Muzakkir Hossain in a recent article published in Dhaka Tribune in 2016, Bangladesh has seen two distinct forms of office culture in its brief history: the relaxing government office and the fast-paced private sector atmosphere. This article acknowledges the slow environment of public sector organisations by mentioning the gradual decline of rigid workplace culture and autocratic leadership practices in the private sector. Government organisations may differ from private sector organisations in terms of efficiency as this sector sees more complexity, more authority, and control over choices by bureaucrats, as well as lower employee motivation. Public sector employees in Bangladesh have an inaccurate perception of the risk associated with generating or implementing new ideas, which inhibits their motivation to innovate. They overlook the fact that innovation is fundamentally risky, and that taking risks is an important feature of innovation.

Jamil (2002) investigated administrative culture in Bangladesh to discover the dominant culture and its repercussions, as well as the drivers of administrative subcultures. He stated that public sector organisations vary from private sector organisations in that politics plays a significant role in them. Alom (2019) lately published a study that examines how Bangladesh's frontline public bureaucracy reflects the country's entire public service. These front-line workers are classified into two categories based on their recruitment: Cadre and Non-cadre. He suggested that any study of public sector organisational culture must consider its external context, i.e., how it interacts with politics and society in general.

3.3.2.2 Resources:

Internal resources both tangible and intangible, play an important part in shaping organisational activities and motivating innovation to take place. Presently, Bangladesh's public administration is mainly centralised, with an excessive reliance on hierarchy and several layers of decision-making. Human resource planning is almost non-existent, and while postings change often, interdepartmental mobility is uncommon. Bangladesh needs a skilled workforce

as well as government aid and incentives to establish a knowledge-based society. However, among the ministries and other government bodies, the country lacks a firm basis of technologically skilled, experienced, and well-organized government officials, which is impeding government innovation. According to a former study by Taifur (2004), it was discovered that within the ministries and other government bodies, there's a significant lack of qualified staff who can take part in building a digitalised and more citizen-friendly service.

3.3.2.3 Recruitment, performance measurement and scope of training:

Different governments in Bangladesh have implemented key rules governing the structural and functional aspects of Bangladesh public service under the constitutional framework. This includes the Bangladesh Civil Service (Recruitment) Policies of 1981, the Government Servant (Discipline and Appeal) Act of 1985, the Government Servant Conduct Policies of 1979, the Government Servant Special Provision Ordinance of 1979, and the Public Servant Retirement Regulation of 1974, among others (Alam,2015).

Currently, there are essentially no incentives in place to stimulate innovation and recognise excellence. The current performance management method is inefficient and subjective. The promotion process is mostly politicised to date: the government frequently promotes partisan loyalists, and under-qualified officers, denying well-performing personnel. Training has nothing to do with career planning or other aspects of human management. Career prospects are often limited to a cadre, and hence are dissimilar (Memon et al, 2019). Overtly politicised PSC leadership leads to politicised recruitment; training institutions lack qualified and well-trained employees, as well as professionalism; and training methods, tactics, and curriculum are obsolete, denying learners the opportunity to expand their knowledge and capacity (Paul,2017).

Additionally, it has been found that civil officials that are underpaid are prone to corruption and have low morale. The disciplinary standards are outdated, the consequences are light, and the disciplinary procedure is lengthy, preventing complainants and departments from taking action (Alam,2015).

3.4 External Factors:

3.4.1 Socio-Economic Factors:

Almost half of Bangladesh's population is poor. Uncertainty about one's survival provides no

room for consideration of the country. Scarcity causes many people to engage in illicit activities, causing social unrest. These social conditions stifle creativity among society members, especially public officials and administrators, and impede economic growth and social progress. Government innovation in Bangladesh is hampered by people's lack of comprehension, which is a result of poor education and literacy rates in the village and coastal areas. The current government has set up e-governance facilities in several government offices and utility centres, but most people are unaware of them, which is a hurdle to the program's adoption.

Again, Bangladesh is significantly reliant on imports, particularly in the field of specialised industrial machinery. As a result, industrial costs are high, and a large portion of foreign funds is used to cover import expenses, further deteriorating the country's already bad balance of payments. Lack of specialised research and training services, fluctuating raw material prices, and excessive inflation are all contributing factors to obstruct innovation in the public sector.

3.4.2 Bureaucratic and Political Factors:

Political leaders abuse their power and position to exert control over personnel management choices such as transfers, promotions, and recruiting, as well as encouraging the public officials to engage in corrupt actions. Personnel management decisions are based on a person's political party loyalty rather than on quality and efficiency. Furthermore, the relationship between professional and political cadres may result in less information transmission, less responsiveness to people's needs and expectations, and less organisational creativity. The political systems grabbed control of the bureaucracy by appointing party bureaucrats regardless of their qualifications. Political instability is a big issue in developing countries which directly creates a challenging condition for any innovation to take place. There are numerous issues regarding how Bangladesh's public bureaucracy operates. The bureaucracy has gotten engulfed in opaque and damaging practices. Financial illiteracy, deterioration of law and order, insecurity of individual rights, and violations of regulations on the road and in a wide variety of activities have all become commonplace in national life. These are the outcomes of an opportunistic attitude to governance obligation (*Sarker, 2006*). According to a recent report published by Human Rights Watch (2020), Bangladesh is going through turmoil. Security forces' violations, such as enforced disappearances and extrajudicial killings, remained unpunished. In its attack on government critics, the administration continues to breach international principles on freedom of expression.

Bangladesh's administrative system has been beset with dysfunctions since its foundation, owing to organisational and procedural difficulties at both political and bureaucratic levels. The governmental process is further complicated by the lack of clarity in the relationship between the two, which can lead to difficulties in coordinating and integrating policymaking and execution. Currently, the government is collaborating with the corporate and non-profit sectors to resolve the issues. However, this effort is failing in several ways; Bangladesh's economy is receiving international investment, but it is mostly focused on the textiles sector and exports (Cao, Clarke & Lehane, 2000; OECD, 2002; Eusuf et al., 2007). Other industries have received insufficient attention to date due to the difficulties of government policies and bureaucratic complications. Again, because of bureaucratic complexity, delays in the tendering process, setbacks in land acquisition, and retention of cash, the projects will not be completed on time. This as a result increases the cost of the projects and limits their outcomes.

3.4.3 Environmental Factors:

Environmental imbalance is one of the elements that has hampered and continues to hinder Bangladesh's development efforts. Bangladesh is positioned in the world's largest delta, which is formed by three major rivers: the Ganges, the Brahmaputra, and the Meghna. Drought, flood, waterlogging, cyclone and tidal surge, tornado, thunderstorm, river/coastal erosion, landslides, saline intrusion, hailstorm, extreme weather events, as well as other natural catastrophes are common in the nation. Approximately 26,000 sq km, or 18% of the country, is flooded each year. During massive flooding, the impacted area can reach 52,000 sq km, or 36% of the country's land area and roughly 60% of the net cultivable area. This affects the economy as well as damages the infrastructure and the wellbeing of citizens and thus, impacts the financial resources greatly. Additionally, each year Bangladesh faces some seasonal disease outbreaks like Dengue, Cholera, Chikungunya, Nipah Virus etc. which cause significant damage to the national economy. For a growing country like Bangladesh, deciding whether to prioritise growth or the environmental aspect is a challenging task (Rafi et al, 2020).

The COVID-19 pandemic produced by SARS-CoV-2 has seen a rapid increase in the number of infected people, as well as a high fatality rate, making it a global public health concern. Bangladesh has been infected with the virus since March 8, 2020. Since then, people have become infected at such a rapid rate that the country has risen to the top of the list of the world's most contaminated countries (Rahman et al., 2021). The lockdown has caused a 6 percentage point decline in Bangladesh's economy in 2020 compared to 2019 (IMF, 2020). Because

Bangladesh's economic growth has not been inclusive, the country's progress in recent decades has not been able to prevent impoverished people from becoming extremely destitute (*Hossain,2021*). Barriers to combating Covid-19 included a lack of resources and medical facilities, as well as insufficient testing facilities, personal protective equipment (PPE), and other safety measures. Furthermore, the crisis was made more severe by public knowledge and attitude, social distance issues, price hikes, and natural calamities. The situation demanded more investment in the field of healthcare and pharmaceutical research and therefore impacted the budget of government-led innovation massively (*Islam et al, 2020*).

3.5 Summary of the Chapter:

The above chapter gives a clear and concise idea about the variables that play a direct or indirect role in the innovation process as a whole. The main points have been derived from an extensive literature review and analysis of current news sources regarding government innovation projects. These themes or points mentioned in this chapter are just a guidance of what kind of findings may generate from the collected data. In the next chapter, a detailed discussion will take place about the methodology of the research. The chapter will talk about the researcher's philosophy in perceiving the research area, justify the method of conducting the data collection and analyse the findings to find the research objectives of this innovation-leadership study.

Chapter 4: Research Design

4.1 Introduction:

Research design works as a blueprint of the whole research. Based on the research questions and objectives, the researcher is taking the ontological assumption, which is subjective, the research philosophy being pragmatism. The qualitative research method of this study will take on the Case study approach to understand the situation and provide a practical contribution as well as contribute to the existing gaps in the literature. The goal of this chapter is to ensure that the data will be collected and analyzed in a systematic way to accurately answer the research questions and meet the objectives of the study as stated by Belk, Green, and Tull, (1978). This chapter will go through all the sections one by one- first shed light on the summary and the justification of the research belief and philosophy, followed by discussing the aspects of qualitative study and case study approach. This chapter will focus on which case studies are taken into consideration and how the data will be analyzed to gain an understanding of the research questions and objectives thoroughly.

4.2 Research Philosophy:

According to Saunders, Lewis & Thornhill (2019) in their book, the term research philosophy is a combination of different techniques, a system of assumptions and beliefs of the researcher about the knowledge and understanding of a matter or study. As Burrell and Morgan (2016) suggested, a researcher is bound to make assumptions about the matter, either consciously or not, and is related to the assumptions of the reality of the situation in which the research will be conducted, about the human knowledge or the extent to which the researcher will impact the research based on his own beliefs. This process, later, helps the researcher to understand the research questions, choose a research method and decide on the techniques to interpret those findings (Crotty, 1998; as mentioned in Saunders et al, 2018).

According to Marsh & Furlong (2002), ontology and epistemology are like skin as they provide guidance on how to choose theory and method in research, they cannot or should not be worn as an occasional garment. For this reason, the researcher must acquire the knowledge to recognize the vision and understand the context and setting where the research will take place and from which perspective, he/she will assess and validate the findings. Ontological and epistemological philosophies are important to determine the philosophical positioning of a researcher and the cases he wishes to choose for the research. These philosophical positioning

may not change from case to case. however, can certainly change with time for the researcher (*Takahashi and Arujo, 2019*).

4.2.1 The ontological and epistemological Assumption:

According to the conventional perspective, the social sciences are generally analogous to the natural sciences, and researchers who take this stance are therefore interested in figuring out laws governing human behaviour (*Schulze, 2003; Krauss, 2005*). Only when the reader has sufficient comprehension of the philosophical foundations (i.e., principles) and theoretical presumptions of the field can social research be effectively and appropriately interpreted (*Heberlein 1988; Mascia et al. 2003; Newing 2010*). This claim is supported by the observation that each field has its own set of guiding principles and presumptions that are applied to the planning, execution, analysis, and interpretation of research and its results (*Moon & Blackman, 2014*). The epistemological and methodological positions of research begin from a starting point. According to Grix (2002), this starting point is Ontology. The definition of ontology as described in the dictionaries of philosophy is a discipline that is concerned with what already exists (*Cambridge 2020; Oxford 2020*). Ontology normally is associated with one of the branches of metaphysics and thus the idea around it revolves around finding answers to the questions about real phenomena whose reality is beyond the capabilities of scientific methods. it asks questions about the most general must-have attributes of anything to be an entity or being. Ontology, according to Richards (2003), is the presumptions individuals have about the nature and type of reality and the entities which exist. Ontology is sometimes referred to as the character of the world and what it is possible for humans to know, according to Snape and Spencer (2003). Furthermore, Bryman (2008) introduces the notion of social ontology, which he characterises as a philosophical angle taken into account in research about the nature of social phenomena (*Al-Saadi, 2014*). Ontological assumptions are about the nature of reality, although sometimes may seem too far-fetched in front of the actual subject or field of research. However, in the field of business and management, this philosophical standpoint is very much relevant as it shapes the way of the researcher's visualization and perception of the research objects (*Saunders et al, 2019*).- in the current research scenario, it will be the organizations, employees, organizational values and cultures and different projects.

In this current study, the reason behind taking on this assumption is to look beyond the typical hurdles that may come in the way of launching or implementing innovation in the workplace and how to simply eliminate them, but to focus on how different chosen organizations work

and what best approaches can be utilized to benefit them or give them the knowledge of preventing the challenges in the first place.

Epistemology, on the other hand, focuses on the procedures of gathering knowledge and validating them, the main philosophy is centred around a theory of knowledge (*Grix, 2002*). From a positivist's point of view, a social phenomenon is an entity of causal relations where only a single truth exists which needs to be identified, confirmed, and validated. In this tradition of philosophy, case studies test hypotheses and use deductive approaches along with quantitative data collection and analysis. According to Neuman (2003), positivism views social science as a disciplined approach for integrating deductive reasoning with exact empirical observations of individual behaviour to identify and validate a set of probabilistic causal laws that can be applied to forecast broad trends in human behaviour (*Tuli, 2010*). According to positivists, the characteristics of social reality are as follows: empirical facts are independent of one's ideas or beliefs; they are governed by the laws of cause and effect (*Ahmed & Ahmed, 2014*); social reality patterns are constant, and knowledge of them is additive (*Crotty, 1998; Neuman, 2003; Marczyk, DeMatteo, and Festinger, 2005*). For the field of anthropology and social observation-based qualitative research, scholars have decided on some alternative versions of epistemologies as the world of reality is an ever-changing process. Since the 1970s, management studies have gradually adopted qualitative methods and have developed a wide range of research concepts based on the observation of individuals and society (*Godoy, 1995; as mentioned in Takahashi and Arujo, 2019*).

The exact opposite ideology of positivism is interpretivism. An interpretive-constructivist perspective sees the world as being constructed, interpreted, and experienced by people in their interactions with one another and with larger social systems (*Maxwell, 2006; Bogdan & Biklen, 1992; Guba and Lincoln, 1985; Merriam, 1988*). This perspective serves as the theoretical foundation for the majority of qualitative research. Following this paradigm, an investigation's nature is interpretive and its goal is to comprehend a specific occurrence, not to generalise to a population (*Farzanfar, 2005*). This tradition argues that there is no single absolute truth that needs to be discovered in the social and business world. the knowledge of the world and how it works is the result of different social constructions (*Tuli, 2010*). Thus, the social world as it is known is constructed of interactions and the interpretation of the knowledge cannot exist without the researcher's knowledge. Hence, there is no single truth, the reality can have multiple facades and depends on the way somebody looks at it (*Marsh & Furlong, 2002*).

The suggestion would be that it is not possible to assess and persevere this social phenomenon through objective or detached methods like deductive approaches, hypothesis testing, and quantitative methods (*Brinkmann & Tanggaard, 2010*). These methods will be irrelevant as the mechanisms and relationships of these social interactions need to be studied thoroughly. Hermeneutics or interpretivism will have relevance because this method allows the researcher's interpretation of data, actions, and observations, even though it reflects the "truth" of the subject. Ethnographic case studies, interviews, and observations as data collection techniques are applicable to the research designs according to interpretivism (*Ulin, Robinson and Tolley, 2004, Takahashi and Arujo, 2019*).

Pragmatism, on the other hand, is a deconstructive paradigm that supports the use of a mixture of different research methods. It puts aside the argument over truth and reality (*Feilzer 2010*) and focuses on what works on finding the truth under the research investigations (*Tashakkori & Teddlie 2003*). Thus, pragmatism rejects taking part in the conflict between two opposing viewpoints of interpretivism and positivism. Pragmatism is suitable for social research as it does not regard the methods being used to collect and analyze data be it qualitative, quantitative, or mixed methods. It is relatively a new tradition and works as a replacement for the older theory or approaching knowledge and understanding of social research in terms of ontology, epistemology, and methodology (*Guba & Lincoln, 1994,2012*). A pragmatic approach to issue solving in the social environment, according to Feilzer (2010), provides an alternative, flexible, and more reflective framework for research design (*Kelly & Cordeiro,2020*). The reality, in the view of pragmatics, is not constant; it alters with each new development. The world, in a similar vein, is not static; rather, it is always changing. Action is the only means of affecting existence, hence actions also influence the world (*Maxcy 2003; Morgan 2014; Goldkuhl 2012*) as discussed in Kaushal and Walsh (2019). Its primary focus rests on the demonstration of the widened value of the research philosophy as well as the practical perspective on issues like research design. For example, Merriam (2009) acknowledges that if one is choosing a case study as a research design, one can choose both qualitative and quantitative methods; however, qualitative case studies require an induction reasoning approach and interpretation rather than testing hypotheses (*Ostman & Wickman, 2014*).

After the discussion of the philosophical standpoint of the researcher, it is important to determine the multidimensional continua along which the business and management research philosophies can be scattered (*Niglas, 2010; as mentioned in Saunders et al, 2019*). The nature

of the research is mostly subjective. As per Saunders (2019), Subjectivism includes the assumptions related to arts and humanities, emphasizing that the reality of society is made from the combinations of perceptions and actions taken by people who are the social actors. Ontologically speaking, subjectivism connects to nominalism or conventionalism which in its extreme form, considers the subjects we study are a creation of the researcher and other social actors through language, arts, perceptions, and actions. The subjectivist belief refers to discovering multiple realities rather than a single reality because each person perceives the world differently and their experience is different (*Burrell and Morgan, 2016*).

Subjectivists disagree with the notion that subject and object, observer and observed, or mind and world can be separated, arguing that each person views the world from a unique perspective that is motivated by their interests and goals (*Schwandt 1994; Pratt 1998; Powell 2001; stated in Moon & Blackman, 2014*). This is particularly important for the current research to embrace the subjective paradigm as it encourages us to see reality from multiple points of view (*Creswell, 2013*). The current research is based on the understanding of leadership practices in the public sector and how innovation in services is influenced by various factors. For the study, it is required to explore the experiences of people who are either the heads of various departments of different public sectors or work closely in the decision-making process. Another version of the subjectivist approach is social constructivism which is again another most efficient way to conduct the current research.

Social Constructivism relies on the interactions among the social actors and the researcher. Social interactions are a continuous process and therefore, the researcher must study the situation in detail, keeping in mind the historical, geographical, social and cultural contexts to understand what is happening or how realities are taking shape. As stated by Cunliffe (*2003*) and later mentioned by Saunders et al (*2019*) in their book, this way helps the research to understand different opinions and narratives. Since this study aims to conduct research among various stakeholders of the company and have a conversation on their perspective or experience of the situation, thinking in a socially constructive subjective way can help the researcher to understand the social reality of different stakeholders and reflect on their value and understanding of the situations.

4.3 Case Study- A Qualitative approach:

If taken a tour of history, it can be observed that the method of Qualitative study has always existed in social and scientific research, sometimes by having known a different term like ethnographic or interpretative research. Even when the founders of sociology- Simmel, Weber,

Durkheim, and Max were making their contributions during the age of Methodenstreit (“dispute about methods”), qualitative studies existed even when the scientific methods or quantitative approaches were given more emphasis. The most notable and extensive discussion of methods which later came to be recognized as the earliest version of qualitative methods was Bronisław Malinowski’s (1922) “Argonauts in the Western Pacific”, although this study does not quite address the meaning of “qualitative” in a detailed manner (*Aspers and Corte, 2019*).

As mentioned in Lazarsfeld and Barton (1982), in Weber’s work (1978) a tension was found between methods that were scientific in nature and methods or findings based on observation and interpretation. It was stated in Rawls (2018) that, post the second world war, the USA saw a rise in the critique of sociological work that depended on the philosophical aspect of the research. Despite all the confusion of definition and recognition as a proper research method, the use of qualitative methods has risen significantly in the last five decades (*Aspers and Corte, 2019*). Additionally, the methods have been developed and flourished, and many journals and books were published to emphasize its importance as well as criticized by many for example- Snow and Moril, (1995); Hood, (2006); Jovanović, (2011) for the lack of scientific evidence and by Goertz and Mahoney (2012), saying that the use of methods in the qualitative study makes it less standardized than the quantitative paradigm.

Denzin and Lincoln defined qualitative research as a formation of different methods which interpret and take a naturalistic approach to its subject matter. Flick (2018) mentioned in his book that qualitative research works as an umbrella term for several approaches and is not quite hard to design research as per the methods. It involves the perspective of the subjects being involved in the study without changing a setting, takes a more detailed route, and may involve the use of a variety of empirical materials such as a case study approach, personal experience or observation, introspective, life story, interviews and historical, interactional or visual texts to include the actual moments and meanings of the subjects’ lives (*McIntyre, 2004; Creswell, 2017*) and social events (*Bryman, 1989-as stated in Aspers and Corte, 2019*). Thus, the qualitative study is the most suited method for the current research as it aims to capture the bigger and more detailed picture through observations, interviews, and interpretation of the subjects’ perspectives.

The current study focuses on getting the factors affecting projects both internally and externally and how leadership can be implicated to overcome them. To identify this, leadership

approaches, personal objectives, behaviour, motivation, creativity everything needs to be studied closely which will not be captured by numbers only (quantitative study).

There are many empirical ways to conduct a qualitative study. The most common ones are fieldwork, ethnography, grounded theory, and case study. Ethnography can be described as the study of people and their daily lives (Aspers and Cortes, 2019), involvement of the resocialization of the researcher through the merging of both social worlds of the researcher and the subject (*Emerson, 1983; Hammersley 2018*). Fieldwork involves the method of research where the researcher gathers knowledge in the form of data by spending a considerable amount of time in the actual field of study (*Lofland, Snow, Anderson & Lofland, 2006*). Grounded theory is a systematic approach that requires researchers to get close to the field to discover new concepts or further distinctions of old concepts through detailed coding and other distinctive processes (*Glasser and Strauss, 2010*).

For the current study, the Case study method has been chosen and will be discussed in detail in later sections. A case study could be descriptive, exploratory, explanatory, single or multiple (*Yin, 2014*); intrinsic, instrumental, or collective (*Stake, 2006*); and confirm or build theory (*Eisenhardt, 1989; stated in Harrison et al, 2017*).

4.3.1 Defining Case Study Method:

Case study research has earned a reputation as an excellent tool for investigating and understanding complicated challenges in real-world situations, according to Harrison, Mills, Franklin, and Birks (2017). Case study designs have been employed in a variety of sectors of research, most notably in the social sciences, education, business, and public services, since they may address a wide range of research issues. The case study technique has evolved significantly over the previous four decades, with the introduction of a wide range of methodological approaches. Traditional methodologies, as well as the individual researcher's perspective, experience, and interpretations of the case, have influenced these modifications and signals of development.

Various authors have proposed different designs and definitions about how to prepare, plan, conduct, and interpret the findings to achieve the most suitable outcome (*Anthony & Jack, 2009*). There are a few definitions and descriptions that were presented in different publications- some describe it as a research method, and others define it as a research strategy (*Creswell, 1998*). Eisenhardt (1989) mentioned in Harrison et al (2017) talks about case study as a research strategy. The case study is a methodology that was introduced in the works of

Sharan Merriam and Robert Yin in the 1980s (*Merriam, 2009*). On the other hand, Stake (*2003*) explains case study not as a method but as a choice of the unit that needs to be researched (*Boblin, Ireland, Kirkpatrick, & Robertson, 2013*). As a result, while the case study has evolved into a reliable pragmatic approach to research, the variation in definition, application, validity, and relativity has created confusion among the researchers. However, regardless of the difference in their opinions, authors agree that case studies should be explained within a specific context as it tends to explore and analyze phenomena in a detailed manner.

A case study investigation is a qualitative method that enables the researcher to find important details regarding connected phenomena within the context of the participant's experience (Tellis, 1997). The case study focuses on experience, identifying new themes, using researcher interpretation of the data, applying dependable and credible data analysis, and ultimately stating the case's lessons learnt. The comprehensive discussion of the case context provides the reader of the study the capacity to judge if the case study may be applied in settings other than the one in which it was done (Coy, 2019). Yin (*2014*), Stake (*2003*), and Merriam (*2009*) provide the most widely accepted definitions of the case study. From a methodological standpoint, Yin provides a two-part definition that focuses on the scope, methods, and characteristics of case study research. He also stressed the empirical aspect of the study and the importance of the case's environment. Stake (*2003*), on the other hand, takes a different approach, focusing on what is researched as a case rather than how it is studied (the method). He uses a flexible yet cautious approach, never losing sight of the concept's core. Case study research, in his opinion, is the in-depth examination of a single case to comprehend its various facets. Merriam (*2009*) adopts a similar approach to Stakes, emphasising the importance of the case study research's most conspicuous component, namely the case or limited system. Adding to the definition, she also stated that case studies or investigations should be descriptive and interactive.

In his study of the escalation of numerous meanings and the resulting confusion, Flyvbjerg (*2011*) believes that the most appropriate strategy to be taken amongst all of this is to use a basic definition. He used the Merriam-Webster Dictionary's (*2009*) definition as an example, which captures the case study's main elements. A case study, according to the definition, is an in-depth examination of an individual unit (as a person, an event, or an organisation) that focuses on the development aspects of the environment in which it operates. These various definitions stem from the researchers' various approaches to creating case studies as a methodology, and they frequently reflect the core elements of their design. Given all of these

core features and many approaches to case study research, Creswell's (2017)'s definition appears to best capture the complete scope and significance of case study concepts and descriptions. A case study is defined as a technique, a method of constructing qualitative research, an object of the study, and a result of the inquiry (Harrison et al, 2019).

Case study analysis allows for the discovery and interpretation of complex topics by using findings from previous studies as well as taking new cases and comparing the findings. When comprehensive, in-depth research is required, the case study methodology is sometimes described as being ideal (Feagin, Orum, & Sjoberg, 1991). For the investigation of the current research, it is a reliable research method, especially because a comprehensive, in-depth investigation is needed to understand the research objective thoroughly. The researcher is using case study approaches to go beyond objective statistical results to consider behavioural as well as social, economic and political aspects from the viewpoint of the actors. With the help of the research method, the researcher will also be able to produce comprehensive qualitative accounts that not only will help to explore or describe data in a real-world setting but mostly clarify the nuances of real-world scenarios that may not be captured by experimental or survey study (Ebneyamini & Moghadam, 2018).

4.3.1.1 Constructivist approach of the case study:

Merriam (1998) adopted a constructivist approach to case study research, in which the researcher assumes that reality is produced intersubjectively through comprehending the meanings of social experimentation. Merriam (1998, 2009), like Yin (2014), emphasised the importance of properly utilising processes that can help analyse the information in a meaningful way by interpreting, sorting, and managing information, as well as adapting the discovery to provide clarity and applicability to the findings when information is abundant and the concept is rather abstract.

Thus, Merriam's perspective brings a pragmatic approach to constructivist inquiry. She mentioned that although case study research can use both quantitative and qualitative methods to analyze and collect data, in qualitative case studies; methods tend to aim at producing inductive reasoning and interpretation rather than testing hypotheses. Cases are generally selected based on the research questions and objectives and what they could potentially reveal about the main topic of interest of the researcher. The current research takes on Merriam's understanding as this portrays what the researcher is trying to find out. There is no absolute

truth to be proven, rather the researcher aims to gain an understanding of the phenomenon and generate a rich holistic script of the findings.

4.3.2 Phases of Case Study:

The main stages of research activity when planning and undertaking a case study are- defining the case; selecting the case(s); collecting and examining the data; interpreting data; and reporting the findings. According to Teegarapu and Summers (2008), the case study method could be categorized into three distinctive phases:

- (1) Define & design phase,
- (2) Prepare and collection phase, and
- (3) Analyze & conclude phase.

4.3.2.1 Phase 1- Design and define phase:

The first phase entails developing the case study protocol. This phase comprises a detailed plan and justification for the methods used to choose specific examples, create hypotheses, construct competing theories, collect and analyse data, and interpret findings. The success of a research method is determined by its design. At first glance, the case study technique appears to be the generic process used by design researchers in their independent investigations. The essence of a case study, on the other hand, resides in its design, a principle that is not strictly implemented in the field of 'design research' (Teegarapu and Summers, 2008).

Every empirical research method has a design, sometimes implicit. It is the logic connecting the data gathered during the study, to the study's questions.

The following five components of research are significant for case study design and therefore its success:

- Case study questions
- Case study propositions (Similar to hypothesis)
- Units of analysis
- Logic linking data to propositions
- Criteria to interpret case study results

Three case studies have been selected for this research. All the cases that have been chosen to have either been successful/ partially successful and still ongoing.

4.3.2.1.1 Chosen Case 1:

As per the report of New Age and Daily start (2017), Dhaka South City Corporation launched e-trade licenses and e-holding tax payment services for its citizens in an attempt to diminish their burdens and sufferings and create complete automation of their major revenue-generating system. For example- the process of issuing trade licenses conventionally is complex and time-consuming. Due to the conventional strategy, there was no data that more than 50,000 business owners had no trade license in Dhaka city and the government was losing more than 100 crores of income.

To improve this situation, Dhaka South City Corporation launched an automated e-service with the help of the Service Innovation Fund (SIF) of the a2i Programme of the Prime Minister's Office with technical assistance from UNDP and USAID. The system has been created to ease the complications of applying for trade licenses and paying holding taxes through which all the business institutions in Dhaka city can now visit the link: <http://www.etradelicense.gov.bd/> online and able to apply for a new trade license and renew an old trade license easily within a short time, low cost and transparent manner. The citizens are no longer required to come to DSCC offices and stand in queues to get trade licenses and pay holding taxes. The mayor hoped that the introduction of the e-services would help to ensure transparency and accountability among DSCC officials.

4.3.2.1.2 Chosen Case 2:

To ease the method and be more citizen-friendly, the Bangladesh Police has begun an internet GD filing service. Although it has exceptionally restricted usefulness, it is making fast improvements. The service is called CHR or Citizen Help Request and is right now completely operational in Dhaka City. Not all sorts of complaints can be recorded currently, most genuine offences are required to be recorded in person at the nearest or most appropriate police station (*Chr.police.gov.bd,2020*). All non-serious offences and wrongdoings can be recorded online through this system. The criteria for non-serious complaints incorporate:

1. Information on Eve Teasing
2. Information on Snatching
3. Information about loss/theft of certificate, ID, and documents
4. Information about Night Guard, Guard, Servant, Caretaker
5. Information about new/old tenants
6. Expatriate Problems/Complains

4.3.2.1.3 Chosen Case 3:

In 2010, the government created the National Plan for Disaster Management 2010–2015. Taking after the national arrangement, the government presented the National Disaster Management Act 2012. This statute made the Department of Disaster Management (DDM), which was set up in November 2012 and attempts hazard reduction exercises, reacts to calamity occasions, and fortify and coordinates programs embraced by diverse stakeholders (*Uddin & Haque, 2013*).

There are few information and communications technology (ICT) facilities that have been developed to monitor natural phenomena and create a system to alert the citizens. The one below has been chosen for the use of this current research as it is very important in the context of Bangladesh and is still ongoing to improve the performance constantly:

- Early warning through mobile broadcasting has been introduced for cyclone warnings in disaster-prone areas.

4.3.2.2 Phase 2- Prepare and collect:

According to the study by Yin (*2003*), there are six sources of evidence that can be utilized as a way of collecting data for a case study-based research. The sources are documents, interviews, direct observations, archival records, participant observations, and physical artefacts. Case study research is unique in its way because it has the strength to deal with a wide variety of data evidence. This phase of the research involves the preparation of data and questions, preparing the participants, and writing individual scripts of the interview or generating case reports in case it being multiple case studies-based research.

Study Propositions, theory, research, or questions work as a conceptual framework and they need to be supportive of the case being researched to guide the design and methodology of data collection and analysis (*Stake, 2006; Stewert & Shamdasani, 2014; Yin, 2014*). In chapter three, the conceptual framework has been discussed in detail. The conceptual framework was based on the initial investigation of secondary sources like literature and newspaper articles. Maintaining systematic evidence of the data collected and being able to present and explain the data is very crucial as well as explaining the process of data collection with ethical integrity supporting the research findings (*Merriam, 2009; Yin, 2014*). The collective positioning of the elements creates a justified framework for the research and encourages an environment for the validity, reliability, and credibility of the findings.

Based on the conceptual framework and the research questions, the interview questions will be based on 4 themes. The themes were planned to give the respondents a better idea about what sort of areas the researcher is hoping to cover and extract in-depth information from. The questions will be open-ended so that the respondents feel that they have the opportunity to go into detail about their experience and observations rather than just asking straightforward yes/no questions. The main four themes of the interviews revolve around the project itself- the idea creation, the process of developing the service and implementation, the external and internal challenges that were faced during the project, the management’s approach to dealing with the project, and how they perform as an organization overall. The figure is shown below:

Figure 4.1: Interview Themes (*Source: Author*)

Data Collection will be conducted through semi-structured interviews and will consist of open-ended questions. The semi-structured interviews (SSI) are conducted with one respondent at a time and they are more of a conversation-based interview. The questions are generally a mixture of closed and open-ended questions, accompanied by why or how questions following the conversations (*Saunders et al, 2019; Kallio, Pietilä, Johnson and Kangasniemi, 2016*). According to Adams (*2015*), about an hour is considered a reasonable maximum length for conducting SSIs. the dialogue between the researcher and respondent can revolve around the

main interview themes rather than verbatim questions like a generalized survey and may evolve into more meaningful conversations covering areas with unforeseen issues.

In-person SSIs are more relaxed and engaging but may take more time than anticipated, but they do not last as long as a focus group. If the resources are plenty and if the group is not big, it may be virtually possible to interview all of the members like the key members and chief executives (*McIntosh and Morse, 2015*). Where time and resources are restricted, it is still necessary to get the perspectives of more than a few people (*Newcomer, Harty & Wholey, 2015*). Due to the covid restriction going on, travel is not feasible and therefore the interviews will be contacted over the telephone or other social media calling platforms.

The researchers aim to at least interview 6-8 key people from each project as the research is both times and travel restricted at this point, The respondents have been chosen carefully after having a preliminary conversation with the top officials, and they have actively assisted in setting up the interviews, providing contact details of the staff who were involved in the project and thus simplifying the process of identification of the respondents. The respondent were all given the participation sheet to have a look at and a consent form to fully comply with the researcher's institutional policy and research ethics guidelines,

4.3.2.3 Phase 3- Analyse & Conclude:

Phase 3 of the case study research is focused on analysing the collected data and deriving results from them to generate recommendations and concluding remarks. For the current research, the researcher will analyse the data using a Thematic analysis (TA) to understand the patterns of behaviours and themes that recur throughout the interviews conducted. The merit of qualitative research lies in the knowledge that is derived from it, as well as being a method of transmission of presentation and treatment of research methods as living entities, By doing so, simple classification can be resisted and meaningful, solid, and validated results will be generated(*Giorgi, 1992; Holloway & Todres, 2005; Sandelowski, 2010-as mentioned in Vaismoradi, Turunen & Bondas,2013*).

TA is a method to identify, organize and shed a light on the insight into meaningful patterns or themes across a data set systematically. By focussing on the in-depth meaning of the data collected, TA enables the researcher to observe and gather sensible information from the collection of shared experiences or conversations. As per Merton (*1975*), the concept of TA was developed to go beyond the obvious knowledge to more implicit themes and structures.

As per the founder of TA, such materials can be called ‘themata’ and the inferred preferences are shared groups with certain types of concepts

Discovering unique themes found only within a single data is not the goal of TA. It rather works better in identifying commonalities in several topics that are written and talked about and making sense of them. The patterns found in the TA allow the researcher to find the important ones that are related to the research objectives and research questions (*Braun and Clarke, 2012*). Ideally, the systematic element characteristics are similar to traditional TA and content analysis (CA), but TA also allows the researcher to bring together the analysis of how frequent the themes appear as well as provide a deeper knowledge of the meanings of the themes. Thus, it adds value to research by a subtle and complex understanding of the research phenomena.

In this current research, the interview themes will be taken into consideration when analyzing the data and report findings as well as any recurring theme that has not been picked up by the researcher yet in the secondary literature investigation.

4.4 Criticism of the case study approach:

Although the case study method is being widely used now, it is not free from derogatory criticism by many authors (*Yin, 2003*). The most widespread criticism of case study research is that the researcher cannot gather sufficient knowledge from a single case. The case study method is not based on a simple argument, the main focus is to gather analytical information not statistical. However, case studies are very effective in the identification of one single case for which a theory will not be valid (*George & Bennett, 2005*). Hence, using a case study method can still be beneficial for a single case; depending on how the case is chosen and its context.

A common concern regarding case study research is that it does not follow any strict and systematic guidelines and therefore, may lack rigour. Also, most often the researcher does not represent thoughtfulness, does not have regard for guidelines, and does not analyze and report the findings accurately. This lack of diligence of the researcher most of the time overshadows the case study as a research method (*Teegavarapu & Summers, 2008*). Additionally, the case study research method gets confused with the case studies being used for teaching (*Yin, 2003*). The case studies that are used by teachers are generally presented in a way that will focus on specific issues that the teacher wants the students to gather knowledge about; and thus may

have the possibility to be biased and not systematic. Thus, these experiences with case studies for educational purposes often lead to a bad reputation for case studies in general.

It is also believed that case studies take a long time to be conducted and analyzed. Sometimes, researchers complain that they produce a large number of scripts and data that are never used to the full extent. However, it's been also stated that, if the researcher is careful and develops justifiable arguments, and follows them thoroughly, the abundance of inefficient and invalid data will not be generated at all. In addition to that, the case study research method offers some specific techniques to write the reports and findings and does not take a long time to produce (Teegavarapu & Summers, 2008).

Case studies are considered to be biased because they are influenced by the subjectivity of the researcher. According to McComas (1998), every form of research, even the scientific methods involves some level of subjectivity. There are two reasons to reject this statement of being biased. First of all, most case studies use falsification logic, where the researcher tries to prove his hypothesis wrong, hence the researcher is not biased here to prove his previously determined argument (Krusenvik, 2016). Secondly, case studies sometimes use triangulation techniques which require collecting data using multiple sources, using multiple data collection techniques. This helps to reject any biases influenced by the researcher's subjectivity (Saunders et al, 2018).

The current research is taking multiple cases as a source of data. Although the main data collection process is done by semi-structured interviews only, because of the nature of the open-ended questions, more insightful data will be generated from more than a few people and hence will not be biased by the researcher's perspective. Again, secondary sources like previous studies and news articles have also been studied thoroughly to understand the concept, generate a framework, and design questions so there will be little to no chance of generating unnecessary data or getting invalid findings.

4.5 Summary of the Chapter:

Designing the research is a key motivator for a researcher to understand how to generate the outcomes and how they can be presented tacitly and validly. Although there are some arguments against the case study as a research method, it is still a well-used form used by many scholars worldwide. To gain a proper understanding of what is happening in the chosen cases of the research, the researcher has to carefully observe and also analyze the situation in depth. Case study research methods designed with semi-structured interviews and a thematic way of

analyzing data will be very helpful to gain insight into the government projects in Bangladesh. Social constructivism's philosophical approach allows the researcher to connect the social reality of different stakeholders and reflect on their value and understanding of the situations and is suited for providing recommendations.

The next chapter is the detailed scripture of the collected data through semi-structured interviews. It will shed light on the cases in detail as well as the various aspects of the occurrences happening throughout different phases of the projects from the perspective of the respondents who were carefully chosen and played a vital role.

5. Case Study: Interview Data

5.1 Introduction:

The presentation of data in the research is a form of art, as it provides the researcher with a chance to create a story and enables the reader to be a part of the journey. It also helps the reader to walk in the footsteps of the researcher and the respondents and understand the concept in detail. In this chapter, the captured data from the interviews of the participants in the chosen government innovation projects have been summarised to uphold the authenticity of the research and also to observe the difference in opinions of different stakeholders. The data is described and presented in a systematic manner, case by case. In the previous chapter, the research design and method have been discussed in detail and it was mentioned that semi-structured interviews will be conducted to address the research questions. The data collection and interview questions were formed based on topics discussed in chapter 3 where the conceptual framework has been discussed thoroughly.

This chapter will present the interview scripts in an intelligible and interpretable form in order to identify recurring and potentially important themes for the research to understand the factors affecting government innovation and how leadership is having an impact. The findings will be discussed in the upcoming chapter of analysis and discussion.

5.2 A little refresher on the government innovations:

In Bangladesh, the use of ICT has become very effective in recent times to develop and transform various government services for the use of the citizens. To connect the citizens with the services offered by government agencies digitally, the ideas of e-government and e-governance have appeared as the new gateways to public service reforms. As mentioned in detail in the introduction and background chapter, the a2i program (jointly initiated and supported by the Prime minister of Bangladesh, UNDP, and USAID) is making a change of the mindset of the government officials to embrace the digitization process as a significant driver to the social and economic development of the country. After the success in the initiation phase, the a2i program has steadily moved to encourage and establish innovation in service delivery. Since the early 1990s, the government has been trying to switch to a market-led system by establishing decentralization, efficiency, competition, and partnership in the public sector organizations. Currently, the project has been transforming traditional services with e-service delivery across different ministries, departments, and field-level authorities. As mentioned in the research design chapter, the three chosen cases for this study are all under the

a2i program and are currently fully implemented for the use of the citizens. They cover the automation of local governments' services (city corporations- started with Dhaka South city corporation), the digitalization of online general diary creation of Bangladeshi Police (Started with Dhaka Metropolitan Police), and the digital approach to predict natural phenomena and alert the citizens. Three different projects have been chosen with a hypothesis of discovering diversities in strategies and outcomes.

5.3 Data Collection Process:

5.3.1: Participants of the study:

According to recent studies (Hameduddin et al., 2020; Mergel and Desouza, 2013; Srensen and Torfing, 2011), innovations are increasingly seen as open processes that involve the deliberate fusion of internal and external ideas. Useful information is widely dispersed both inside and outside the company, and it can be found, connected, and used to support innovations (Chesbrough et al., 2006). Therefore, it can be stated that stakeholders either internal or external play a vital role in the overall innovative process. Boon, Wynen and Callens (2021) established that there could be two types of stakeholders who work actively for the successful initiation and delivery of public sector innovation projects. In their study, they highlighted that internal stakeholders both managerial and non-managerial contribute to the innovation process and they affect internal innovation as well as external innovation. Their study explained the importance of stakeholder impact and perspective on different levels of innovation previously discussed in the works of Osborne, (1998); Verhoest et al., (2007); Godenhjelm and Johanson (2018) etc. As discussed in the conceptual framework chapter, there are multiple stakeholders in the public sector innovation project- Ministries, cabinet members, bureaucrats, external non-government organisations who help to develop the system/ product and government organisations who will change. The current study aims to look into the innovation process from its initiation to implementation and understand what factors affected them in the overall process from the perspective of stakeholders who were closely connected to the different phases of the project. Therefore, for fulfilling the objective the interviews were conducted among the people who had encountered barriers throughout the process

With the help of existing pieces of literature on the public sector innovation practice in Bangladesh and other developing countries, the key phases have been summarised in the conceptual framework in chapter three and can be identified as Idea generation and discussion of the procedures, service design and implementation. The respondents who were chosen to

take part in the interview were all internal stakeholders and directly participated in at least one of the phases while some of them were key players in multiple phases simultaneously and therefore to understand the barriers that impacted the process in different phases, their experiences are extremely valuable and are crucial to obtaining the objective of the current study. Ministers and bureaucrats played vital roles in the process but access to the ministries is restricted for various reasons and thus after careful consideration, they were not included to take part in the interview. The stakeholders in the three cases that were taken into consideration are presented in the figure below-

Chosen Case	Idea generation and discussion of the procedures	Design and delivery of the service	Implementation
Case 1: The automation project of Dhaka South City Corporation (DSCC)	Departmental head/ Senior managers of accounts and revenue department- Respondent 1 & 2	Departmental head/ Senior managers of accounts and revenue department- Respondents 1 & 2	Departmental head/ Senior managers of accounts and revenue department- Respondents 1 & 2
		IT specialist (from an externally recruited agency)- Respondents 3 & 4	IT specialist (from an externally recruited agency)- Respondents 3 & 4
		Mid Level Managers- Respondents 5 & 6	Mid Level Managers- Respondents 5 & 6
			General Staff
Case 2: Citizen Help Request project (Online GD) by Dhaka Metropolitan Police	Police chief- Additional Police commissioner of a police station- Respondent 1	Police chief- Additional Police commissioner of a police station- Respondent 1	Police chief- Additional Police commissioner of a police station- Respondent 1
		Senior inspectors – respondents 2 &3	Senior inspectors – respondents 2 &3
		IT Professional (Internal team and external agency recruits) Respondents 5 & 6	IT Professional (Internal team and external agency recruits) Respondents 5 & 6
			Police sergeant- Respondent 4
Case 3: Mobile network-based cyclone early warning system for coastal areas	Officials of the Ministry and DMD – Respondents 1 & 2	Officials of the Ministry and DMD – Respondents 1 & 2	Officials of the Ministry and DMD – Respondents 1 & 2
		BMD Scientists – Respondents 5 & 6	CPP Officials- Respondents 3& 4

			Officials in the committee of warning signals- Respondent 7
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Figure 5.1: The Stakeholder Map for the chosen cases (*Source: Author*)

5.3.2: Overview of Interview questions:

As mentioned in chapter 4 section (4.3.2.2), the responses have been generated through a semi-structured interview with open-ended questions. A semi-structured interview method promotes dialogue between the interviewer and the participant. A thorough discussion of important subjects is made possible by the ability of both the interviewer and the interviewee to ask questions. The respondent would most likely feel more at ease sharing further about their experiences due to the conversational tone. Building on the conceptual framework, the interview question revolved around four themes and based on those four themes, some questions were asked and as they were open-ended, created a scope of follow-up questions to understand the problem in more detail.

The interviews revolved around 4 themes-

- Project
- Internal challenges
- External challenges
- Leadership approach

The interviews were conducted over the telephone and lasted around 40 minutes to one hour. For each project, around 8 participants have been chosen carefully, based on the level of their involvement and authority over the project. The initial aim of the research was to thoroughly observe the projects as well as face-to-face conversations with the participants but was later changed due to the global pandemic situation. The data collection process took place in the last quarter of 2020 and 1st quarter of 2021. Although the original interview participants were meant to be slightly higher than the present number, this limitation is due to the current covid situation, complexities in reaching government staff and some were reluctant to take part in it due to some privacy issues.

In the beginning, each respondent was asked some icebreaking questions about their role and background to make them engaged. Then, the researcher started with a theme with an open question to get the interviewee talking, and then prompted the interviewee for specific features

of that theme. Icebreaking questions included a little glimpse of their background just to ease them into the conversation. (For an example of the questions asked- please see appendices)

5.4. The automation project of Dhaka South City Corporation (DSCC):

Dhaka South City Corporation is one of the two municipal corporations in Dhaka created when the former Dhaka City Corporation was divided into two. The Corporation was created by the Local Government Amendment Bill 2011 on 29 November 2011, passed in the Parliament of Bangladesh, following the President's approval (*dsc.gov.bd,2021*). The city corporation has 75 administrative wards. According to the existing legislation, the executive power of the corporation is exercised by the “Mayor”. The main administrative body consists of several standing committees that look after the broad range of activities of the corporation. The Mayor is accompanied and assisted in the running of the corporation by the Chief Executive Officer, secretary, head of departments, and zone executives.

One of the many duties of the city corporations is to control and collect holding taxes, issue trade licenses, birth certificates, traffic management, estate management, etc. Previously the process of paying taxes or creating or updating trade licenses was a nuisance. The process developed by the National Board of Revenue (NBR) was a control-based system that mostly relied on physical monitoring and doing everything manually. According to research by Ullah (2016), this reflected a low level of automation of processes, inefficiency in data management and sharing, and a lack of transparency in the collection and management of various taxes. In order to get rid of this situation and as per the vision of digitizing government services in Bangladesh (under the a2i), an automation project has been developed to create an online one-stop service for the citizens of seven city corporations in Bangladesh. The pilot project was developed and implemented in both Dhaka South and North City Corporations.

The main goal was to bring together two major departments – the revenue department and the accounts department. Previously the two boards used to work separately; there were fewer chances of sharing data and everything was done rather manually. To get a license or a simple birth certificate; citizens had to go through numerous departments and wait longer. The automation project involved an external vendor who developed the whole software and provided maintenance support with the help of the head of the departments (revenue and accounts), mid-level managers, frontline workers, external banking agents, and internal staff.

The interviewees were a mixture of the IT staff, frontline staff, heads of departments, mid-level managers, and external IT developers.

5.4.1 Conversations with the Executives:

Interview 1:

This participant is one of the executives of the DSCC. He has been working in the organization for over 15 years now. He had completed his studies at the most prestigious university in Bangladesh and then went to finish further training in Singapore. He mentioned this was a new project for them and in terms of any software-based system design, this was the first time he came across something like this in his entire career.

He mentioned previously the department used to collect revenue manually, with this system they were able to collect everything online- such as holding tax, building and municipality taxes, trade license issues and renewal, and many more. This is a successful project, but it took some time to go online as citizens are used to paying everything manually and even if the online system was established, they took time to get used to it. Tech-savvy citizens welcomed the process wholeheartedly; for the part of the population who do not own a smartphone or do not have access to the internet, baking booths were integrated into the system so they can simply go there and submit the money.

He mentioned although the project was successful in the end, the path toward success wasn't an easy one. He said, *“When you transform all your activities into a software-based system, there are lots of things that can go wrong in the process of doing so, and we had our ups and downs”*. In each phase, the software development went to numerous corrections and amendments according to the requirements of the local government and the departments. The tender for the software design and development was distributed and external IT teams were brought in for the process.

He was one of the main facilitators of the project and supervised every step closely. The planning phase included the executives of DSCC, the Mayor, the Minister of the local government, and other cabinet officials. The initial plan was the automation of seven city corporations and to understand whether it is going to be successful or not, DSCC and DNCC were chosen as the pilot project bases. Since it was a decision taken by the ministry itself, there was no political interruption on their part. The process made everything a lot simpler. Previously for just issuing a trade license, there was multiple paperwork that needed to be filled,

then there were inspectors who would go through the papers, then a long waiting in lines to pay the money, and after that, the license would be issued. Now all the forms are included in the online version, anyone requiring a license can just fill out the forms online, pay the money, and then wait to get the copy of the license. If there's an error in the data, the form will not be saved and the application process will not be completed.

Talking about the challenges, he described them step by step. *"When the project was declared, the first interruption came from the staff. I would not call it a resistance; I would call it an indirect non-cooperation"*. Some of the staff were not happy because their interest would be hampered if everything was done online. To state the matter in detail, he said, for example- the field-level officers who used to collect the revenues manually sometimes took extra money from the taxpayers. Sometimes the taxpayer would pay the money to please the collection staff or sometimes they would pay it on their own to make the whole process quicker. With the online system in place, even if the staff go for physical collection, they will ask for the mobile money account of the payer and then deposit the money there giving them a payment reference number. This process ensured more transparency and of course, some people did not take it well.

Secondly, they thought their jobs would be replaced by the systems. In their mind, once a taxpayer realizes they can do it by sitting at home or going to the nearest internet cafe or using mobile money, they will not need any physical revenue collector to submit the taxes, and thus they will no longer be needed. For these reasons, the staff was reluctant to cooperate in the process and it took a good amount of time to get them on board.

Initially, every sub-department was given a chance to attend proper training to use the system accurately and every sub-department had an online booth placed to utilize the internal staff in collecting revenue from people who do not have access to smartphones or the internet. *"However, I noticed even after giving several training sessions, they kept making up excuses of not using the system"*. For at least 2 years, DSCC had to outsource an IT team to maintain and develop the project until the staff got fully trained on the process, which required extra financial resources and was not paid by the local government as they thought maintenance would be done by the internal staff once the system is up and running.

The third factor was the educational, social background, and age of the field level and junior level staff. Most of them are not educated that much and were unwilling to understand the significance of using technology in order to ease their workload. The younger staff took it well.

The older staff (60% of the office population) were offered training multiple times, external training teams were also brought to train them however, they did not take the training seriously. *“We got to know that some of them did not even attend the training, it took some time to get to us but at the end, I gave orders that whoever does not take the training, will face serious repercussions”*. They thought if they do not take training, the whole process will eventually go back to the traditional way.

When asked about the organizational culture, he stated that the office culture is very friendly. The higher officials appreciate creative ideas from the subordinates and are very welcoming to hearing new thoughts. *“Whenever someone came to me about any ideas about how the automation process can be implemented better or what can be done differently, I always listened to them attentively and praised them for coming forward and we discussed if the suggestion can be utilized, but the proportion of those staff was 1-2%.”*. The staff was made aware of the changes from the very beginning, but still, they fought really hard and wasted a lot of precious time.

When asked what could have been done better as a leader, he mentioned due to the guidelines and policies of government recruitment, even if he wanted to, there was not much to do. For about 20 years there were no new recruitments of the officials in DSCC. He gave a proposal to the Mayor that there should be new recruitments for expert workers who can handle the job well. Due to the policy, it is rarely impossible to move staff from one department to another and it is not an easy task. Additionally, he could have introduced reward-based management and it probably would have encouraged the staff to be a part of the change and be open about it rather than resist it.

Interview 2:

This participant is another high official working for the DSCC accounts department. He is working in his position with honesty and pride for about 15 years now. He is well educated, completed his post-graduate and took on extra training and professional development courses to succeed in his profession. He always had a keen interest in technology and when the government initiated the a2i programme he was very excited about whether the city corporations' service could be integrated into it to transform the service delivery for the population.

The DSCC executives, the Mayor, the Minister of Local Government, and other cabinet officials participated in the planning process. The original proposal called for the automation of seven city companies, and to see how it would work, DSCC and DNCC were chosen as pilot projects. He was one of the project's key facilitators on behalf of the accounts department, closely monitoring every move and also providing key decisions about requirements, staffing, resources and key changes in the automation of the accounts department.

The project was split into two sections. The first step involved creating applications for seven city corporations; there would be two versions, one for revenue and one for accounting. The project's hardware was ordered, the software was integrated, and the project was fully implemented. The project started a long time ago back in 2012 but took a long time to finally implement. The initial project time limit was 2 years, but it took around 5 years to finally open it to the public.

“Of course, I would call it a successful project. It is still ongoing in full capacity” he carried on. The most successful aspect of the project as per him was the complete automation of the payment process in the accounts department. With the new government ICT rules of introducing an online payment gateway, now there is scope for an online payment system for different types of tax and revenue generation. It's still not secured and not fully operational, for example, one cannot have an online banking app like the most developed countries to manage their accounts online.

However, cash and check transfers and deposits can now be done using the service. It helped the population living in the city with an internet connection to complete the transactions online, similarly, it helped the majority of the population without any proper digital devices at home. Partnerships have been developed with some banks for the deposit of money using their payment booth, mobile money and banking agent booths. Now the citizens who can complete the form using a local computer cafe but do not want to provide payment details because of security reasons can pay the money using payment booths, mobile money and banking agents. *“It has saved a lot of time for us as we can look over the whole process online as well- how much money is coming in, who is paying for what purpose and much more. It's much more simplified and systematic”*

Another success factor is that automation has created a scope for transparency in different phases of work in the accounts department. In some previous cases, people needed to spend some extra money on the officials to get the job done quicker or some people used to get better

treatment from bank officials because of their connections and used to get away with faster payments. *“Now the process seems a lot friendlier to the users and they can rely on being treated fairly as there is little to no chance of corruption using the online system” he stated.*”

He mentioned the transformation was not an easy process. First of all, the DSCC did not have any qualified IT professionals in the team to bring forward the change, design it and maintain it afterwards. *“Two sets of teams were brought in one team who designed and implemented the process and the other team helped with the implementation and maintenance later on”* he added. Initially, when the first IT team came in and was given the requirements of the local government to automate all the sectors of the city corporation Since it would have been a daunting task and there were not enough resources assigned for it, they decided to first automate the accounts and revenue department being the major 2 departments. All the forms and policies had to be explained in detail to the team as they were externals, it was somewhat a bit exhaustive and time-consuming. *“Their adjustments and our requirements were not matching up all the time and to come to a balance was critical,”* he said.

The next hurdle was the reluctance of some staff. They were not cooperating to their full capacity, not completing the necessary training, not giving briefs to the IT teams about what jobs they were doing and simply showing a mistrust in the management that their jobs will be gone. First, they were saying they do not want to take on the new system as they think it may fail, and will create problems for the department. They were multiple occasions of training to use the system, they were given chance to speak to their immediate supervisors on and one to one basis to discuss the issue. Most of them came around, however, some of them did not want to go through the change and for them *“We needed to be very strict about their training and involvement. I think because of this fear they agreed in front of us to cooperate but in reality, they still are looking for a chance to find an issue so the whole system could go back to the traditional way”*.

Again, the lack of resources and funding from the local government made it a bit harder for the second phase of the project, which was the implementation and maintenance. As mentioned previously, the DSCC did not have any skilled IT staff and because of the complications in the government recruitment policy, there were hardly any new recruitments in that department. The externals were brought in with a temporary contract and when they left, DSCC had to bring in another IT contractor team using their financial resources. *“This use of our finances impacted our budget and funding generation”* he added.

The interviewer asked in further detail why he thought the staff were resistant and how he, as a manager, impacted their actions. He responded by saying that not all of the department staff are well educated and come from all walks of life. With their poor socio-economic background, they are not very keen on taking up challenges that might affect their job role. They are happy doing the bare minimum needed to get the job done. So when the change was introduced, they were scared that they have to learn new skills. Also, they feared their jobs would be gone since everything was getting automated, they have a lack of understanding of their job roles as well. Additionally, there is no reward scheme at DSCC at this point, so staff generally did not feel motivated to go that extra mile to it. *“As a leader, I think I am very open to communication and I listen to any feedback given to me. But in Bangladesh, the culture is still very hierarchical, and I do not think the lower-level staff’s concerns and feedback reach my department. They either do not feel comfortable or are very fearful that they keep their distance”*. He did not blame the staff for not being comfortable in confrontations or open feedback about the whole automation process, as the culture taught everyone to be submissive to their superiors therefore, openness in discussion is rarely found, at least in public sector organisations.

5.4.2 Conversations with the IT personnel:

Interview 3:

This participant was a member of the external IT team who worked with a contract under the local government. According to her, when the local government released tenders for the automation project, her team applied for the tender to work on the automation project. She was one of the system developers of the IT team. She mentioned that the initial idea was generated in the ministry of urban planning and development that the activities of seven city corporations in Bangladesh should be automated. Hence the tender for the automation project was released.

The project floated in two phases. The first phase was developing software for 7 city corporations- there would be 2 software- one for the revenue department and one for the accounting department. The hardware necessary for the projects was purchased and the software was integrated there, and it was finally implemented. The project span was 2 years. When they developed the software and handed it over to the pilot city corporation (DSCC), it was their responsibility to further maintain it.

The revenue department collects various types of taxes and issues licenses and certificates and later on the accounts department deals with the monetary side. Now, as per her, the goal of the

automation project was to combine them, so the process becomes smoother both for the service users and for the working officials. It created a scope for transparency in the collection of data and collection of money. Previously the officials who used to work physically collecting data and taxes had a chance to make extra money and manipulation or loss of data was a common occurrence. With the automation project, any taxpayer or business can simply go online and use the service using their identification or registration number. The charge for each service has been fixed so there is no chance of any malpractice there. The money will be collected by the partner banks and will be automatically transferred to the accounts department. Also, people do not have to wait a long time in lines to use the service, they can simply do it from their home using their mobile.

Besides the calculation of money, the software generated for the accounts department can also help with vouchers and budget creation. She mentioned when asking about the success of the project that most of the staff were very welcoming to the changes made as they could see the results. The reports were generated without any hassle, daily monitoring and management of data have become easier and after the successful implementation, the other city corporations went ahead and started their automation project. The challenges, according to her, were much more overwhelming than they initially assumed. The projects went through many challenges, technical difficulties, and a lack of resources made the project implementation delayed much longer than anticipated. The huge amount of data that needed to be included in the system and the maintenance afterwards was an issue and still, the interviewer is worried about how the DSCC staff will maintain the hardware and software in the long run and they may have to go back and help them maintain it.

Another big issue was the dimension being brought into the workforce; the change in the overall workflow created a lot of resistance from the mid-level staff. To quote the interviewee, *“They were so against the change and they created so much problem from the development to the implementation process, we had to extend for 2 years from its initial deadline ”*(it finally was up and running in 2019).

The staff thought since everything is being automated, their jobs will be replaced by the software and they won't have anything to do other than being redundant. They were very afraid everything would become easier and they wouldn't be able to do it their way; the whole process would be very much transparent.

According to the interviewee, “ *The major issue on their part was transparency. I don’t want to talk about the bribery which takes place among those staff while offering any service to the citizens. They fought to their extreme for the system to remain unchanged. The top officials, along with my team, had to convince them hard just to make them co-operate, that nothing will be changed, they won’t lose their jobs*”.

Even after that, they showed very much redundancy and the top officials had to take a strict approach to make them co-operate. Looking back, she thinks if that staff was made aware of the change gradually, they might have acted differently. However, with the issue of transparency, it would have been hard to achieve. She praised the top management as very supportive and enthusiastic from the beginning. They were always eager to offer extra support, tried to arrange some necessary training to use the software, and tried their best with resource allocation. Without their continuous support and strong handling of the stiff resistance, the project would not become a success.

Interview 4:

This interviewee was the IT manager for the project, he was included in the team as an external vendor. He has experience working in government and private sector innovation projects for 7+ years. He mentioned that his role was to design and develop the system and since the beginning, they have had to go through several hurdles. Their team was brought in to collect the requirements of the project and generate different ideas which will later have to go through the department heads to finalize.

He said to start from the beginning when the project was initiated, they were asked to come in, they wanted the requirements of the projects. The officials failed to give them a proper list of requirements. When two huge departments would come under the same system, there would be a tremendous amount of data that needs to be collected. These include- the work roles, the exact definition of the works that were undertaken by various staff under revenue and account departments and exactly what they wanted to achieve, the gadgets given by the government, and the rules and regulations regarding the service transformation. This was one of the biggest challenges for him which surpassed the technical difficulties they faced. Much of the problem was created by the officials not having proper knowledge.

He goes on to say, “ *The staffs working in the government sector does not have any strong knowledge about technical and digital aspects, they never could give us the proper*

requirements, when we go work for a project under government there are certain rules that we need to follow and it was difficult to understand what they wanted from us ”.

He mentioned that if a private sector wants to go through a digitalization process and brings in a team of IT, the team will normally go talk to the internal IT team, the system designer, or the ICT manager. However, when working for the government the system is quite different. They do not have any strong IT officials as most of the process went on in a traditional manner using a manual approach. This initial disruption created a problem in the business requirement development (BRD) and the system requirement structure development (SRSD) phase. Despite that, they managed to pass these challenges and were able to build a prototype for the system.

“Our initial goal was to create automation for 7 city corporations - Dhaka North and South, Chittagong, Rajshahi, Sylhet, Khulna, and Barisal, and we designed the system with all their requirements. Later DSCC went ahead and invested some more money in order to improve their maintenance process.”

He thinks the project is very much successful despite all the problems they faced as it is up and running to date. Talking about technical aspects, he said different types of service integration have taken up the main space of digitalization nowadays. Previously every single service had its system, but now they have designed a central integration system that is highly efficient to integrate any service from any part of the world into the central system.

He said, *“Our biggest achievement was the automation and digitalization of the revenue collection in a country like Bangladesh. It is the first time somebody has taken the initiative to do it”.* They have designed the central system for the city corporations and integrated other systems like online banking (payment gateway), agent banking (payment booths), mobile financing, and physical banking for the collection of money. The next phase included the integration of the central system to include the foreign direct investments (FDI) that come to Bangladesh. They require a trade license as well before starting the investment in any business. It was a joint objective of the Prime Minister's office and

the Bangladesh Investment Development Authority (BIDA). With the request of the cabinet secretaries, the central system was integrated with BIDA to facilitate foreign direct investments.

When it comes to resources, the project requires a big number of human resources. Apart from the delivery and design team, another 40-45 system engineers were included in the whole

process to run it successfully. They were not government officials and were included in the project by the interviewee's company as they did not get the human resource required for the project from the government. According to him, the budget was planned by the local government ministry, so they did not have any involvement with that. The funds were generated as per government guidelines.

"Hardly anybody wanted to take any responsibility in taking a final decision" he added. Whenever they approached an official about making changes and saying if they are happy with the requirement change, they used to carefully slide it to another person in charge and that person would provide some completely new requirements for the system. Hence, the planning, design, architecture, and implementation of the system have gone a different way than planned. It could have taken its actual shape if there was less time wasted in organizing the requirements from all different officials and creating a final list.

5.4.3 Conversations with the Mid-Level Staff:

Interview 5:

This participant is a middle-level management staff working in the revenue department for the last 15 years. He started working in the revenue department in the license section and then gradually rose to the managerial position with hard work and passion. The automation of the revenue and accounts department is a comparatively new phenomenon for him as he did not see the department going through such a drastic change technologically.

When asked about his role in the automation process, he mentioned he was overseeing the collection of the huge data and requirements to transform them digitally. *"It was a gigantic task, we normally collect so much data manually, I never realized it would be so much hassle to put them together for the system generation,"* he said. He described that before the automation process, the revenue department used to work in a very traditional manner. The whole department is divided into two major sections- the licensing department and the estate department. The main day-to-day functions included assessment and collection of tax, issue of trade license, driver's license and other vehicle licenses, maintenance, establishment and leasing of housing, marketplace, parks, etc. to name a few.

He is one of the managers in the trade license section which looks after the taxation and licenses. Previously people had to wait in long lines and waste a lot of time going from one department to the other just to renew or issue their license or just resolve any tax matter. The

monthly and annual report generation was a very time-consuming process as everything was done manually. He gladly said *“We as managers become very happy when the process is automated. Everything is now way simpler, and I can collect data and generate reports in just a few clicks”*

The whole idea was first initiated in the local government ministry. They were told in a meeting called by the Mayor of DSCC that tasks were going to be automated and digitized. Various training sessions were arranged for the managers and staff to finalize the requirements and resources and hand over the tasks. *“It was very overwhelming in the beginning, but we gradually understood the necessity and started working hard to put everything together.”*

When asked about the challenges, he mentioned that initially there was a communication barrier between the external IT vendors and the staff of the DSCC. As they did not have any prior knowledge of what was being asked of them, the answers were difficult to obtain. Their questions were sometimes very specific and having no technological background did not make it easier. Besides, they had to follow different protocols set by the local government and there were some restrictions on sharing information. However, these problems were resolved with the help of the higher management, the CEO, and the deputy chief of the revenue department. they spent time with everyone as much as they could to explain the process a bit better.

“I don’t want to quote it, but I am not very happy with how my staff behaved. It was a shame that they showed so little interest in the automation process. Some of them did not even bother when they were asked to cooperate. I don’t blame them entirely. It was hard for them to swallow the hard pills that they will not be able to have their way in doing things and everything will be predetermined in the system”. He talked about handling internal staff resistance as a big issue as they were disrupting others’ work. They thought they would be gone, they felt threatened and some of them did not even want to learn how to use a computer start. They were not happy with the new and creative way to do things and were unhappy that they will have to learn to do it from scratch. *“I remember having countless meetings with them, sometimes one to one just to get them on board, to cooperate with others and do their portion of work”*. The department did not have enough technologically skilled staff and because of the complications in the recruitment process, new staff could not be hired instantly which is so much easier in the private sector.

When asked about any external difficulties they faced, he said he can not recall any, since it was a government-initiated project, he does not think there were any bureaucratic interferences

in the project. He specifically wanted to mention how the senior officials were involved in the project, they were very determined to make changes from the beginning and they tried their best to make their staff happy as well as the system designers. They were very keen to listen to any ideas the staff bring forward and were very encouraging in their creative thoughts. They arranged training sessions to the best of their ability following the government guidelines and keeping in mind the resources. The training sessions were very helpful.

He thinks in the initial phase when the project was first introduced, if the higher management would slowly integrate the change to all levels of staff, their resistance would have been tackled easily, and if DSCC had skilled staff who could handle technical aspects; the project could have been finished on time.

Interview 6:

This interviewee is currently working as an accounts manager in the accounts department for DSCC. He completed his education in accountancy and joined DSCC as a non-gazetted accountant 7 years ago, he has been promoted recently for his hard work and dedication.

He mentioned this project was the first software-based innovation that he has seen in his entire career as an accounting expert. *“It’s one of its kind. I was very surprised when the idea of bringing two major departments was introduced. It was sudden, but it was a pleasant surprise”*. He mentioned the accounting department deals with all sorts of monetary aspects of the city corporation which includes but is not limited to budget preparation, fund generation, revenue generated by tax collection, employee salary and much more. The resource of income includes internally raised revenue and loans and grants from the government; sometimes funds generated through international donors. Internally raised revenue includes different types of taxes, and tolls collected from citizens for providing different services- land management, rent, marketplace, trades, vehicles, animals, advertisements, registration of marriage, birth and death etc.

“Previously people used to come to the city corporation office and submit all the paperwork and money. We had a designated government banking partner. They had to go and pay the money thereby waiting in long lines. It was a time-consuming process as we used to do everything manually as the files used to be transferred from one person to another person, sometimes it would have taken you a whole just to submit a request and money for a trade license”. After the integration now people can pay money using a banking booth, online

banking or using mobile money. The mobile money transfer system has been specifically helpful for people who do not have any internet connection at home. *“You can simply go to an internet cafe, submit your paperwork and you will be given a reference number along with the way you want to pay the money. The traditional system is still in place for people who prefer it that way but the automation has made it easier for the majority of the people who do not like the hassle of doing it in person”*.

Now everything is automated and it has made the whole process a lot simpler for the service users. They can submit the money sitting on their own if they have an internet or a mobile banking account. When asked about the challenges, he said that integrating other financial agencies into the system was a problem initially as all have their payment systems. The revenue department staff had their requirement as well as the accounts and the technical aspect were very complicated. Deciding on the final requirements of the system took some time which delayed the process. The staff had to take some training just to use computers and deliver their data using them. Besides, some of the staff made the transition a bit challenging by creating a strong opposition to the idea of everything being automated. They did not want their role to be gone as they said, but actually, if the process is automated they wouldn't be able to make money like they used to do before.

He gave an example saying *“if somebody wants to pay a for creating a trade license, the government has a fixed rate that should be charged and this is now integrated into the system; but when it was done manually, the staff had the opportunity to manipulate the value and extort some extra money saying they will be able to provide the license quicker. people used to pay this extra money just to avoid the hassle. The main aim for our automation project was to deliver transparency, and obviously, some people did not like the idea of it”*

He mentioned they did not face any external pressure or interference from any source outside of the organisation. The local government as well as the higher officials in DSCC tried their best to provide resources and on their part, there was no corruption. He said they were a bit sceptical about how the public would welcome it but seems like they have taken it positively and he hoped that the system will be maintained and updated regularly for becoming more user-friendly. In a country like Bangladesh, digitization is taking a shape slowly and people not living in cities are still getting used to it, so it will take some time for them to grasp the nature of the change. People need to be educated about the new process so it can remain transparent and the organisation can maintain its reputation.

5.4.4 Conversations with the general staff:

Interview 7:

This participant is a field-level staff for inspection. If somebody submits paperwork that is not relevant or if there was an error in it, he must inspect the error and the authenticity of the submitted paperwork, Sometimes he even goes to the respective person's home to investigate and collect the required papers if anything is missing. He loves technological staff, he said he uses his smartphone for various reasons like social media, video calling apps and online money transfers. He thinks the automation project has made everyday activities easier for him.

When asked about his contribution to the project, he helped his superiors to collect the requirements of his role and what he used to do manually daily so that it can be put into the system. it took a lot of time to incorporate the data into the system. The external team came in and asked for the data over and over again so it was a hassle. *“Some of my other colleagues were not happy when I was helping in the process as much as I can as they did not like the change, they thought I was flattering them for my gain”*. When asked about the reason for the unhappiness of the colleagues, he said he does not want to say too much about that as it might affect his relationships with them and he needed the connection because he still has a long way to go.

At the mention of the organisation's environment, he mentioned he likes working there. The managers are always supportive and they arranged multiple training sessions to accommodate the staff in learning the new software system. When asked about creativity, he said did not have many chances to put forward any new ideas yet but he believes he will be heard if the situation ever occurs. He said he learned it quickly as he liked the new way of doing things. *“Going to people's houses to investigate, collect everything and manually do the paperwork was a bit hectic. I like that I can just do everything electronically, smoother for me, less chance for error.”* Additionally, he stated that the management could slowly adapt the staff to the new changes so they would have been more comfortable in welcoming the changes.

5.5 Citizen Help Request project (Online GD) by Dhaka Metropolitan Police:

Dhaka Metropolitan Police is the biggest unit that looks after the laws and regulations and protects the citizens of the Dhaka area. It started its journey on the 1st of February, 1976 after a major reconfiguration of the police department of Bangladesh. When it started, it consisted of 12 police stations and a force of 6000 members only. At present, the total number of police

stations is 49 and the police consist of more than 26,000 members including all ranks (*police.gov.bd,2021*). The main departments include:

- The police headquarters and administration
- Crime and operations
- Detective and Crime Intelligence
- Traffic
- Counter-terrorism and transactional crime

Other departments are SWAT, SWPC and Cyber Crime Investigation Unit. The Dhaka Metropolitan police have been taking slow and steady steps to incorporate various ICT projects to improve the service delivery among citizens and become more digital. They have taken many notable projects which are still in progress. In the process of ICT advancement, one of the most demanding public service organisations, ‘Bangladesh Police’ created an ICT-based initiative named “Citizen Help Request (CHR)” in 2010 to provide efficient service to the citizens of Bangladesh. The project aimed to offer online services to the citizens to form General Dairy (GD) through their website <http://chr.police.gov.bd> (*Hasan,2012*).

Under this service, citizens can report or file a gd without having to go to the police stations in most cases. the reasons are stated below for which online GD can be done-

1. Eve Teasing: Using the online GD service, victims of eve-teasing (public sexual harassment of the female population) can make complaints to the “Children and Women Victim Cell” department of police.
2. Snatching/Theft: People who are victims of snatching, pickpocketing and forceful theft of belongings such as money, mobile phones or electronic devices, pieces of jewellery etc on the road or the vehicle can complain about using the service.
3. Loss/theft of certificate, ID and documents: Citizens who have lost their identity card, important documents, or educational and professional certificates from their own home or while travelling can use the service to inform their closest police station.
4. New or old tenants: Citizens/landlords are required to gather prospective details of their current or old tenants for their record and can also submit it to the police for verification, identity check or in case of any urgency and it can also be done using the online GD platform.

5. Maid, caretaker, and security guard's information: To induce the investigation about the burglary at a flat, the citizens of Dhaka city can supply their old or recently selected servant, caretaker, and security guard's data to the particular police station.

6. Foreign citizen's complaint: Foreigners who face any difficulties during their residence or visit to Bangladesh can use this service to put forward any complaints to the Expertise Help Cell of the police.

Citizens who require the above six types of services can submit their requests through the online service and it gets stored in the database located at Police headquarters and an electronic receipt gets sent to the person who used it. To understand the project and related challenges, one of the additional commissioners (headquarters), police inspectors and sub-inspectors, sergeant of different wards and system/IT analysts of the projects have been interviewed to cover all the possible stakeholder groups.

5.5.1 Conversations with the High Officials:

Interview 1:

This participant is one of the additional commissioners working in the police headquarters and looks after the operational aspect of DMP. He joined the police force by completing the BCS exam and is successfully working in his current role for 8 years now. He is an active member of the innovation body of the DMP. He is proud of how far the DMP has come since its initiation in 1976. With time, the public trust is increasing, and they are working restlessly to provide different forms of service to the citizens of Dhaka city.

With regards to the online GD platform service for innovative service delivery, he said that the project was not entirely straightforward. To understand the project, the whole innovation process needs to be explained. To propose innovation in the daily services is just one step, but to put it into action, they have to go through multiple steps. First, the innovation team will sit together and discuss the proposed notion and analyse its implacability and authenticity. Then they will set some objectives. A team will be formed that will look into the positive and negative aspects of the project being designed and implemented on a national scale. Budget and resources need to be allocated in the next phase. Then the team will design an initial system and a pilot project will be initiated on a small scale for example in a relatively small police station and based on the review from there, it will go on a broader/ national scale.

There were many technical challenges of the online GD process initially like the lack of a verification process and no scope of generating an online version of the GD copy. Now with the advancement and new policies being put in place, digital signatures are included in the system and citizens can download a soft copy of their filed GD. There's no need to visit the police station for non-serious offences at all. There is still a lack of marketing to get more citizens to utilise the service to release some pressure off the staff in the station and involve them in other matters. The marketing and press department is currently developing strategies to improve this situation. DMP has recently started being more active using its social media platforms to reach more people and inform them about the services.

The online police services as well as the GD filing service have been integrated into the central system of the government already. The a2i programme run by the Prime Minister's office has taken steps to include all the government-led digital services under one central system and it has provided the protection and security of data in the server that was initially absent from the online GD website. *"The firewall is improved, we are getting very minimal hacking incidents and they are dealt with efficiency"*, he added. Besides, with the new Bangabandhu satellite, the government-provided internet has improved the LAN of most police stations. Some stations still do not have LAN and they are located in old infrastructures as the budget allocation can only consider a few things every fiscal planning year, but it has been taken into consideration and the headquarters is working to provide infrastructure to the police stations.

"When we initiated the online GD filing process, we designed an initial system, some budget was allocated from the local government ministry, but it was mostly us and the pilot project took place in Uttara station" He commented. Replying to the interviewer's question about how the creative ideas took place and how much they take into account the feedback of the subordinates, he stated that, there's a feedback /complaints box placed in every single police station in the Dhaka Metropolitan area to provide complaints, constructive feedback and suggestions from both staff and general public use. It can be anonymous, or one can use the name as well. If this system is effective or not when asked, he said, *"We are seeing very slow but consistent progress in terms of staff feedback and creative suggestions"*. The process is slower than expected because of a centralised hierarchical organisation system. The police, although being modernised every day, the public sector organisational culture is still following the colonial British centralised system, where the subordinates maintain a distance from the

executives and there's still a level of fearmongering atmosphere of being criticised if opposing an idea or being outspoken or creative.

"We are trying our best to encourage all levels of staff to be more participative in any discussion. Besides proving the feedback box, we are now having conversations with them in the monthly meetings and conferences and providing training to staff who are in any supervisory position to be more supportive and open to the subordinates" he said. Generally, middle-level police officers have more managerial and leadership functions rather than their subordinates. Now there's a scope of professional training and development for the staff in a supervisory positions to enhance their leadership skills. This is a new attempt that he is hopeful will be proven helpful in the future. Assistant Superintendent of Police (ASP), Sub Inspector, Sergeant, and Constable are the four tiers/ranks in the Bangladesh Police Force. A Bangladeshi male or female citizen who meets all the requirements will apply for any of these three positions and be accepted after passing a rigorous physical and written examination, an interview, and police verification.

"For the ASP position, you need to have a 4 years graduation degree and need to pass the BCS examination as well, whereas for the constable position your educational requirements in only passing school level. So, you can understand the level of knowledge the constables have, and it is a tough job to get them trained to use digital services" he added. He emphasised that now with police service on the verge of total automation, they need to rethink the qualifications and initial training phases to incorporate a more digitally trained and enthusiastic police force.

Again, the recruitment of police is still not enough. For every 600 citizens in Dhaka, there is only 1 officer to look after them. In times of busy periods, even higher officials like sub-inspectors and inspectors go on traffic duty or provide security to large gatherings. Being such short-staffed already and getting less funding in the digital aspect, it is really difficult for them to hire more IT professionals, provide IT resources to all the stations and staff and provide appropriate training to all staff simultaneously. *"The government at the moment is providing more resources and funding to the teams who investigate terrorism or criminal level activity rather than the digital transformation of police. We are hoping to generate some international funding to improve our digital processes"* he stated. Being the main source of protection to the general public, they have a lot of pressure and expectations from the public as well as the government. It is difficult to be in a position where he, as a leader is facing immense stress

currently. There needs to be a balance in every service the police provide and the department is trying its best to improve it and make the people trust them.

5.5.2 Conversations with police officers:

Interview 2:

This interviewee mentioned this was the first time he saw the police stations using some sort of up-to-date technology. He was working as the senior inspector at Uttara police station where the project was first started. He is aged between 40-50.

He said when they were first told about the project, they were not very enthusiastic if it is going to work out or not. He thought using digital services is futuristic and all other developed countries' police use technology in their daily activities, so it is high time Bangladeshi police start utilizing them.

He stated that citizens are required to provide their name, address and telephone numbers to make a non-urgent complaint like eve-teasing, loss of belongings or theft. The person who is making the complaint needs his national identification card or birth registration number as well. The system takes all this information and then sends an automated code to the mobile number given. The user then has to input the number in the system and then the system will ask further questions such as the reason for GD, how the incident happened and which respected police station he or she wants to register the GD. After submitting the form, an e-receipt is sent to the user's mobile number or email address provided and they can collect the official complaint document from that police station after a week.

He mentioned although it is a wonderful initiative on the part of Dhaka Metropolitan police this is not an efficient service to date as *"You still may need to go to the station to pick up your official copy of GD filed (using the number provided at the website after you submit the form) as we have received complaints that people could not download the soft copy or simply it was not generated. Since you must go to the station regardless, the effectiveness is in question."*

Secondly, the system is only applicable for non-serious offences, the citizens still need to visit the police station if there is a serious crime for example murder, threats for money, unusual death and many more. So, it is still an ongoing process of encouraging people to use the service for non-serious cases. They like to stick to the traditional ways despite being time-consuming and frustrating. *"We receive very few requests online. Maybe 3 or 4 a day, sometimes even 0"*

A lot of challenges came when the process was initially inaugurated by the then Home Minister. The police stations were not fully equipped with computers, there was no high-speed internet and the staff were not fully trained. The biggest issue faced was providing staff training and avoiding false cases. *“Initially, we received so many requests with fake mobile numbers, addresses and email addresses and back then we did not have any verification process integrated into the system, so it was a waste of time to sort them out”*. Currently, the users have to provide their national id numbers and officers can verify them.

When asked if there was any staff resistance at all like the reviews on the website said officers used to charge money before a physical complaint, to make a quick enquiry, he said he doesn't believe that is the case. Few police officers may do that, but mostly in big police stations like the one he works in, there was no resistance from the staff related to this bribery matter. Rather they did not show any excitement because they were hardly trained for it.

The higher officials encouraged us to take training and they had to go through training as well. The internal IT team was very supportive and skilled, and they designed the system to its best capabilities. Without the persistent involvement of the top officials, the project would have been a total failure. *“However, I think the advertisement of the process could have been different and different approaches could have been taken to ensure more people know about the service and how it will save their time”*. Now he feels gradually everything is improving and the Dhaka metropolitan police have taken some more digital initiatives for service transformation. He is hopeful for the future.

Interview 3:

This interview participant is aged between 35-40, working in the Gulshan police station as an inspector. Daily, he supervises a team of 15-20 officers working in the station. He takes on a leadership role from time to time to make key decisions about the activities of the station following the guidance of his supervisors. The online gd platform was the first digital process transformation that he encountered. Although there are numerous approaches are now being introduced for the improvement of service delivery to citizens, the journey towards this was not straightforward.

He mentioned when the online GD process was first proposed by the previous DMP commissioner, it was very much appreciated as part of the vision of the “Digital Bangladesh” initiative taken by the Prime Minister’s office. *“However, there was no central system designed*

yet, so we were sceptical about how it is going to be managed after the implementation”, he went on to say.

It was decided by the ministry of local government and police chiefs of different police stations which processes will be included in the online platform. After careful consideration, they went ahead with the non-serious crimes which did not require the police force for deeper investigation. Typically, the not dangerous offences include lost/theft of certificates, pickpocketing, stolen goods from vehicles, information about new tenants, drivers, maids, caretakers etc. and citizens had to go to the police station to file the general diary. With the new system, they can do it at their convenience using their home computers or mobile phones.

“IT analysts were recruited for the police department following the government recruitment protocols and designed the initial system for us”, he commented. They talked to each one of the police stations to understand their part in the GD filing process to incorporate them into the online system. All the paper copies of various forms were included which were done manually. The system analysts informed us that the system is well protected and some shortcomings could be proven detrimental to the system. But the higher officials decided to go ahead with the platform and released the system for the public to use.

“The initial challenges were many. If I look back and think when it was first implemented, I will call it a mess” he stated. There were no provisions for ID verification and therefore, loads of fraudulent complaints were being lodged. There was no system in place to track those applications as people were using fake names, addresses and telephone numbers. The police staff were stressing a lot to verify and investigate those countless fake GDs. Additionally, there were no ICT regulations in place to incorporate a version of a digital signature at that time. “We are talking about 6/7 years ago, the digitalisation did not start yet”, he added. So, regardless of filing a GD online, one had to come to the police station where they filed a complaint online to manually sign it and get the paper copy. The purpose of making the whole system digital and hassle-free thus could not be fulfilled.

Besides, as per the IT team’s concerns, the system was not protected by any firewalls. There were numerous attacks by hackers to get the citizen’s valuable information. With no security in place, the citizens were reluctant to use it as they were scared of data theft. *“This was being published by the media as a failed attempt and our reputation was being hampered. Generally, people do not like to get in business with the police for numerous reasons- they find it distressing going over to the station, the countless visits and questions and forms they need to*

fill before the actual process can start, and amongst all these, the news of it being a failed attempt was not very appealing for our image” he commented. The police departments had to run their campaign to make the citizens more knowledgeable and make them trust the online platform.

Although the current system has been updated with the new ICT policies to include a digital signature and upload identification documents in the portal to verify the person who’s making a complaint, the marketing of the platform is still not enough. A recent survey done by the DMP has revealed that most people do not know about the system as it was not advertised to them properly.

When asked about how the general police staff took the approach, he said before the design and implantation of the process, a general survey was done by the high officials and the IT team to determine what is the state of staff perception and understanding of the process. *“Unfortunately, most of the junior level staffs did not have sufficient knowledge about computing skills, general understanding of the term ‘innovation of process’ and gave the opinion that they do not think the process will be successful”*, he said. But it did not discourage the superiors as they arranged more training to make the staff comfortable with the process. The government funding for police system innovation was relatively low at that point. So the arrangement of resources like IT equipment, the required number of computers and necessary hardware at the police stations were hard to achieve. Besides, no reward system in place and a slow process of promotion made it difficult to keep people motivated in learning the new skills as they did not feel it was important.

The leadership approach according to him was quite appropriate but definitely not enough. The police chiefs tried their best to get the process running and make the staff trained but they failed to provide enough resources in order to do so. A large number of the police staff’s basic salary do not allow them to have an up-to-date computer or internet connection at home, so they did not have an idea about what to do or how to practice their learning at home. Furthermore, the recruitment policy of the police department does not take into account their basic computer knowledge to date, so unless that is resolved, the interviewee is not sure how their future endeavours will become successful in the long run. Also, there should be a bonus scheme or reward system in place so the staff can feel the enthusiasm for learning new skills.

Interview 4:

The next participant is one of the police sergeants, aged between 35-40, working in the Wari police station. He said he does not understand the technical aspects of the system so he has no idea what happened in the project but he can give a general idea about what happened inside the police force, how the staff coped with the changing process and how his superiors managed it.

He mentioned on an average day, a police staff has to go through many duties and most of them are still being done on paper. Creating records of the complaints, verification checks, investigation data, maintenance and records of criminals spending nights in the police station lockup- all data is kept on paper. *“It is a gigantic task to maintain and preserve those paper copies, and that’s why I appreciate the initiative of being innovative in everyday life. The application of e-governance in the police department will ease the administrative tasks and it creates an effective workflow”*.

First, the internal staff were briefed in a general conference by the supervising officials (inspectors and commissioners) about the automation of the GD filing services. DMP was the first to come forward and be part of the pilot metropolitan to implement it and if successful, the local government will go forward and start automating other services in the police department as well as other metropolitan city police departments will also start the online process. *“We were given duties to hand over all the requirements and necessary forms to the IT team so they can include them in the online system. The team also spent a good amount of time speaking to all department staff to understand the process better”*. The police stations were provided with some basic materials at the beginning like computers, printers and such to replace the old system of storing data by writing manually. It was done to get the staff used to the new digital process.

Gradually, the process got implemented. Most of the staff took it positively, however, did not use it that much initially. Some training was provided but then again, not all of them had computer and internet facilities at home to practice, so it was tough to get them accustomed to digitization.

When asked whether he thinks the automation is successful, he described that although it might sound effective on the surface, in reality, the change in the service delivery still needs some time to be properly utilized by the staff and the service users. Most police staff’s perception of using technology in daily tasks is relatively still very low. Besides, most of their social background and salary do not allow them to use technology outside of the workplace and thus,

limits their adaptability. Additionally, the poor salary and complicated promotion system at the workplace do not make the staff enthusiastic about any change as they do not see it changing their condition to a better level.

Similarly, the assumption that the citizens will be able to use the service using their smartphones or laptop also seems a bit unrealistic according to the participant. Although Bangladesh is supposedly offering internet services utilizing their own satellite and submarine cables, the private companies offering broadband services are still not covering all the areas of Dhaka metropolitan city, let alone the whole country. Besides, the government-operated broadband connection is slower than other services and relatively costs higher than most South Asian countries. These make it harder for citizens to access the service properly as well as for the police station staff to get proper training and utilize it in the workplace. *“The infrastructure, as well as the job reward scheme for the police department, needs to be revisited in order to make the staff more eager for changes and be more supportive in the process”* he emphasised.

In terms of encouraging a creative atmosphere, he said in police work and specifically the department he works in hardly has any scope for thinking outside the box. The police staff can be creative in solving a crime, no doubt; but sometimes the traditional ways of solving a problem still take advantage. *“The new way of doing things is not entirely forbidden, but it is sometimes a bit frowned upon depending on who is in charge of the case”*. The automation project of the police department started as an ambitious aim by the then-police chief, but it was time the department took a leading step to greet the digitalisation of service delivery. He was a visionary who took the first step and his subordinates had to carry on doing it and make it better if possible. Not all the leading police officers are bad, otherwise, the whole system will be collapsed and as per the interviewee, there is hardly anything to be done by them unless the government starts looking after its law regulation and most important service. The staff are underpaid, there is not enough funding for ICT training and digitization and the working hostels and training are not sufficient and only some chosen ones get to go abroad and get special training. *“When you do not provide enough resources to the service which provides security to every single member of the population, you simply will not get the expected results from them,”* he said.

5.5.3 Conversations with the IT personnel:

Interview 5:

One of the system analysts of the DMP was the next participant. This interviewee is aged between 38-45, has been working in the digital sector for almost 8+ years now and has been working on the online GD project since its initiation. She not only worked on the digitization process and helped build the initial design, but she also worked as the main press correspondent for the project on behalf of the DMP.

She talked about how the journey of this project started. *“The law enforcement process provided by the police is a very difficult one if you think about it. In 2009, the government thought about how this most needed service can be more convenient for the citizens and can reach the growing population of Dhaka City.”* The officials realised that the digitalisation of some processes has the potential to offer a better and more effective service and how it will aid the Digital Bangladesh initiative taken by the prime minister’s office. The new ICT law reformation paved the way to incorporate digital technology into the police force. The pilot project started with DMP and if it was successful, to be introduced to other metropolitan cities as well.

“Our initial requirement for the project was to create a platform that people can access sitting at home at their convenience and will not have to visit the police station for everything. Some of the services that do not require detailed investigation can be incorporated in the online platform initially and so we created the online GD platform for non-serious offences.” The project was very enjoyable, and the participants learned a lot working on this as it was one of the very first ICT projects in government organisations.

When asked if the project was successful, she mentioned their team could not reach their projected outcome in the beginning. The system went live for the public despite the project having lots of technical and design flaws. She said it was not related to any lack of skilled people as the ICT team in DMP was very efficient to design the system.

First of all, several hacking incidents took place because the protection of the system was flawed. Although it managed to recover from the incident, the web portal was up and running in little to no time. The recurrent hacking incident mostly took place on the website contents and information parameters. *“To get rid of this problem, we shifted the database to the local LAN of the DMP. But even that was not protected by a proper firewall”*, she added.

Secondly, the system did not have any option initially for the user's digital signature, so they had to go to the police station for the signature. It did not make the system more efficient as the citizens had to physically visit the police station anyway. *"Back when the project took off, there was no law for digital signatures to be incorporated in the system and it affected the success of the project,"* she said. Now the problem has been solved as there is an option for digital signature and other ID verification steps, but till now the citizens have to visit the police stations for collecting the copy of GD as mostly the soft copy is not received, so the project is still not 100 per cent efficient in service delivery.

To answer the question of internal challenges, she said the main problem was they did not have resources. There was a lack of computers, the LAN was not properly built up, the system was not connected to the one-stop citizen access point yet and it was tough to get all the staff trained. Another point to be mentioned was that the police station morale was not high. The officials were not too enthusiastic about the project and it took some time to get them involved and make them understand how it will ease their job as well as reduce the amount of paperwork and increase transparency, resulting in a good reputation for the department.

The higher officials, specifically the then DMP commissioner provided the best possible support to make his police force more efficient. From the beginning, he was very involved in the project and took necessary decisions to mitigate the problems and make the change more acceptable for the staff. Some of the staff still do not understand the system well but training was offered to them. He ordered his subordinate officers in authority to create a proper training schedule to include all the police station staff. He also tried to generate more funding from the local government ministry as per technical requirements.

Talking about the external challenges, she stated *"We never had any lack of skilled staff to design and maintain the system, it was the lack of government policy to support the innovations and the lack of resources in terms of both financial and equipment. The project was not even advertised well to gather funding from other sources other than government"*.

But the system has gone through many changes so far, she is looking forward to keeping working in her role to maintain a secure data transaction between the police forces and citizens of Dhaka city and gradually transform all the services digitally.

Interview 6:

This participant worked on the online GD project for Bangladesh police as part of the external IT team. He is aged between 35-40. He is working for the IT services provided for 5+ years and they did numerous projects for both the government and private sector companies. Currently, he is working on another government project.

Initially, DMP introduced an online GD diary filling system so that people could file complaints from home, the process needed the person to come to the police station physically to complete the process and thus it kind of made the main aim of the process useless. Keeping this in mind, DMP wanted to fully automate the entire process where users will not only be able to file the GD online but they will receive a verification code and a soft copy of the filed complaint without actually visiting the police station. *“Our team designed the full automation process via the technology being proactive”*, he stated. With the new system, each user who has filed a complaint will receive a QR verification code in order to access their soft copy, this ensures the identity and valuable personal information provided in the GD are well secured. If the users do not have their desktop or laptop at any point, they can access it using their smartphones or tablets as well.

When asked about the challenges, he said there were many- firstly, the previous process had so many technical hurdles that the external IT team needed to overcome. The system was not protected by any firewall as it was not integrated into the government’s one-stop service access point system yet. *“We tried to overcome these issues by first integrating the system to the one-stop access point under the a2i project run by the Prime Minister's Office. This central system is now providing the much-needed firewall for data security”* he mentioned.

Secondly, when they started working on the project, the government was yet to go through the ICT policy reformation for including the identification documents and digital signatures in any online system. This lack of policy made the previous system very vulnerable to misuse as there was no verification process in place. Anyone could have filed a complaint against anyone and there was no way of figuring out who did that. He said, *“Now, we have included digital signatures in the system, so the user must upload his digital signature and therefore, do not have to physically go to the station. Additionally, he/she has to upload one or 2 forms of ID for the verification process and only then the system will let them move forward into the next phase.”*

Another significant problem was the infrastructure of the police stations. According to the interviewee, “*I do not want to put a finger on any particular one, but the majority of the police stations still need to go through a major restructuring process. Not only the stations did not have enough digital equipment, but the office buildings were also sometimes really old, and the hardware installation and maintenance process were tough*”. When the project first started, the funding was really low but later it got better as they were able to bring in external experts.

The government, although has put enough funding into the digitisation process now, it still needs to go a long way before the entire public service will be fully automated. Although Bangladesh has their satellite now to provide a high-speed internet connection, the speed is relatively lower than the private providers. The police stations, of course, use the government-provided internet connection and therefore, the connectivity and running of a smoother operation using digital services are much slower than anticipated to date.

The buildings and the resources provided to make the police stations digital have to be ample, the staff needs to be educated to understand the importance of digitisation and be willing to get trained rather than forced to. Properly skilled professionals also need to be hired to maintain the system and train, internal staff. Although the then chief police commissioner was a visionary person who took the initiative to transform the service delivery and make police services more citizen-friendly, the staff under him did not fully cooperate in making it a success. Still, a lot of training and persuasion are needed to reach all levels of police staff.

5.6 Mobile network-based cyclone early warning system for coastal areas:

Bangladesh is one of the countries that are most susceptible to Tropical Cyclone (TC)-related calamities. Bangladesh is particularly vulnerable to natural calamities due to its geographic location. The country is situated near the mouth of the warm-water Bay of Bengal, which acts as a cyclone vortex in the region. Every year, Bangladesh is the target of catastrophic storms. Furthermore, the majority of Bangladesh's territory and a significant chunk of its 180 million people lie below 40 feet above sea level. Fourteen of Bangladesh's nineteen coastal districts have high or moderate cyclone risk (*Khan, Bhuiyan & Rahman, 2010*). Around 40 million people live in these exposed districts right now (*Bureau of Statistics, 2020*).

When Sheikh Hasina was elected Prime Minister in 2008, she and her government officially acknowledged the relationship between coastal Bangladesh's survival and climate change. She elevated the Disaster Management and Relief Bureau to the status of a full-fledged ministry. It

is in charge of risk mitigation efforts, such as implementing humanitarian assistance programmes and coordinating government and nongovernment-led initiatives (*Wazed,2017*). The Bangladesh government is putting tremendous effort into creating an appropriate methodology for managing cyclone situations to protect the safety of citizens in coastal areas. As a result, during the previous few decades, citizens' reaction to evacuation orders has vastly improved.

The Bangladesh Department of Disaster Management (DDM) has recently created three mobile-network-based warning message transmission mechanisms to make warning messages easily accessible to coastal people and disaster management committees on the field level.

1. The Cell Broadcasting System can be utilised to transmit warning messages to a specific demographic group, such as coastal inhabitants.
2. Interactive Voice Response is a means of listening to a recorded warning message by dialling a phone number.
3. Short Message Service (SMS) is a text messaging service built specifically for disaster management committees on the ground. In cyclone situations, members of these committees receive continual updates on their cell phones about the oncoming cyclone.

For the sake of the research the stakeholders chosen (see figure below) for interview are from the ministry of disaster management, the Cyclone preparedness programme (CPP) implementation board, scientists from Bangladesh Meteorological departments to understand the technical aspects and difficulties and the committee for speedy dissemination for disaster-related warning/signals.

5.6.1 Conversations with the officials of the Ministry and DMD:

Interview 1:

This participant is currently working in a very important position in the Ministry of disaster management and relief and has actively participated in and supervised key decision-making processes. The department she works for directly plays a vital role in the policymaking of the disaster-related issues of the country.

She described that Bangladesh is very susceptible to natural disasters, specifically tropical cyclones and floods. Every year the country sees at least three major storms. Due to this situation, the ministry along with the help of the Prime minister's office is working tirelessly

to develop a strong infrastructure to improve the disaster preparedness programme. As part of the agenda, a mobile-based early warning system had been included in the already existing process. This system has been designed to reach a mass population in one go using their mobile phones. The government has teamed up with the mobile network providers to broadcast the warning message to the coastal population, an interactive voice messaging service and an SMS-based service. *“The primary reason for this move was that if people were properly prepared for frequent disasters, their effects would be minimised, reducing the need for assistance and rehabilitation”*, she commented.

Answering the question about how the idea was generated for the mobile-based system, she said there is a dedicated innovation team in the ministry who looks after the policies and decides on the new idea after careful consideration of all related factors. For this particular project in the investigation, the ministry looked into opportunities derived from the use of ICT in disaster response during a post-Haiti earthquake meeting of technology and development in 2010. *“The department also regularly researches ICT methods to utilise which are being used in the other developing disaster-prone countries”*, she stated.

Before implementing the mobile-based system, the ministry with the help of UNDP and the World bank did a thorough investigation on whether it will be a feasible idea or not. In the research, SMS facilities and connecting via mobile phones were viewed as key measures in responding to disasters because of the large volume of mobile phone usage. It was also discovered that many people are left homeless and on the move after a tragedy. Sending out messages via mobile phones can be an effective way to keep people organised and operate post-disaster operations more efficiently in these instances.

She declined to call it a failed project as it is still ongoing, and people are using it. However, mentioned that it is still under scrutiny to improve various aspects. Firstly, she thinks the major goal of reaching a massive population living in the coastal areas has been achieved mostly. Since the price of mobile phones is relatively cheaper, it has been shown in various investigations taken by the ministry that even in remote areas, almost 70% households have access to at least one mobile phone. However, the population not being educated enough, and sometimes does not realise the necessity of utilizing their mobile phones to avoid damage in times of disaster. They still prefer the warnings preached by the local religious institutions, NGOs and field-level staff using megaphones.

Secondly, the early warning message forecasted by the BMD department recently faced backlash due to not being accurate and created confusion in two previous major cyclone events. Due to the confusion, people fail to grasp the severity of the situation and the major damage that had been done. Similarly, in another case, they issued high-level risk alerts in the areas where it was not needed and unnecessary precautions were taken, wasting a lot of resources. *“These occurrences created a level of mistrust among the population and they showed less interest in using the IVR or mobile broadcasting in later incidents”* she added.

Thirdly, the use of IVR is not free of cost. Although it’s very cheap still not being free does not make it very appealing to the population who lives under the poverty line. Furthermore, complete dependence on the mobile-based system is not very promising since communication networks that have been damaged or destroyed will result in a complete communications blackout in the impacted region. *“Still the mobile network has not reached all the areas, even if they do, the connection is very poor. The offshore fishermen are yet to be included in the system as there is no network yet on the open sea, making them most prone to damage”* she said.

The ministry is trying its best to update ICT policies to improve the mobile-based early warning system. She stated that to make the mobile-based early warning programme successful, the Ministry of Disaster Management has generated a series of policy, strategy, and programme actions to address disaster management through mitigation, preparedness, and recovery. For comprehensive disaster management preparations, the government established a national council and numerous committees at the national, district, Upazila (sub-district), and union (local council) levels. *“These sub-level committees have been formed to prepare the population before any disaster and to provide them with sufficient training to utilise the mobile-based warning system better. They are very important as the SMS-based service is designed for them to get all the updated information and then make the decisions accordingly”* she added.

She said the flaws in the existing process make it hard to become an ultimate success. The problem with the accuracy of BMD forecasts is being looked into. The government is recently overhauling its budget allocation in important sectors and the disaster department has always been a bit neglected. There are always more pressing issues like a disease outbreak, transportation, crime or economic crisis due to the global downturn which makes it hard to allocate enough funds for the purchase of resources or recruiting more people. *“The recruitment policy of the government is a bit strict, you cannot just go ahead and hire people when you*

need to bring a change; you got to work with the existing ones”, she said. The ministries sometimes you see people getting promoted because of their political connection not because of their qualifications. This can be seen only in a few cases, however, has its impact on the work being done. The BMD department needs new equipment, need training facilities for the scientists working there and need more qualified scientists who could work with the generated data. The lack of training facilities creates a motivational gap in the field level workers who in turn do feel encouraged to keep doing their work and the coastal people suffers the consequences. The ministry is now trying to make new policies to generate more and more funding to look after the people and retain staff.

When asked about the leadership approach to overcoming the challenges and how creativity is nurtured, she mentioned that the ministry wanted to give everyone equal participation and be a part of the team by creating different decision-making bodies at different levels of disaster preparedness. The SMS-based warning service has been specifically developed for the field-level management staff so that they can receive the forecast and changes in warning levels promptly and make decisions. *“This system is still not getting popular among the staff as they feel they do not have the capability of making the decisions and even if they take, there is a lack of accountability”*, she commented. She further added that due to the lack of confidence in taking part in decision-making, they also do not want to come forward and have their opinion. The ministries are still to date following traditional principles in managing staff and the field-level staff hardly have any scope to change the process. The low pay, low scope of training and managers not being motivated themselves, do not nourish the subordinates to be opinionated, creative and enthusiastic in their work; and it impacts the services they provide and the training they run to educate the people about the new early warning system.

Interview 2:

The next participant is a member of the innovation department of the ministry of disaster and relief. He mentioned the department is currently reviewing several improvements to the current mobile-based early warning system. He has been a part of the innovation team for the last 3 years and working for the department of disaster management for the last 10 years.

The system has been in place for over 8 years now and has seen some ups and downs. The department took some initial ideas from similar approaches in place for developing and developed countries and proposed a system of their own that can help provide alerts to the cyclone-affected coastal area population. *“We were very interested in this project due to the*

high volume of mobile users in Bangladesh and how it can complement the existing practices of disaster alert in place”, he stated. There are three systems and they all equally work to prepare the population before the disaster and minimise damage.

Although the project has been initiated for a long time now, it has some areas for improvement he said. The forecasting provided by the scientists of BMD needs to be accurate. They have provided some inaccurate warnings in the past which have negatively impacted the credibility of the forecast among the coastal population. BMD does not have the development of new and renovated observatories, needs updated modelling techniques and requires more skilled scientists who can interpret the data correctly. Currently, they provide the message through an interactive voice message service. The message is updated three times a day, and to listen one must dial a number and use the option to listen to the message.

Now, the people receiving the message need to be educated enough to utilise it and understand the technical factors. *“The updates provide the state and level of warnings, they do not provide an impact-based warning to give them a full idea of what would happen if they do not take precautions”* he added. Again, sometimes the cheaper mobile phones do not have an option to receive Bengali text messages and the vast majority not having the minimum literacy to read English texts cannot follow through with the message therefore, the system lacks acceptance.

He further mentioned, that to be able to utilise the system in full capacity, the vast majority of the population needs to be trained accordingly. The field and district levels staff are the main face to facilitate the workshops and make the mass aware of the systems. *“We can see a massive gap in their part to engage actively in the process to make it a success”* he stated. The reason behind this according to him is that the majority of them reach the topmost position at the district level at the end of their careers (55+). This role, however, ought to be exceedingly dynamic to effectively reach out to distressed people during an emergency. It's difficult at this age (nearing retirement) and causes issues at any point in the process.

Furthermore, they have a limited potential for advancement in their current position. It is a significant contributor to job demotivation and harms performance. Additionally, volunteers (under CPP) play a critical role in assessing damage and distributing relief before, during, and after a cyclone warning. However, they do not get sufficient training, there is no reward or incentive in place. Although they are recruited as volunteers, there is no practical incentive to keep them motivated.

Resource allocation plays a major role in the success of any project. Every year in July, the department receives its allocation from the government and then it gets distributed to the required areas. There is more budget allocated to deal with the post-disaster phase and very little for the actual innovation, development of new ideas/systems and improving the existing systems that provide pre-disaster phase warnings and forecasts. This lack of budget creates a serious issue in looking after the field level staff, recruiting more skilled people and arranging appropriate training as well as modernised equipment for the betterment of the service.

“I think the bureaucratic policies are a loophole which hinders any kind of innovation process. You have to go through so many policies and regulations just to get them to hear your ideas, it is understandable why we do not get enough ground-breaking ideas coming from the public sector”, he commented.

He wanted to point out the management aspect as well. According to him, several bodies working under the ministry create a complex environment when it comes to making decisions and causing difficulty for field employees in implementing orders. Although the DDM has taken some steps to improve training and reformation of governing bodies, it will still take a long time to put into effect rather than just be on paper.

5.6.2 Conversations with the official in the CPP:

Interview 3:

This participant is aged between 45-50 working as a Union Development Officer in the CPP department of the ministry of disaster management and relief. He has completed his university education and joined the public sector. He is been working relentlessly for the last 6 years in order to develop the planning of disaster management at the Union Parishad levels.

He gave a brief overview of the duties of CPP officials. Their responsibilities are panned out in a few phases. In normal times while there is no risk of disasters, the CPP team along with its volunteers work to educate the coastal and disaster-prone area citizens about the warning systems, run classes, and arrange seminars and workshops to give them a better idea about how they can utilise all the government system in place. In the alert and disaster phase, the team works tirelessly to warn everyone using all the early warning dissemination channels, make sure they reach the shelters and conduct rescue operations. *“I look after a team of 50 officials and around 1500 volunteers and in the post-disaster period, I instruct officials and volunteers to send a preliminary report of loss and damage to support post-disaster relief and*

rehabilitation efforts” he stated. It is also CPP’s responsibility to collect data on cyclone losses and damage, write a report, and transmit it to CPP Headquarters, the Union, Upazila, and District Disaster Management Committees.

He described the work process by saying when a depression forms in the BoB, cyclone warnings are broadcast to a huge number of people, including the President, Prime Minister, all Ministries, Directorates, and Departments, the Armed Forces, the media, humanitarian organisations, and the CPP. CPP then sends warning messages to their coastal nodes, primarily the Upazila level offices, via radio, and from there to the Unions and villages via cell phones or Very High-Frequency radio, using its own channel. He is thankful that the cell phone companies reached an arrangement with the Bangladeshi government and now, early warnings are issued by all six mobile phone providers using the Cell Broadcasting System, Short Message Service, and Interactive Voice Response.

“The cell broadcasting system works in line with the message sent by the BMD, updating the citizens three times a day, you can access the voice response by dialling a certain number and the SMS service is really to reach us quickly in order to get updates” he mentioned. It is a very futuristic aspect and the government took inspiration from other disaster-prone countries in the world. It is still an underdeveloped concept according to him. It offers much help and has prospects of becoming a successful one in the future. Firstly, Bangladesh's high mobile penetration (around 75 per cent of the population) provides the potential to improve this communication and dissemination component. Secondly, the SMS service to alert the field level workers and the CPP staff has been proven very beneficial in terms of taking steps promptly to mitigate the damage caused by cyclones.

Thirdly, the interactive voice recording can be accessed by anyone with a phone by dialling the number 10941 and the attempt of aiming to get national-level information about the communities that may be affected is highly appreciated. *“We have done a recent study among the recipients and they agreed it is helpful for them. However, it does not capture all the factors,”* he added.

The project has many downsides that still need some revisiting and planning. According to him, first and foremost, although the cell broadcasting service reaches a maximum number population, a large number of them still lack the basic education to utilise it properly. When conducting training workshops for the coastal citizens, a good number of people did not have an exact idea how to use it in times of dismay. Again, the participants in the workshop and

training were mostly men so a lack of interest in women is very noticeable. To be able to engage everyone in the process equally the management needs to be proactive and layout constructive approaches to get everyone involved as much as they can. Additionally, the authenticity of the message is still a big confusion for the users. *“A lot of them raised the issue that they received several messages from different numbers alerting them, and as a result became confused about what to follow”*, he mentioned. This problem is due to having different organisations working at the same level as the government and their involvement not being in harmony with the DMD and CPP, which is creating a lot of confusion. Furthermore, most users not having a basic knowledge of English, the warning messages need to be in Bengali which can be read and understood by the people. Then again, not all the handsets support Bengali fonts so the Ministry needs to focus on making handsets available at a lower price that can also support Bengali.

Again, the numbers of the CPP staff and the ground level staffs keep changing or they carry multiple sim cards for personal use. Therefore, sometimes the number that is recorded in the DMD system is no longer valid and the message does not reach the user. This can be prevented by allocating all the members of staff a fixed number for office use only which must be operational at all times. *“I think the management also needs to increase accountability among the staff so even if they carry multiple numbers, they report it back to the senior management so they can be traced in time of need”*, he added.

He commented that the frequency and accuracy of the warning message sent by BMD need to be thoroughly checked before publishing. In previous cases of disaster, BMD failed to provide accurate warning messages which led to more damage than anticipated. The training and recruitment of staff at the field level is another matter of concern. The involvement of CPP in early dissemination, warning the local people and post-disaster phase rescue and rehabilitation is of utmost importance, however, hardly there are any updated training sessions for the officials to upgrade their skills. The recruitment seems to be frozen due to a funding crisis, there is no recognition of the work the volunteers do and as a result, the CPP team is losing valuable volunteers to work for them.

“I think the higher management needs to be proactive in the decision-making process. There are so many governing bodies working under the Ministry, the chain of command somehow goes missing and a lack of firm decision leads to confusion, thus creating delays in alerting people” he stated. The management should decide about allocating more funding for the training and development of staff in the pre-disaster phase as prevention is always better. When

asked about how creativity is encouraged within the organisations he mentioned not having any sort of creative discussion with the subordinates as only a handful of them understands the need of being creative. It is a friendly culture within the workplace, but he would not agree it is a cultivating place of innovative ideas. *“I do not think there is a lack of creativity, they are just not enthusiastic enough to come forward and have their say. Mostly because they are not even being encouraged for the current work they do. Why would they want to go an extra mile?”*, he said. More and more funding is being allocated to the post-disaster phase and if they do not invest in elevating the skill level of the staff, staff retention and idea generation would be an issue as well as generating awareness among people.

Interview 4:

This participant is aged between 45-50, working for the senior project officer post for the last 8 years. He has completed his bachelor’s degree from a well-established public university in Bangladesh. He was previously working in the victim rehabilitation department for the disaster-prone areas under the Ministry of Disaster and Relief and then took on this opportunity at CPP Headquarters.

According to him, weather predictions and cyclone hazard warnings are prepared by BMD’s SWC. The SWC disseminates cyclone forecasts and advisories through various media (television, radio, and newsprint) and the headquarters of the Cyclone Preparedness Program based on information acquired from radar observations, satellite images, and field observatories, and the Regional Specialized Meteorological Centre in New Delhi. *“We (CPP), then send the information to various coastal zone offices, which then transmit it to the sub-district disaster management committee, which then pass it on to Union Level Disaster Management Committees”*, he stated.

Talking about the current mobile broadcasting EWS he commented that an Interactive Voice Response (IVR)-based early warning service is currently operational, which may be accessed by any of the existing mobile phone providers. This service delivers information about five issues for BDT 2.15 per minute by contacting a specific number, 10941. The free warning from the SWC (three times a day) is the major source of information for persons living along the shore who are at risk. Before starting the implementation of the service, DDM has gone through a pilot study, which has shown great promise because it can reach a big number of people fast in a certain area without the need to gather their phone numbers.

However, there are several problems for which this system is not an entirely successful one. First of all, Bangladesh's high illiteracy rate makes it difficult for people to comprehend text-based messages. Although Bangladeshi technology is quickly developing, not all mobile phones support the Bangla script. As a result, messages are conveyed in English, making them even more difficult to comprehend. Additionally, the message generated sometimes fails to be exact and accurate which creates an even more confusing situation for the citizens to understand the criticality and take important steps to minimise the loss.

Secondly, the SMS services generated for ground-level staff to be more prepared are seeing some difficulties as well. It takes a long time to update and maintain. The difficulty in gathering and preserving the phone numbers of government officials is the biggest obstacle faced by DDM while using SMS. *“This is due to the fact that people in Bangladesh have many SIM cards, and government officials shift every two to three years, therefore phone numbers change as well”*, he mentioned.

Again, Various officials (civil and military), private, and non-governmental organisations (NGOs) collaborate during a disaster to avert harm and provide urgent help to compensate for emergency losses. As a result, complicated and short-term administrative structures emerge during this time, which frequently results in inter-organizational conflicts. He commented, *“This leads to a major detrimental impact on the proper utilisation of EWS and the post-disaster management of relief and distribution efforts.”* As a result of visible or concealed disagreements, mismatching, and non-cooperation among personnel under the same administrative authority, planning, organising, leading, and controlling get disrupted.

He went on to say, there is a lack of training for the people in CPP. Recruitment is frozen for the last couple of years due to a lack of funding. There is no fresh source of new talent. The pay is not adequate, and the job security compared to the private or NGO counterpart's disaster-related departments is poor. *“Therefore, we are failing to attract new, talented people who could have made an impact in changing the situation”*. At the moment, CPP only has 10-15 volunteers in every coastal area, but this number is decreasing with time due to no proper training, lack of motivation and appreciation.

The leadership approaches taken by the ministry are sufficient he thinks. They are micromanaging so many departments that the chain of command somehow gets lost along the way. When the actual warning is generated from the SWC, by the time it reaches the ground level staff, the private sector counterparts start acting and it creates confusion among the

citizens on who to believe. *“It eventually creates a mistrust of public sector bodies working and the dependence on private and charitable sector increases”*, he added. The ministry should go through proper strategy revisits in terms of committee formation and a more centralised chain of decision-making.

Furthermore, the funding to develop an accurate EWS system through mobile broadcasting needs to be strengthened. Still, the major focus is on post-disaster phase mitigation rather than improving the early stages of preparation which can prevent a lot of loss. Adjustments of IVM and SMS are needed to incorporate them into the available handsets used by the coastal people. There should be an option to send the message in Bengali so all the people can read it and they need to be educated about the system a lot more to make it effective.

5.6.3 Conversations with the BMD Scientists:

Interview 5:

The meteorologist interviewed was aged between 40-50 and had a background in mathematics. He has been working in the role for more than 8 years now. TC forecasting is a non-routine task that meteorologists conduct in addition to their regular duties during cyclone emergencies. This unit where the participants work is entirely responsible for monitoring, forecasting, and disseminating TC warnings in Bangladesh.

According to him, the current TC forecasting approach is a hybrid of three TC forecasting techniques- steering airflow determination, averaging over prior TCs and persistence and climatology. He stated, *“We use each methodology independently rather than merging the outputs of these three systems. It’s called the hybrid forecasting methodology”*. The systems are rather complicated for a common person to understand. In the first phase, the data generated from the ground level are interpolated and shown on the map for producing continuous fields of wind direction and wind-speed information. In the second phase, wind direction and speed at a pressure level that best corresponds to the TC's movement direction and speed are compared with the wind information within the TC vortex and the last stage is very crucial. In phase 3, The future movement direction and intensity of the present TC are estimated by averaging the motion and intensity features of these historical analogues (averaging across TCs), as well as by utilising regression to relate the current TC's recent movement direction and intensity to that of previous analogues. *“When combining the output of the three systems to anticipate TC track and intensity, we rely on their professional knowledge”*, he added.

To forecast the findings, they create warning signals based on self-generated and numerical-model-generated forecasts obtained from India's Regional Specialized Meteorological Centre (RSMC), with self-produced predictions receiving the most weight. *“During a cyclone, we issue new warning messages in critical situations via special weather bulletins that are broadcasted using the radio, television and in recent times, using the cellular network service, either you get a message texted to your phone or you can call a number to listen to a recorded message to get the level of the alert”.*

When he was asked what he thinks of the success of the system in place, he said he would not call it 100% successful. There are many problems with the forecasting system at the moment, which are affecting the type of warning messages they want to send. The main system that is used by BMD to send warning messages to the maritime and river port areas recently followed the old colonial British mechanism, where there were no processes incorporated to alert citizens of the coastal area. Due to this issue, in the times of Sidr and Mahasen (2 previous TCs), BMD could not provide any safety instructions for the residents. *“It was such a relief when DDM incorporated resident safety measures in the warning system. it helped a lot with the later incidents”* he commented.

Again, he mentioned that meteorologists are unable to check the existing TC forecasting system's prediction ability because no benchmarking approach is in use. As a result, the precision level of the created forecast cannot be included in the warning message. Additionally, there is a lack of skilled staff who can utilize the advanced numerical models properly. The recruitment is biased, people are still not hired based on their technical and academic knowledge; one could get his way up using political or family connections which drastically reduce the quality of forecasting analysis. He described, *“These models are not advanced, and most meteorologists lack the data-processing and computational abilities needed to alter them to create forecasts for new meteorological phenomena such as TCs.”*

Again, he thinks the residents in the coastal area are not known to utilise the service well. Most of the time they did not understand the message that was sent to them and response time is still very low. Besides, in times of natural disasters, it is possible to overlook the use of the number given to listen through a whole message as people are in a panic. *“The field level staff should be more proactive to provide a better understanding of this mobile broadcasting service to citizens. Not only will it give them ample time to prepare and reach the nearest shelter, but it will also reduce the fatality and damage”* he stated.

Talking about leadership approaches to mitigate the barriers, the respondent mentioned that he does not think the decisions taken by the ministry and higher officials are enough. There is little to no opportunity for professional development and training and the recruitment process of scientists in BMD still needs to take into consideration a lot of skills before appointing someone in the role. There is little to no chance of proposing a new idea or bringing something new to the table to improve the existing system. Hardly anyone shows any creative venture due to a lack of understanding of the scientific aspects. Furthermore, the resources and funding for the research are still not enough. *“We never had enough funding to buy or upgrade equipment, some of the departments in BMD are still using old bulky computers and older versions of software. Funding should be increased so we can improve our forecasting system. We are dealing with a large population here, so even a little fault on our part can cause massive destruction.”* he commented.

Interview 6:

The next respondent is another meteorological scientist (aged from 45-55) working in the BMD department for the last 10 years. He finished his undergraduate and postgraduate from the most prestigious university in Bangladesh in physics. Later on, he completed another postgraduate and PhD from one of the top universities in the USA and then joined the department.

He described the process as being completed in three phases. After gathering plentiful data and going through multiple analyses (including comparing them to past trends) all-weather predictions and cyclone threat warnings are prepared by this department. The BMD disseminates cyclone forecasts and alerts to various media (television, radio, and newspapers) and uses mobile broadcasting, interactive voice messaging and SMS. They also pass on the information to the headquarters of the Cyclone Preparedness Programme (CPP) based on information acquired from radar observations, satellite images, field observatories, and the Regional Specialized Meteorological Centre (RSMC) in New Delhi. The national headquarter then passes on the information to the district, sub-district and union levels- where the field level committee gets into action to make sure everyone is safe, and the warning message has got through to people.

About the success of the system, he thinks it has contributed to the lesser havoc caused by natural disasters in the last couple of years. In his own words, *“It has significantly reduced the mortality and morbidity likelihoods, reduced the chance of false evictions and increased the chance of early preparation to safeguard the property and cattle.”* But he still thinks there is

a lot to improve when it was mentioned that the statistics and recent studies referred to some errors in the warning system by BMD. These difficulties highlight the accuracy and dependability of cyclone early warnings.

He further commented that he is aware of the incident of Sidr and Mahasen, where (BMD) issued seven special weather update bulletins in which the risk rating for specific ports had abruptly increased from 4 to 10. People were put in danger as a result of the significant variation in two consecutive warnings, which led to distrust in the warning system. He said this is due to the data of wind steering information not being available. It only gets updated every 12 hours whereas the ground level and satellite data is updated every 6 hours. He added, *“Over the Bay of Bengal (BoB), ground-level and upper-level atmospheric data are frequently lacking. Therefore, we have to employ 12-hour old and estimated wind direction and speed over the BoB as input to TC forecasting in such conditions”*. This estimated data creates a scope for errors.

Again, there is not enough skilled staff in the department who can decode generated data properly and go through the analysis. There is not enough scope of training as well so they can develop their skills, the department is constantly underfunded because funds are needed somewhere more important. He sighed saying, *“BMD is unable to use these data to compensate for the BoB's occasional data updates since the received data is frequently in forms that are not supported by current forecasting methodologies, and our scientists lack the necessary skills to re-code the data.”*

Additionally, there is a lack of computational resources at the BMD. According to the interviewee, currently, the department is utilising a cluster computer with 15 quad-cores running at 2.8 GHz apiece and 16 GB of RAM to make forecasts. For complex numerical models, these computational resources are inadequate. He says, *“We need to upscale the devices and upgrade the software and definitely should collaborate with other groups to cross-fertilize technological and intellectual ideas to produce an accurate forecast for the warning system.”*

Another challenge mentioned by him is the social and educational background of the service receivers. With a low literacy rate, the people living in the coastal areas are unable to utilize interactive voice message (IVM) and SMS services properly. They do not know how they can access the information, solely reliant on the announcement of mosques, temples and field-level disaster management workers to let them know what is happening and what needs to be done.

With the previous confusion in the forecast, they also developed mistrust about the mobile broadcasting options.

He said he is not completely satisfied with how the ministry and upper-level decision-makers are handling the situation. *“There is no proper planning, I think. Their decision for the betterment and involving new methods of communication about early cyclone warning sounds promising but lacks proper design and risk management”*, he mentioned.

They have gone ahead and incorporated mobile network services into the system but there is a lack of creativity. They are simply following other developing countries’ footsteps, not researching whether it is being successful or not and what else can they do to improve it. Regarding the funding, the department solely relies on international funding whereas it is high time they start thinking about generating innovative and realistic proposals and securing more funding in the annual budget.

5.6.4 Conversations with the officials in the committee of warning signals:

Interview 7:

This participant is aged between 30-35 and is working as a committee member in the field level of disaster preparedness and early warning signals. He is a university graduate and he is working in this position for the last 5 years. He volunteered as a field-level disaster management worker while he was a student and since he liked working for the people so much, he applied for the position of “Project Implementation Officer” after completing graduation in Project Management from a well-known private university in Bangladesh.

According to him, dissemination, and coordination of early warnings at the field level, as well as related response capability needs, are handled by Disaster Management Committees at the district, Upazila, and union levels, which are often mandated with particular roles and responsibilities by the DDM. He said, *“We are instructed to ensure prompt and efficient dissemination of disaster forecasts and alerts among all district officials, related individuals/organizations, and take steps to submit the messages to the concerned individuals at the Union, Pourashava, and Upazila levels”*. Their main duties are to alert all people who are in danger, evacuate the vulnerable people according to the evacuation plan, review the overall search and rescue operation readiness, and train the search and rescue teams. They also provide awareness to the coastal people about the mobile broadcasting system to get the most out of the early warning system.

When asked whether he thinks the mobile broadcasting method to provide early signals is a successful initiative taken by the DDM, he stated that have already begun to reap substantial benefits because of improved meteorological data obtained through ICT services- mobile messaging and interactive voice messages. Since just 30% of the population has access to electricity, many people did not often have access to other forms of communication such as television or radio, which could be switched off in a crisis. As a result, mobile technology, which is more widely available and widely used, is the most useful. The mobile prices in Bangladesh had significantly fallen in the last few years and a large proportion of the population, even in villages have access to mobile technology and, it seemed like a good plan adopted by Government to provide better communication to alert people in disaster-prone areas.

However, the project has its downsides as well as per him. He commented while talking about challenges, *“Although people have access to mobile phones, they are not fully aware of the services that government provide. When we go and ask them if they have listened to the mobile message, they said they do not know the number to call.”*. So, there is a lot of training needed to make them utilise it at an optimum level. Besides, communication networks that have been damaged or destroyed sometimes result in a complete connectivity outage in the impacted region. Even if a portion of the communications system still managed to operate at the time of the calamity, increased traffic levels quickly overwhelm it.

Additionally, there were several times when the dissemination provided by the BMD has made even the field team confused, let alone the public. In the event of a previous cyclone Mahasen, their inaccurate warning tiers have changed and made the onshore people stay at home than evacuate and made a fatal impact on the number of casualties and damage to properties and cattle. Besides, their warning message still does not manage to reach the offshore fishing boats due to a lack of connectivity. In the matter where there is still an issue of connectivity, it is highly impractical to even think that the mobile broadcasting methods will take over the traditional ways of alarming people such as the use of mosque miking and mass miking by volunteers and field officials using megaphones.

There is a lack of skilled staff at every level of managing disasters in the country. *“Despite our role being highly important, there are constant vacancies in the field level posts. There is no appropriate and up-to-date training for us and therefore, it creates a lack of motivation and people eventually leave”*, he added further to the ongoing challenges. He also mentioned that

the accuracy of the warning message needs to be ensured and there might be a lack of skilled professionals who can deliver it. If the main observations are not correct, the people will not trust the warning messages and the mobile broadcasting system will face more failure in the future. The connectivity range of mobile networks should be broadened and well established to make sure everyone is under cell phone coverage and can use their phones even in times of cyclones.

The most important problem according to him is that pre-disaster risk reduction and early warning distribution are given less attention than post-disaster recovery actions. The government is taking more initiatives to provide support after the disaster like relief distribution, the rehabilitation of the victims, the creation of more infrastructure for the shelter etc, but there is not enough funding to improve the pre-disaster phase. There should be more and more funding to train the individuals at the field level, there should be modernised pieces of equipment for use of the scientist as well as the officials like him and the recruitment of staff should be revisited. “We need more and more people every day as every year we are getting hit by at least 2 major cyclones and flood incidents. *“We are the base level of the operation of the preparedness, warning, and post-disaster help. If the government does not implement a plan to look after us, there will be no people left in the future to work in these roles”*”, he stated.

He thinks the issue stems from the current governance and management setup. The public administrative approach to delivering services has created an environment in which officials' and volunteers' motivation is greatly impacted. Multiple bodies are working under the ministry of disaster and relief and sometimes it creates a confusing atmosphere in terms of taking a decision and problems arise for the field staff in following orders. The DDM has taken some approaches to more training and development of a new restoration project, it still needs a lot of time to put into action rather than just be on paper.

5.7 Summary of the chapter:

The above description of data provides important aspects of the three cases that have been chosen to address the research questions. The interviews provide a detailed understanding of the projects, what the respondents think of them in terms of success and failure and what they have to say about the existing management practices. The reason for these detailed interviews was to understand the contexts in-depth and encourage the researcher to have a glimpse of different perspectives and observe the tone and involvement of the respondents which will aid in a thorough analysis and come up with valid and robust recommendations. The themes generated from the interviews will be analysed and discussed in line with the conceptual

framework and literature review in the next chapter followed by some recommendations to improve the situation.

Chapter 6: Analysis and Discussion

6.1 Introduction:

As mentioned by Braun and Clarke (2013), the researcher's job is to examine data intelligently; crafting a certain narrative about the facts, a tale that answers the research questions. The interview dialogues were transcribed in chapter 5 to provide a summary of the discussion that took place. The researcher aims to find themes in the data that allow for a deeper understanding of the participants' experiences. To achieve this goal, this chapter will provide a thorough analysis of the emerging key themes that are relevant to finding the answers to the research questions. The chapter will begin with a general observation made by the researcher throughout the interviews, followed by comparing cases under key themes, and then providing a detailed discussion of the understanding of those themes in terms of the research context.

6.2 The researcher's observation- some key points:

In a realistic situation, observation is the intentional perceiving and comprehensive evaluation of participants' actions and in this research, the interview recordings, the tone of voice and the response to each topic when the questions were asked. Each interview participant had a prior knowledge of the objectives of the research and themes around which the interview would be centred, and their responses to questions varied.

Some liked talking about in detail how their involvement impacted the project, some were not interested when they were asked about the failed aspects. Mostly a hesitant tone was noticed when their relationship with upper management was discussed. It was hard to get them talking about their superiors and their leadership style, and whether the organisational culture-whether it is a nurturing place for creative ideas or not.

As part of the case study research, the researcher wanted to gain a more in-depth understanding of the participant experience to improve or grow the existing practice. To understand the participant and the phenomena more the researcher has taken note of some intuitive observations –

- All the upper-level and middle-level management officials who were interviewed are highly educated and obtained several professional qualifications too which gives them a good understanding of the digital innovation process and be more open-minded about the changes.

- Although there was only one female upper-management participant in the study, all three cases had female respondents in the IT team
- Most respondents were aged between 48-58 and male; only a handful of participants were aged below 40.
- The educational and socio-economic background played a part in understanding the research context better. Respondents with a strong background also spoke more confidently and were more engaging in the conversation
- Almost all the upper management officials expressed their concern and how they could have made things a bit better from their perspective if they have been given the opportunity, which has been proven very beneficial to provide recommendations of a possible leadership approach to facilitate innovation.
- It was prominent from the discussion that the budget crisis of the public sector is almost entirely due to inappropriate funding allocation to the departments. Much of those also derived from the complex and rather insufficient policymaking.

6.3 Thematic Analysis- Generating Themes:

Some information kept being repeated by the interviewees and was related to the research objectives and based on those recurrent patterns of the data, general themes have been developed. Patterns were manually detected after familiarising the dataset by summarising the interview audio recordings. In this situation, the researcher is looking for information on certain themes, thus a deductive approach was used, and only the data relevant to the research objectives were summarised and will be analysed hereunder. The researcher identified certain essential themes which were mentioned with utmost importance, after carefully considering all of the pertinent data provided by the participants. The topics concern the internal and external influences on the selected cases, as well as the leadership impact. The three cases will be used to analyse and compare each theme.

Generated Themes	Patterns of recurrent Data
Government Policies	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Outdated ICT policies to include digital identification documents, digital signatures • policy update for payment gateway • Inflexible recruitment and staff retention policy • Lack of policy to generate funding for disaster management, outdated policy to

	include onshore citizens in the early warning system
Distance between management and employee	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Taking all the crucial decisions without engaging all levels of staff • Notifying staff about the change and asking them to follow orders • No proper communication between different levels of the organisation • Junior-level staff not feeling comfortable approaching the management with any issue • Junior-level staff being hesitant to provide opinions
Resource Constraints	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lack of skilled staff • Lack of IT professionals • Lack of training facilities • No modernised equipment • Slow broadband connection • Limited budget for employee welfare • Limited to no budget for maintenance of the innovation projects • Poor infrastructure
Staff reaction to the innovation/change	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Little to no engagement • Resisting the implementation by non-cooperation • Discouraging other staff who feels motivated • Lack of interest in the process overall
Response of the service users	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Good response due to good advertising • No knowledge about the service in place-afraid of data security and mistrust in the system • Lack of interest in using the system, mistrust due to inaccuracy in data, dependence on the existing system, and no proper training in place to educate them
Lack of creative environment	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • No discussion between management and employee to encourage creative personal growth • Financial and bureaucratic limitations to introducing innovative work culture

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • No motivation to think outside the box • Fear of being criticised, not being heard, or acknowledged
Leadership Approaches	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Mixed/confusing leadership approaches • Not creating a creative environment • A highly autocratic approach to tackling staff resistance • No scope for reward or performance-based management • No measures were taken to adapt staff to new changes

Figure 6.1 Themes generated from patterns of data (*Source: Author*)

6.4 Analysis of the generated themes:

Before conducting the interviews, the researcher designed some themes (chapter 4, figure 4.1) to plan the semi-structured open-ended questions. The themes were generated based on the conceptual framework and research objectives. These themes helped in finding relevant answers and keeping the interviewee on track with the discussion. However, the themes that will be analysed in this chapter are based on the recurring facts found in the interview transcripts. The interviews were analysed carefully keeping in mind the experience of each participant on the chosen projects.

6.4.1 Complicated Government Policies:

This theme came up in every high-level official's discussion for each case. Every project encountered difficulties at various stages of the innovation projects under examination. It wasn't a political interruption that affected the projects; rather, it was the government's policies that impacted them. Whether it is simple recruitment and employee retention policy or creating a digital presence, public sector organisations must strictly follow the laws and regulations set forth by the government in all areas of operations. Higher authorities are more likely to address it because they are responsible for upholding policies rather than their subordinates.

In the case of the automation project of DSCC (case 1), the executives raised concerns about the recruitment, inter-department staff transfer and bonus scheme policies in the government sector. It was pointed out that, unlike the private sector, public-sector organisations are unable to hire employees based on their current needs. Due to unforeseen circumstances, DSCC has been unable to recruit for a long period. The government rules also do not allow public sector

organisations to fire or replace staff, rather they go on suspension if there is any major fault on their part. Furthermore, there is no reward system in place to achieve targets for the lower-mid level to field level staff. These complications in the policy did not allow DSCC to replace their staff or transfer them to a different department when they showed reluctance to adopt the automation process. This resulted in major delays in the design and implementation process. The lack of skilled staff could not be filled with recruits and so, external teams were brought in, causing budget problems. Moreover, the lack of a reward system in place did not encourage the staff to actively participate in the project or to adapt to the changing environment easily. They also ran into difficulties during the system requirements phase since the government had yet to revise its policy on establishing an online payment gateway, which is essential for the automation of the accounts department.

In the second scenario, the government's out-of-date ICT policies interrupted the online gd filing procedure in its early days. The participants agreed that due to not having a policy in place for incorporating digital signatures, the GD process for non-serious offences could not be completed online. The user had to visit the police station to manually sign the documents and complete the process after submitting the GD online. This did not make the system's integration into citizens' daily lives any easier. People were hesitant to use it because they had to physically visit the station for the signature anyway. Additionally, there was no ICT policy in place for ID verification and therefore, countless complaints were submitted with fake names, mobile numbers and email addresses. With no verification in place and no way of tracking those submissions, the police officers were under a great deal of stress in the early stages of the project.

The third case (early warning through mobile broadcasting) went through several difficulties due to the lack of adequate regulations in place as well. There is no policy in place for performance analysis and therefore, meteorologists are unable to verify the existing TC forecasting system's prediction ability. As a result, the forecast's precision level cannot be included in the warning message. Besides, until very recently, DDM did not have any policy in place to include residents of the coastal areas in the early messaging system and it added to a lot more casualties due to not having enough preventive measures in place. The lack of policies in place to generate more funding and training facilities for the pre-disaster phase came up frequently in every conversation. The government and ministry are allocating more resources to support in the post-disaster phase, even though the harm would be far less if preventative measures were stronger.

6.4.2 Hierarchy Issues:

The gap between high management and subordinates can be seen in all three scenarios. Whether it's making quick decisions in critical situations, participating in a strategy plan, or offering creative ideas, the organisations in question all adopt a similar approach. Although the majority of participants agree that upper-level supervisors are warm and approachable, however in reality they tend to maintain a distance from them.

In case 1, the organization's management and decision-making processes are highly centralised. General and mid-level management admitted that all key strategic moves, including project start and planning, were decided by upper-level management in collaboration with the ministry, and that they were excluded from the decision-making process. It was substantiated by senior executives' comments that though they want everyone to participate, they make the majority of the critical choices. The external IT teams also indicated that senior management was closely involved in crucial decisions. Furthermore, it was mentioned that the staff were ordered to comply with the changes and a lack of active engagement of all the parties in the decision-making process can be observed.

The police department, in scenario 2, is another highly centralised organisation. The junior and mid-level staff agreed that the mid-senior level and upper-level officers have the most power in determining the course of any case and that the project under discussion was solely originated, planned, and handled by the highest level of officials. Although upper-level police officers encourage effective communication and input from workers, it is nonetheless ineffective since there is a fear-mongering culture among subordinate police officers who are reluctant to bring up their opinions.

In case 3, on the other hand, top management attempted to decentralise decision-making by introducing various national bodies at each level. However, while this procedure appears to be highly promising, it has caused a great deal of uncertainty in times of crisis. Field personnel and volunteers lacked sufficient understanding about who to consult. Furthermore, even if decisions are made, the absence of leadership of commanding officials at the field level makes it difficult to decide whether to follow the central decision or take independent action to establish control of a situation.

6.4.3 Scarcity of resources:

The lack of suitable resources was noted by almost all of the participants as one of the most crucial facts. To accomplish the government's vision of a digitally transformed country and the a2i initiative, the country will need to dedicate significant resources to its public entities. The dearth of resources is not limited to finance; there is a shortage of competent labour, as well as infrastructure and digital equipment. Due to a lack of resources in all three cases under investigation, the projects were significantly delayed and disrupted. Sometimes the resources available were insufficient, and other times they were of poor quality.

In Case 1, the city corporation was granted a budget to complete the automation process. However, the departments lacked adequate equipment. There was no hardware to be found. DSCC made progress and allocated computers to each desk with their funds. They also recruited an IT team to maintain the system, but they did it at their own expense because the local government's funding was only given for system design and implementation, not for maintenance. There were also no skilled internal employees who could design the specifications, so external teams were brought in by issuing tenders for the project, and they, too, had to work under budget limits. As a result of the disturbance, the project had to be extended.

Case 2 encountered similar issues with their project. Not only did the police stations lack computers, but they also lacked effective internet access in the majority of their locations. Some of the buildings were extremely old, making it difficult for the IT teams to install machinery and maintain its quality. The IT staff evidently noted that their planned system had inadequate security, resulting in numerous hacking incidents and data theft. To avoid this, they relocated the base to the DMP's LAN, but they still lacked a suitable firewall. The lack of a decent working environment and IT training facilities, according to the junior officials, had a significant impact on their job. The police department's higher management expressed dissatisfaction with the lack of resources allotted to digitalize the department and provide full training to each officer. In Dhaka, there is just one cop to care for every 600 residents. Because they are already short-staffed and receive less financing for digital initiatives, it is extremely difficult for them to hire more IT professionals, give IT resources to all stations and personnel, and provide adequate training to all employees at the same time.

In case 3, there were various resource limits. In terms of skilled staff, equipment, and training facilities, the majority of the participants admit to having very few resources. The BMD

scientists first stated that there is a lack of trained personnel in the department who can properly decode generated data and go through the analysis, resulting in incorrect early warning messages. They do not have access to modern training facilities. Secondly, to create forecasts, the department uses a cluster computer that is insufficient for performing complicated numerical models. Most notably, there is more funding dedicated to giving aid post-disaster, such as relief distribution, victim rehabilitation, and expanding shelter infrastructure, but there is insufficient investment to improve the pre-disaster phase or the early warning system. Field employees are undertrained and underpaid, and there is little financing for their training or well-being. Furthermore, participants stated that individuals are still not receiving messages since there is little to no mobile connectivity in the areas during disaster times and also not all the existing handsets support Bengali font in messaging, making it difficult for the rural coastal people to understand the warning. These issues negate the major objective of the mobile-based early warning system.

6.4.4 Reaction to change:

Change is unavoidable in any organisational growth; however, it doesn't make it any simpler to deal with. Organizational change can cause stress and worry in many individuals, affecting their job performance. Businesses must anticipate the kind of reactions their employees will have to reassure and assist them in making large-scale changes to remain competitive. In all the cases in this research, a mild or major form of staff reaction has been noticed as part of the conversation and was mentioned as a key barrier or factor that positively or negatively impacted the success of the projects.

In case 1, a major reaction can be observed as a key barrier to the successful design and implementation of the project from the participants' perspective. The junior to mid-level staff showed a lot of resistance when the project was declared. They did not cooperate in submitting their job duties to the IT team to include them in the system. They also tried their best to not attend the training that was arranged to make them comfortable using the digital system. It was mentioned by the senior manager that their job description never demanded a technological improvement and some of these staff are on the verge of retirement. Therefore, they felt there is no need for them to undertake new tasks or learn a new skill. Additionally, according to the junior-level staff, they actively discouraged other members of staff to show enthusiasm and actively participating in the program. The executives and mid-level managers mentioned this staff resistance as one of the key problems that delayed the project. As per them, age,

socioeconomic background, lack of job understanding, and education level played a major part in their reaction.

In case 2, the police department did not see much resistance from the staff but there was a silent lack of enthusiasm that was observed during the interviews. According to the participants, the junior and mid-level staff did not show much interest in the change because most of them did not have any clear idea about digital innovation in the first place. A very minority of police officials did feel threatened that they will not be able to make extra money while making promises of investigating the issue quicker for the citizens, but the numbers are very few. Again, it was mentioned that most junior-level police officials did not feel particularly excited as they did not feel how it will aid in their progression.

Case 3 also did not see much resistance and there was a lack of enthusiasm again among the field-level staff part. They believe there are no appropriate training opportunities or workshops in place to educate the staff in actively using the full facility of the mobile-based early warning system. Since they do not fully understand the system, they fail to educate the citizens as well. Since there is a lack of recognition of the work they do, they did not very enthusiastic about the new approach to improving the pre-disaster phase. They just did not feel the need to be included.

6.4.5 Consumer Reception:

Although the research did not include service consumers in the interviews since it was more important to learn the perspectives of those who worked on the project or were associated with it, the project's reception by its users came up frequently in the discussions.

Case 1 saw good participant response in terms of using the service. All of the participants were happy with how well received by the users. The main success factor behind this according to the executives and the IT specialists was the inclusion of multiple methods of payment for the requested service. The people who could use the internet smoothly and have the options to pay via online banking found it very useful to avoid delays, harassment, and long procedure. It did not upset the users who do not have the luxury of online banking or internet facilities at home either as DSCC has integrated different payment partners using their booths, field agents and mobile money transfer services into their system to provide a wide variety to reach all walks of people. They also used talk shows, annual tax fairs, newspapers, and social media to advertise the new automated system.

Case 2 however did not see an anticipated response from the users. First, the process is still not advertised enough to reach all users in Dhaka city. The lack of utilising social media and electronic media in the beginning phase drew the line for them. One officer in the interview mentioned they were only 2 or 3 requests in a whole day. Again, the previous security issues and the hacking incidents created an environment of mistrust among the users. They still do not want their data to be exposed. However, the upper management mentioned in the conversation that DMP is actively engaging with people using their Facebook, Twitter and YouTube accounts and educating them about the online GD process as well as the new upcoming digital services.

In case 3, the user perception of the early warning system came up as one of the main impediments to the success of the project. According to all the participants from this case, the coastal population who is the main user of the system do not bear enough knowledge to utilise the system fully. Educational and social background as well as the age and gender of the population play a vital role in determining whether they are interested in learning new preventative measures or not. The lack of accurate forecast in the previous years has resulted in distrust among the users. Again, the offshore fishermen are still not under the coverage of any mobile network to be able to use the service. All these issues persist to date since the initiation of the project not making it a useful one to provide warning messages in time of Cyclone.

6.4.6 Lack of creative atmosphere:

The production of unique and valuable ideas is typically regarded as creativity, whereas the effective execution of those ideas is regarded as innovation. An organisation needs to create an environment that cultivates and nurtures creative ideas in order to gain sustainability. In the case of public sectors, the notion of creativity is different. Unlike private sectors, the atmosphere is mostly very formal and rigid, and people only do the job that is asked of them to get by. In three projects that are under investigation in this study, a lack of creativity has been observed by the researcher. Some participants have commented directly, and others just provided a hint of the reality.

In case 1, although the executives agreed to have an open mind about new ideas and always keep their doors open for constructive opinions, the staff did not feel they can do that. The middle and higher-level managers welcomed the new way of doing things wholeheartedly, but the junior and field-level staff were reluctant to take on the innovative way of completing their

tasks. It somehow felt while listening to them that not all of them dare to engage in creativity because they felt it is not necessary, they are not important, they will not be taken seriously, and it will be too risky to change the traditional way of doing things. When asking about encouraging creativity, there was no mention of feedback or a creative discussion system in place between the managers and subordinates. It was stated by the manager that they have to follow government policies in every activity and sometimes the restrictions do not allow them to be more creative.

Case 2 also saw a lack of enthusiasm about being creative in the workplace. The upper management commented about recently introducing an opinion/suggestion box in every police station, to encourage staff to be more participative in providing creative suggestions to improve the service delivery. However, he also mentioned this process is very new and the response rate is very low to date. It was stated by one of the mid-level officers that the junior staff do not have the general understanding of being innovative and therefore, he never gets any suggestion of doing things differently from them. One of the respondents also mentioned that some higher officials do not like getting opinions from their subordinates and thus do not nourish creativity.

In terms of case 3, there was not enough mention of being creative in the workplace either. The BMD scientists highlight a lack of qualified personnel in their department who could think outside the box and come up with a better technique to analyse the data. The field workers stated that they were unable to provide input or make recommendations since they were not allowed to do so. Due to infrastructure, training, and financing limits, CPP officials stated that they do not have a team or working environment that can inspire staff to come up with innovative ideas. Upper-level management indicated that the decision-making mechanism has already been decentralised to encourage more participation from different levels of the workforce. They did admit, however, that there is a dedicated innovation unit that only comes up with ideas, and even those must go through numerous stages of government reform and fulfil several policies before being accepted.

6.4.7 Leadership Approaches:

Understanding the significance of leadership approaches or management techniques on various aspects of the project and overall organisation was one of the key objectives of the current research. This topic was sometimes addressed by the participants directly, on a few occasions

they did not want to voice their opinions and mostly it was observed from the answers given by the participants as well as their take on different challenges.

In case 1, it can be observed from the conversations with the middle-level managers and junior/field-level staff that although they think the leaders are warm and friendly persons, their leadership approach is not necessarily the best. From the researcher's perspective, it can be stated that they were not entirely happy about the fact that they were not included in the decision-making process most of the time in the project; but they have made their peace with the notion as it is normal for them. The traditional ways of decision-making are still prevalent in most public sector organisations and DSCC is no different. The upper-level management staff did not directly mention that they do not involve the middle-level managers but stated all the decisions were taken beforehand with the ministry and mayor and the staff were just notified about the automation project. In terms of innovation and creating a nurturing workplace to motivate employees in taking up new challenging ideas, middle management agreed that they were asked to give their opinions about the project under investigation and they felt valued in that case. The field-level staff mentioned that he has not had a chance to participate in a creative discussion with the upper level, but he believes he will be heard and that shows a positive side of the upper-level management. Then again, they all agreed that the approach taken by them to tackle the resistance of some was not noteworthy and surely, they could have managed it more different to make them comfortable with the whole change process. The overall leadership style of the management felt very warm but not motivating enough for the staff to go beyond their duties, making contributions in innovative actions or adapting to the change.

Case 2 saw something similar and it was noted on a few occasions where the middle level and junior level staffs are not quite happy with their supervising officials. They mentioned always having a distanced relationship with the authorities and were never included in any decision-making step while the project was under development. They felt somewhat reluctant and, also a bit afraid to voice their opinions but did not say the police chief or the supervising officers were not fitted for the job or lacked vision. It's their way of running things that were criticised. The IT team mentioned not being heard when they were informed about the technical glitches and the department still went ahead and released it to the public. The junior-level staff are not motivated at all due to having any reward scheme and training in place, and the upper management agreed with the resource constraints however, it was observed they did not do anything as a leader to uplift the staff and make them more participative. The leadership style

somehow felt very centralized and autocratic as the upper management had the final say, they did not take the feedback before launching the project and some of them did in fact discourage staff to take a more creative approach in the workplace.

Case 3 saw a different approach in leadership as the ministry tried to break through the centralised decision-making process by introducing more national-level bodies for different purposes and different levels of work. This initiative was very promising as mentioned by one of the key members of the DMD as it gave the staff a chance to be more participative in the decision-making process and be more creative. However, considering what different levels of staff had to say, this decentralized approach did not seem well fitted. With different bodies in authority, decisions were confusing, and the ground-level committee managers lacked the leadership quality to come forward and have their say and take firm decisions.

6.5 Findings from the analysis:

There have been several significant discoveries as a result of the ongoing discussion about discovering recurrent patterns in data and categorising the data into themes. In the preceding part, the data from the three cases were analysed and compared to see where there were similarities and where there may have been differences. To determine whether the research has achieved its goal of understanding various obstacles to public sector innovation and how leadership has affected them, it is essential to comprehend the findings produced. The success of the findings in answering the research questions will next be critically examined, as well as how they complement the conceptual framework that was presented to direct the researcher's path.

- At various points in their development, all three projects ran into difficulties. The rigidity of government policies, which had an impact on the project both internally and externally, was one of the key contributing factors. Given that bureaucrats control the framework and policies of every single area of public service, it appeared to be an external barrier. It continuously complicated the decision-making process, which had an internal impact on the project's progress. The management has been prevented from taking the essential actions to resolve challenging situations by the lack of policies for hiring and retaining employees as well as the absence of performance measurement and reward systems. Project design and delivery to citizens were significantly delayed as a result of a lack of digital policy and slow implementation of such policies.

- A substantial form of staff reaction has been noted in all the cases in this research and has been mentioned as a major hurdle that negatively influenced the success of the projects. Diverse projects and phases produced different reactions, and these reactions took many different forms. Some employees lacked enthusiasm for the new procedure being developed, while others actively opposed it while it was being put into place. Since they didn't feel included in the process and were primarily not informed about the broad changes it would bring to their workplace and service delivery, the junior and field-level workers were more affected by the initiative. Their integration into the project was not seamless; and because they were an essential component of projects that were delivered to the general public and typically worked on the front lines with the public, dealing with the staff reaction and bringing them together cost valuable time and resources, which ultimately led to the delayed outcome.
- In its analysis, current research uncovered compelling evidence of how users reacted to new services and technology and how their socioeconomic and educational status affected their behaviour which acted as a deciding factor in the success or failure of the delivered final product. While urban areas saw a more open-minded approach to the integration of the new services, the rural and coastal area populations did not show enthusiasm. This is a reflection of their socio-economic background, their educational level to understand the importance of the newly introduced or changed services and the availability of resources such as smartphones, internet connectivity and mobile network. However, it has been observed that the integration of the new system into citizen's life and service user reception could have been better using some creative marketing initiatives taken by the management which was advised by the middle management but ignored by higher authority.
- Nearly all of the participants cited the absence of appropriate resources as one of the most important facts. There is a lack of resources across the board, including finance, skilled labour, digital equipment, and infrastructure. In all three of the cases under review, the projects suffered from serious delays and disruptions because of a lack of resources. Sometimes the resources on hand weren't enough, and other times they weren't very good. The resource allocation capacity in a country like Bangladesh is impacted by several factors like socioeconomic, political, geographic and environmental to name a few. Even though these occurrences are expected, there are some instances where severe infrastructure damage and human suffering have a

significant impact on government decision-making and cause an economic downturn because they may necessitate a lot of attention and resources for recovery and rehabilitation. This ultimately affects the budget allocation to promote innovative projects within government, train staff and arrange performance-based rewards.

- The lack of a creative environment, which had a significant impact on the three government cases in question, was influenced by the rigidity of the policies and strong division between high management and lower-level employees. Organisations in question all take a similar stance, whether it be making prompt judgments in urgent situations, taking part in a strategy plan, or contributing original ideas. Although the vast majority of participants concur that upper-level supervisors are friendly and approachable, in practice, they often keep their distance. There was no mention of feedback or a framework for innovative discussions between managers and employees when it came to fostering innovation. The management claimed that they had to adhere to government regulations in every activity and that occasionally these limitations prevented them from being more creative. People just perform the tasks required of them to survive in the atmosphere, which is generally highly formal and rigid. Due to a lack of policies and management's reluctance to actively promote creative ideas, staff members in three of the study's projects have been reluctant to use their creativity because they believe it is not necessary, and will not be taken seriously due to the high discrimination between authority and subordinates, and will be too risky to alter the way things have always been done.
- The current study was able to recognize the specific leadership styles adopted by the three projects and how it mirrors the general leadership environment in Bangladeshi government sector organisations. It also found that all the obstacles that were uncovered through the data collection and analysis of recurrent themes were clearly impacted by leadership styles, and some of the issues might have been solved more effectively with a different or less rigorous management style. There is a lack of a creative environment and subordinate participation due to the highly centralised power structure and the high power distance. This uninspiring culture is the product of ill-conceived policies that do not encourage an innovative leadership style. It does not account for the possibility that various innovation phases will face various challenges. In the context of Bangladesh, a leadership framework should be instated that will take this possibility into account, implement the necessary measures, and uphold the authority of public sector managers.

6.6 Discussion:

6.6.1 Addressing the research questions:

It's critical to discuss the themes and whether they lead to the responses to address the research questions. The focus of the research was to learn more about the present state of the projects and whether there were any challenges encountered through the case study research. All the projects are now up and running, and steps are being undertaken to rectify any shortcomings. As indicated in the conceptual framework in chapter three, the three government programmes faced numerous internal and external problems. In this section, the research questions will be addressed one by one, and the answers will be analysed based on the investigations. The research questions set to reach the objectives of the studies were:

- What is the current state of innovative approaches/projects taken by government organizations?
- What were the successful or failed features during the projects?
- Which are the internal and external factors that impact innovation?
- How did the existing leadership approaches impact the innovation process?
- What will be the recommended leadership approach to overcome the challenges?

6.6.1.1 Current state of the innovation projects:

As part of the present government's vision of Digital Bangladesh, Bangladesh is undergoing a digital service revolution. The a2i project, as indicated several times in earlier chapters, serves as the hub for all other government projects aimed at making government services more accessible and user-friendly for individuals from all walks of life. The three government projects that were examined for this study are now all fully functioning and are part of this hub. In the last 5-8 years, all three have been completely operational, however, some aspects of the projects are still being monitored to improve them in the future. According to the interviews, the projects went through an almost identical procedure from start to finish. The suggestions were made at the bureaucratic level to improve the service delivery system and make it more digital. They went through numerous phases and involved a wide variety of departments to deliver the projects after the initial idea formulation and permission from the ministries involved. It is clear, that public sector organisations collaborated with private sector businesses and other ministries to attain project objectives. For instance, in case 1, active involvement of the external IT team was discovered; in case 2, the department IT team conducted the initial

steps before bringing in the external team; and in case 3, the entire process was established by the internal innovation team with the help of mobile network providers. The collected data suggest that the entire process went through a designated ministry first, who considered the policies and how they could be implemented, and then passed on to the cabinet for the decision-making process to formulate the project and budget allocation, as discussed in the conceptual framework chapter. Once the ideas had been authorised by the ministries, they were transmitted to the appropriate government organizations—city corporations, police, and local bodies.

6.6.1.2 Successful and failed features of the projects:

Although all the projects are currently operational, there are certain aspects of the projects which contributed to the outcome and user reception/involvement. The contributing factors included marketing/advertising of the project to the public, the user-friendliness of the system and employee engagement throughout the project. An important success factor in case 1 mentioned by the respondents was the improvement of transparency in responsibilities due to the automation process being implemented. Additionally, there was marketing, which helped citizens become aware of the new system and comfortable with using it. The city corporation advertised the automation project through many channels and encouraged citizens to use it. However, due to staff not being completely engaged in the innovation effort, the case encountered numerous issues. Throughout the project, they generated challenging situations and caused the project's completion to be delayed. In case 2, the advertising was less effective, and many consumers were unaware when it initially began, according to the respondents. Citizens found it difficult to use due to certain initial technical difficulties and security breaches and had to execute some sections manually, nevertheless. It resulted in a lack of enthusiasm for the digital GD service. The employees were also ambivalent about their participation in the project and did not actively participate in advising citizens who came to the police stations to submit GD to instead utilise the online system. Example 3, like case 1, used various channels to promote its mobile-based communication system for disaster alerts, but the target demographic was not digitally literate enough to appreciate the new service's potential. People in disaster-prone areas could have been trained to fully utilise the system before it was implemented. Because the mobile network is still not robust, there were technical aspects of this project that did not help the project's goal of reaching a wider audience during cyclones. Furthermore, most handsets used by individuals in disaster-prone areas were not intended to receive Bengali text messages back then. Furthermore, the scientists failed to analyse a huge

number of datasets and generate false alarms in the early phases, leading to public dissatisfaction.

6.6.1.3 The external and internal factors impacting innovation:

External Factor:

One of the key external challenges discovered in the data collection was the rigidity of the bureaucratic policies in place. Demand-side policies, such as sensible laws, standards, pricing, capacity building, taxes, and public procurement, are determined by the government and can have an impact on innovation. Therefore, the inflexibility of the government policies created a lot of problems in the planning, design, development, and implementation phase. This factor directly impacted the organisational culture of innovation and the decision-making approach taken by the management. Various works of literature already acknowledged bureaucratic complicacy as one of the main key impediments to public sector innovation. Bureaucracy is a universal problem that affects all large structures, whether public or private. When an issue arises, the bureaucracy creates a new policy to deal with it. The old processes are, however, never removed. Overcoming bureaucratic complexities and resistance is crucial in terms of innovation policy and encouraging bureaucrats who display excellent judgement in promoting innovations would be beneficial.

Analysing the cases of current research, the organisations and their management come off as inflexible, whereas productivity and creativity demand some flexibility. The reason behind this is first, managers of government agencies in any country are required to follow strict protocols to protect citizens' rights to equality (in terms of the location of infrastructure, recruitment, and the universality of services). This issue was raised by the senior management that even if they wanted to recruit more experienced staff or allocate more budget to improve the innovative culture at the workplace, they could not do it because of the strict policies. Second, they had fewer opportunities for substituting resources, particularly labour and capital as stated in Lovell, (2002) and Dunleavy et al (2006). It was observed in several statements where the staff resistance created a lot of pressure on the project and those staff could not be transferred or replaced with more skilled and enthusiastic staff. Furthermore, unlike their private-sector counterparts, the managers had little control over the range of services delivered, as Fox (1999) pointed out. They only have a limited amount of control over the type of service they offer. They cannot decide to stop delivering a service or provide an alternative one on their own.

Another external catalyst that played a vital role as mentioned in the framework as well as generated from the interview is the socio-economic background of the service users. The ability of a user to access and utilise innovation is a determining factor in its adoption. Certain cultural, socioeconomic, personal, political, and geographic factors influence this capacity. It also considers the information's applicability, the information channel's reliability, and the qualities of the information provider. Various studies (*Panne, Beers & Kleinkecht, 2003; OSLO Manual, 2018; Von Hippel, 1976; Bhuiyan, 2011; Sarker et al, 2017, Scwartz et al, 2018*) have found that the success or failure of innovation largely depends on the users' response and their social and educational background act as key factors in their perception or acceptance of the new product/service or system.

Current research in its investigation found strong evidence of user reception of the new services/technologies and how their socio-economic and educational background impacted the behaviours. In case one, the user of the automated tax and account services are mostly city dwellers who have easy access to technology, have the educational understanding of using basic tech services and are open-minded to take on the new approaches to utilise the full benefits of a user-friendly service. Similarly, in case 2, the service was initially designed for the citizens of the Dhaka Metropolitan area. Being the capital, most people again, had access to or understanding of how to use technology in their daily lives. Almost all households nowadays acquire a smartphone and the internet being relatively cheaper, it may be a success in the future. Case 3, unfortunately, is yet to receive the desired outcome. Since most service users live in coastal areas, their educational and economic background is not great, the internet service is not so great either and the older population still tend to rely on the traditional approaches of disaster preparedness and post disasters relief movement. The gender gap also plays a key role in the acceptance and willingness to be involved in training activities to be benefited fully from the new system.

Environmental disasters and disease outbreaks play a major role in policymaking and government fund allocation in disaster-prone countries like Bangladesh. Every year, thousands of people die in floods, cyclones and different disease outbreaks like dengue, malaria and other seasonal illnesses. Although these incidents are anticipated, there are some cases where the heavy damage to infrastructure, casualties and suffering of people impact the decision-making of the government immensely. In disaster-prone areas, every year the disaster strikes, and the people lose their homes, cattle, their jobs. In times of disease outbreaks the hospitals cannot be equipped with the patient demands, sometimes people stay at home due to the sickness resulting

in a long absence from work. These result in a downturn in the economy. In all three cases of this research, the respondents mentioned a lack of sufficient funding for the innovation projects and that they were allocated “to the more pressing” matters. Needless to say, although they did not mention it exactly, reviews of literature, as well as the current covid situation, indicate that in a developing country like Bangladesh; these disasters or disease outbreaks can require a lot of attention and resources for recovery and rehabilitation and the Government, therefore, must adjust the funding and resources to retrieve the economic and social situation.

Internal Factors:

High power distance, lack of cooperation, and willingness to take risks, according to Alom (2019) and Jamil (2002) in Bangladeshi public services, can influence employee motivation to think creatively or actively participate in decision-making. It also affects the culture of approaching a manager with new ideas and gaining positive feedback. To understand the leader-employee relationship and organizational culture of the Bangladeshi public sector, the situation can be discussed in light of Hofstede’s cultural dimensions. Although he noted that national culture and organisational culture are extremely different, an organisation is governed by an individual, and individuals occasionally follow their traditional values and views, which are related to national culture, whether subconsciously or consciously. When the national score is taken into account, Bangladesh has a high score on the power distance dimension (80), indicating that people accept a hierarchical order in which everyone has a position, and no further rationale is required. The ideal leader is a benign authoritarian, and hierarchy in an organisation is seen as reflecting inherent inequalities. The high-power distance in cases 1 and 2 could be easily observed from the responses of senior authorities and middle to lower-level officials involved in the process. Case 3 attempted to break free from this by introducing a more participatory decision-making process, but a lack of a comprehensive chain of monitoring somehow made it even more problematic.

In terms of Masculinity, Bangladesh scores 55 on this dimension and may be classified as a Masculine society. Managers are expected to be decisive and assertive, the emphasis is on equity, competitiveness, and performance, and conflicts are rarely addressed tactfully. The senior management in all three cases exhibited these traits. When faced with resistance rather than addressing the core problems, a rather strict approach was taken to make the staff involved. But then again, the management mentioned that they could not change certain practices as it may undermine their authority as the leader as well as strict and old-fashioned policies. As suggested by Alom (2019) some cases, strict adherence to bureaucratic rules may not yield the

desired results and rightly so, it can be observed in cases 1 and 3 when they could not hire trained staff due to complex bureaucratic policies or could not reward staff based on their involvement in the project. This issue contributed to the organization's lack of trained professionals who can understand, design, and maintain the system as needed. Due to the excessively convoluted recruitment and retirement regulations, the departments also experienced a shortage of innovative staff.

Bangladesh has a high score of 60 on uncertainty avoidance, indicating that it has rigorous rules of thought and behaviour and is intolerant of unconventional behaviour and ideas. The desire to avoid uncertainty hurt the project's ability to fulfil its goals. It prevented officials from taking innovative steps. In case 1, there was rigidity among some staff who were not too keen to take on new and challenging tasks or learn new technology, in case 2 the staffs were reluctant to foresee the benefits of the projects. It is again connected with Bangladesh having a very low Indulgence score of 20. This makes it more of a restrained country as societies with a low score in this dimension tend towards cynicism and pessimism. In case 3, the service's users were hesitant to utilise it since it was a new concept to learn, and it contradicted their preconceived notions and behaviours regarding disaster alert and post-disaster management.

Bangladesh, with a score of 20 in the dimension of Individualism, is considered a collectivistic society. Loyalty in a collectivist culture is paramount and overrides most other societal rules and regulations. Society fosters strong relationships where everyone takes responsibility for fellow members of their group. In collectivist societies offence leads to shame and loss of face, employer/employee relationships are perceived in moral terms (like a family link), hiring and promotion decisions take account of the employee's in-group, and management is the management of groups, which yet again contributes to the scarcity of the desired skills within the organisation. In case 1, one respondent mentioned he did not want to go against the majority of the people who were showing reluctance to the innovative approach taken by management to show his loyalty.

In Bangladesh, one of the numerous constraints limiting innovation and economic progress is a lack of infrastructure and physical resources in the government-run bodies which was highlighted in all three cases that were investigated in this study. While mobile phone technology has revolutionised telecommunications, internet access is still limited to the farthest areas. This immensely impacted the success and popularity among users of the mobile-based warning message services. Inadequate and expensive transportation, communication, water,

and energy infrastructure all have a negative impact on the development and implementation of innovation projects. In cases 1 and 2, it can be noticed that the scarcity of resources created a negative atmosphere among the staff to adapt to the changes and it catered to their lack of enthusiasm towards creativity. The government offices still lack updated computer facilities, the buildings are poorly built, and the working hostels for the government officials are not modernised- all these factors impacted employee motivation and affected their creativity throughout different phases of the innovation projects. It has been identified that it's not only the physical resources but also a scarcity of skills that is present within the government organisations. A lack of skilled and trained staff contributed to the delays in service delivery and process integration. Respondents mentioned, that there is hardly a scope of training and professional development for the lower and middle-level staff to improve their understanding of the innovation and technological process which was one of the prominent factors working as a barrier to the innovation projects considered in this research.

6.6.1.4 How leadership approaches impacted the innovation process:

As discussed in the literature, various leadership styles influence organisational innovation, either directly or indirectly, by influencing the organisational atmosphere, employee and leader behaviour, or other organisational characteristics like learning and information exchange and some leadership styles influenced organisational innovation in both direct and indirect ways. Among all the contextual aspects that influence the work environment of employees, leadership has been suggested as one of the critical elements for achieving individual and organisational success and innovation (*Engelen, Schmidt, Strenger, & Brettel, 2014; Wang, Rode, Shi, Luo, & Chen, 2013*). While Franklin and Plimmer (2019) discussed the negative characteristics of leadership that have a detrimental effect on public sector innovation, Khan, Hussain, and Al-Ghazali (2020) suggested a favourable relationship between leadership style and innovative employee behaviour. The study finds that different leadership ideologies can influence how much innovation is deployed and whether a strategy response is successful or unsuccessful based on the data that is currently available (*Sazzad, Rajan and Demircioglu, 2021*).

According to the findings of the current research, leadership not only affected subordinate behaviour but also directly influenced several internal elements that led to hard conditions in the various phases. As most public sector innovation occurs for not profitable goals but for the betterment of society, it has been noticed that in the first phase of idea generation and proposal of the project, it is rigorously restricted to government policymakers, ministries, and upper-level management officials (*Perry, Hondeghem, and Wise 2010; Schwarz, Eva and Newman,*

2018). The current research confirmed that this phase does not require any subordinate participation in the development of creative ideas, as evidenced by earlier literary works. Phases 2 and 3, which were responsible for the design of the proposed new service and its execution, witnessed a variety of difficulties, and managerial style undoubtedly had a direct or indirect impact on those difficulties.

In cases 1 and 2, more of a top-down central decision-making process can be observed. The employees did not have many contributions to the decision-making process and the idea-generation phase. The upper-level management distributed the work, and the changes in the workplace and project briefing were not shared with the middle to lower-level staff. As a result, the employees did not feel engaged enough to cooperate in the project fully and due to not having any prior idea of how the project may impact their job roles, they showed resistance to the change delaying various phases of the project. This is a reflection of the conclusions reached by Damanpour and Schneider (2006), which were further supported by the works of De Vries, Tummers, and Bekkers (2018) and Moussa et al. (2018). These authors made a strong case that top managers can significantly influence innovation, either for or against it, especially if decision-making power is concentrated in their hands. Although this way of thinking about leadership is particularly prevalent in developing nations, it has a detrimental influence on employee engagement and motivation. Both Frankin and Pilmer (2019) and Aravena (2019) noted that using the wrong leadership approach to deal with challenging situations results in not only delays in the delivery of the product but also a lack of trust and passion among the staff, which makes them feel excluded from the project. Their report addresses problematic leadership behaviours that are evident in the existing research, such as managing up rather than down and a lack of professional and personal support. Middle to the lower-level staff mentioned that they do not go forward with their new ideas as they do not think they will be taken seriously or had barely any idea such a system of innovation idea-sharing exists. At least at the mid-senior level, employee engagement and motivation are crucial for fostering innovation and integrating change processes efficiently. It can be enhanced by several factors, including introducing an effective organisational culture by establishing an open communication system, rewarding employees for their work, and practising performance measurement. Additionally, a simple creative feedback session might be beneficial (Scwarz et al, 2018). The top management said they are open to new ideas but due to the highly centralised power structure, the employees do not feel comfortable enough to speak about their ideas and always maintain a distance. Besides, even the top management officials could not take certain

actions as they did not have that autonomy like private sector managers to make changes as they always have to abide by policies set by the government. These restricted policies did not give the upper management the autonomy to make changes to create a more innovative environment even if they felt it would be better to make some changes to accommodate the necessities of the project requirements. As noted by Kettle (2000) and later supported by several studies, public sector leaders must exercise their leadership practices while policymakers are considering them to sustain the morals of democracy (Cook,1998; Vanwart,2003; Al Ghazali, 2020, Khan et al, 2020). Case 3, on the other hand, took a different approach in terms of the leadership and decision-making aspect. As the ministry of disaster management has different acting bodies to overcome challenges at various levels, the staff working in local bodies were given decision-making power to some extent, however, due to lack of proper staff training, lack of understanding of the initiative and poor performance appraisals, staff did not show the enthusiasm to take on the new responsibility, and this relaxed and distributed form of leadership consequently created chaos while taking the step forward. Again, a crucial part of the disaster management body, the meteorological department faced a rather centralised decision-making approach and a hint of favouritism in recruiting unskilled staff.

This case showed a situation where a more inclusive strategy was considered and employees were given some autonomy in making decisions, but ultimately failed to bring about the adjustments that were required to successfully deploy the service. Although Zhang and Bartol (2010) suggested that empowering employees can result in better integration of innovation in the workplace, in the context of Bangladesh as it can lead to a conflict with the managerial authority because they are the ones who make the final decisions and because there isn't yet enough training infrastructure available for workers to step up and participate in the decision-making process (Qi, Liu, Wei and Hu,2019). This is what went wrong with case number 3, even though scientists were eyewitnesses to some highly authoritarian procedures where they were unable to voice their concerns about hiring, training, or equipment. This sort of inclusive leadership demands the subordinates to have equal knowledge which they did not have. The examples and observations from them provided a clear illustration of how neither dictatorial nor inclusive leadership is effective in the Bangladeshi public sector. Due to the rigidity of the policies, transactional leadership is also not recommended (Alom, 2019; Aziz, 2020) as it demands a reward-based performance which is complicated to achieve as per the interview participants. Again, transformation leadership would not be a better-suited approach to

overcome the challenges either it may have a detrimental relationship with creativity-related processes and outcomes. Because the transformation leaders may come across as imposing their visions on subordinates it might result in a lack of creativity and engagement (*Sosik, Kahai, & Avolio, 1998; Wang & Rode, 2010*). A similar situation could be observed in cases 1 and 2 where the higher management imposed their vision onto the subordinates and they felt less connected to the end objective.

These arguments showed the negative impact leadership can have on innovation by influencing work culture, employee behaviour and handling reaction to change and how one style is not suitable recommended to tackle the challenges that were identified. As *Kesting et al (2016)* suggested, leadership to stimulate innovation in the public sector can be complicated and must need different approaches in different phases. As a result, a framework must be created to better incorporate the findings into leadership practice in the Bangladeshi public sector.

6.6.1.5 Recommended Strategy to overcome the challenges:

In an organisation, leadership does not come out of thin air. According to *Porter and McLaughlin (2006)*, it occurs in the context of businesses and is one of the most important drivers of an organization's ability to innovate and perform successfully. *Krause (2004)* examines leadership in terms of certain qualities of influence (such as allowing for freedom and autonomy, being honest in decision-making, and so on) that promote innovative behaviour in organisations. Leadership appears to be a critical determinant in a company's ability to innovate, according to other academics such as *Makri and Scandura (2010)*, and *Coccia (2015)* shows the vital importance of some countries' global leadership in fostering the invention and diffusion of major technological discoveries at the national level. In short, understanding how certain countries develop innovation and preserve a competitive advantage in the face of strong competition and environmental hazards requires a focus on leadership. (*Coccia, 2015; Tybout, 2000*). Managing and promoting innovation places a variety of demands on leaders that are difficult to address in a single leadership approach (*Alvarez, Svejenova, & Vives, 2007; Mumford & Hunter, 2005*), leading to increased levels of leader role conflict and resource demand conflict (*Eckman, 2007; Hunter, Thoroughgood, Myer, & Ligon, 2011*).

Senior executives, middle managers, front-line supervisors, and HR practitioners play crucial roles in signalling and promoting innovation in the Bangladeshi government because it is largely top-down and hierarchical. It's tough to change a culture within a huge, complicated

organisation (*OECD, 1998*), and it's even more difficult to drive an innovative culture across the entire government. If the civil service is to adopt an innovation culture, it must be fostered, supported, and reinforced at all levels of the organisation. Most of the literature on cultural transformation and change management, such as *Leading Change (1996)* by John Kotter and *Managing Transitions (1991)* by William Bridges, emphasises the need of achieving swift and early successes. Cultural shifts, on the other hand, are difficult to establish, and quick wins are rare. These efforts require a long-term mindset and focus, as well as a good change management plan, but they are often ineffective. Approximately 80% of public-sector transformation programmes fail (*Allas et. al, 2018*).

Sundbo and Fuglsang's approach is based on Giddens' (*1984*) idea of the dual structure of society, which they apply to organisations. Organizations, they claim, have a management structure as well as a loosely coupled interaction structure in which employees and managers collaborate. Different logics are used by these structures. The managerial structure follows a hierarchical logic that directs the actions of the company. The realm of creativity is a highly distributed dynamic system in which ideas originate and innovation champions promote them (*Sundbo, 1996; Muller, Zenker & Ramos, 2012*). Interactions between employees, managers and external actors represent, share, and spread these ideas.

A first step is to openly incorporate innovation into senior leaders' strategic management goals, which just a few companies have done thus far. As a result, not only can innovation be encouraged, but it can also be managed, recorded, and measured as part of a company's long-term growth strategy. Second, without launching disruptive change programmes, Executives can make better use of existing (and often underutilised) talent for innovation by fostering the growth and flourishing of dynamic innovation networks. Finally, they can make a concerted effort to foster a creative culture that is founded on employee trust. People in such a culture believe that their opinions are valued, that it is safe to express themselves, and that risk is shared with their managers. Such an environment may be more effective than monetary incentives in sustaining innovation. As a result, a strategy of dual leadership might be adopted.

Figure 6.2: Dual Leadership Role (*Source: Author*)

Bottom-up: Leaders as innovation motivators:

Even though it's been proved how integrating employees in workplace decision-making promotes commitment, collaborative leadership practices are not widely adopted in government organisations. Bottom-up or participative management approaches, in which important stakeholders in government organisations collaborate to make choices, appear to have the potential to improve labour-management relations, employee engagement, and, as a result, public service (*Steinheider. and Wuestewald, 2008*). Innovation is the result of systematic investment in research and development (*Sauermann & Cohen, 2010*). When employees critically evaluate and challenge standard procedures, services, and products, however, innovation can arise in less formal, unexpected ways (*Zhang & Bartol, 2010*). Employees who spot defects in existing systems, services, or products are often the catalysts for new ideas. Individual employees could develop innovative organisational process concepts based on their day-to-day tasks (*Lee et al, 2014*). Front-line service personnel may have a greater grasp of user demands as a result of everyday interactions, but their creative potential is frequently untapped (*Hasu, Saari, & Mattelmäki, 2011*). Employees may also have relevant network ties outside of the company, which could lead to new information and ideas (*Kesting & Ulhi, 2010*). Employees are thus crucial actors when organisations want to loosen their borders and use open innovation ideas (*Chesbrough, 2011*).

The concept of empowering leadership was suggested by Zhang and Bartol (*2010*), in which a leader creates working conditions for employees in which authority is shared, individuals have increased decision-making autonomy, and the leader exhibits greater confidence in the employees' work and talents. They discovered that an empowering leadership style was linked to employees feeling more psychologically empowered, as well as involvement in the creative process. Conger and Kanungo (*1988*) identified two types of empowerment: relational and

motivational. Power is a relational construct that refers to the process by which a leader or management shares his or her power with subordinates. Power is an employee's belief in self-efficacy as a motivating construct, and empowerment is a type of enabling that fosters motivation for achievement through self-efficacy (*Conger & Kanungo, 1988; as mentioned in Lee et al, 2014*).

Empowerment, according to Bowen and Lawler (1992), is defined as sharing information about organisational performance, rewards based on organisational performance, the knowledge that helps employees contribute to organisational performance, and the power to make decisions that influence organisational performance with frontline employees. They also stated that giving employees the authority to make important decisions motivates them to take ownership of their jobs and so become more accountable. Leaders can provide their team members autonomy, which instils a sense of trust, ownership, and control (*Hemlin, 2006*). In several studies, the degree of autonomy has been linked to innovation (*Denti, 2011*). However, if employed alone, this technique typically leads to ineffective and impractical proposals, as empowerment comes with its own set of problems. Not every employee is ready to be given more responsibility. They may lack focus and direction, as well as being goal-oriented, which makes it tough for them to get creatively motivated. Furthermore, the variety of ideas submitted is frequently vast, both in terms of quality and potential commercial impact. The company may wind up with various ideas that it does not want to adopt or does not have the means to do so. Managers may view the overflow of ideas and solutions from employees as a danger to the system's order, making it appear chaotic and unpredictable. Besides, the empowerment of the employees and taking decisions on their own will clash with the upper management due to social and organizational culture and hierarchy, which in terms will create more problems for the creative atmosphere as well as internal working conditions. On the other hand, the employees may feel they are being denied their rights to creative decision making and result in workplace tensions.

An exclusively bottom-up approach to innovation typically fails in this regard. It may well be seen in Case 3 where the ministry of disaster management used a decentralised bottom-up management strategy. There were several bodies to take necessary actions in multiple steps and were given decision-making autonomy, but the employees didn't understand the concept, the majority of them didn't feel empowered enough to take the initiative, and a lack of proper strategic information and decision-making channels created chaos in a critical situation. The

respondents, in that case, stated that, while they appreciate the effort, it is not adequately articulated, and that the employees are currently unqualified to take on the obligation.

Top-down: Leaders as managing innovation:

Leaders take on the second duty of executing the organization's innovation plans and goals. Facilitating a top-down approach to innovation helps to ensure that ideas given by employees are strategically aligned. And there are various benefits to doing so. Importantly, the innovation process is significantly more efficient because employees' efforts are focused solely on the most important aspects. According to Kim and Arnold, the top-down process is defined as the deliberate coordination of intentions and activities to achieve certain results enforced by a central authority (1996). Top management creates its long-term goals, intents, and methods in the form of a plan, which is then defined in as much detail as possible to translate it into collective actions with maximum discretion before taking action. In general, top management is in charge of setting an organization's overarching goals and objectives, as well as assigning resources, whereas lower-level organisational members are frequently in charge of carrying out the actions required to achieve those goals (Bower, 1974; Burgelman, 1983; Burgelman and Grove, 2007; Mintzberg, 1978; Mintzberg and Waters, 1985; as mentioned in Kim et al, 2014). According to a meta-analysis by Hülshager, Anderson, and Salgado, vision is one of the strongest predictors of innovation (2009). Secondly, an organization's reward system is a means to encourage specific behaviour. Individuals may perceive that such initiatives are supported rather than undermined when they are rewarded. Rewards, on the other hand, do not always have to be monetary. They can also serve as a kind of acknowledgement and positive feedback, which can be more valuable than money in some situations. The organisational hierarchy's distance between top management and lower-level employees generates a gap between managerial intentions and organisational actions, which can result in a misalignment of "intended" and "realised" strategies (Mintzberg, 1978). Like any other top-down initiative, the way leaders act communicates important messages to staff. Indeed, one of the most common ways to inhibit innovation is to pay some attention to it while doing nothing about it. Second is top management's attempt to model innovation, such as taking chances and being receptive to new ideas. It also entails just praising short-term results and retaining a fear of failure.

There may be disadvantages to choosing only this technique. Employees in top-down workplaces are focused on a mission and vision. However, individuals frequently struggle to identify how their current job fits into those objectives. In most companies, if a manager

approached a random employee and inquired about the company's strategy, he would be met with a blank stare. The majority of employees have no idea what drives profitability or how to work to keep the company's offering distinct in the market. They can perform the task at hand. In the depths, this can feel more like a process than a strategy. Cases 1 and 2 indicate that lower and middle-level employees did not feel engaged in the decision-making process and did not have a thorough understanding of the project or its goals. These two cases used a highly centralised top-down approach, but due to rigorous adherence to the approach, they were unable to successfully engage the workers. Employees lacked performance-based reward management, lacked sufficient resources to support workplace innovation, and thus failed to make a creative impact on the project and the organization's overall goals.

Balancing the two responsibilities is a difficulty for management in government organisations, specifically in the innovation project-based environment. There are numerous examples of leadership difficulties involving the dual responsibility of managing innovation. Upper management and R&D personnel, for example, may hold opposing viewpoints on which ideas should be developed. Another issue is one of control vs. freedom: how much control over innovative projects should be exercised. Too much control stifles drive and creativity by restricting autonomy. On the other hand, because an organization's development activities require a direction and strategy, innovation cannot be allowed to run uncontrolled. Therefore, the dual leadership strategy may be considered but it has to be very balanced and must be able to glide swiftly through both leadership types based on the project's requirement. Since a project has different phases, a single rigid style of leadership will not benefit as identified in the current research.

6.7 Revision of the conceptual framework:

As previously noted, the conceptual framework covered in chapter three was illustrated by adding significant elements discovered through an exhaustive investigation of earlier works of literature and secondary sources including newspaper articles and published reports. It served as a navigator to help define the research design and generate ideas for gathering data in an effort to address the research question. Because it was built using recent findings, it should be understood that it is only a tool to assist the study and not a concrete concept and will develop as a result of the primary research. . New evidence will be obtained as part of the study, and some of the components indicated in the conceptual framework may not reflect the outcomes

of new research. Hence, a revision must be made to determine which elements contributed and were recognised as part of the research and which did not.

All three initiatives encountered issues at various stages of their development, according to the findings. One of the major contributing elements was the rigidity of government policies, which affected the project both inside and outside. In all the scenarios in this research, a significant kind of staff reaction was observed, and it was highlighted as a significant barrier that adversely impacted the projects' success. The success or failure of the provided end product was determined by how users responded to new services and technology as well as how their socioeconomic and educational status affected their behaviour. These findings are supported by convincing data from the present study. The lack of suitable resources was also noted as one of the most significant facts. Financial resources, skilled labour, digital equipment, and infrastructure are all in limited supply. In all three of the examples under consideration, a shortage of resources caused significant delays and disruptions to the projects. The culture of a company determines how safe its employees feel to be themselves, as well as how much it encourages innovation and taking risks. The rigidity of the policies and the sharp split between upper management and lower-level personnel contributed to the lack of a creative organisational culture, which had a substantial impact on the three government cases in question. The current study was able to identify the distinct leadership philosophies used by the three projects and how they reflect the overall leadership landscape in the government sector organisations in Bangladesh. It also discovered that leadership styles had a demonstrable impact on all of the challenges that were discovered through the data collection and analysis of recurring themes and that some of the problems would have been resolved more successfully with a different or less strict management style.

Political unrest/interruption was one of the key potential factors that were identified from the review of the pieces of literature. Multiple studies have found that political upheaval, turbulence, and corruption in Bangladesh affect the delivery of any project and, in some cases, decide the project's conclusion. It did not, however, appear to be a hindrance to the gathered data. The fact that the projects were all controlled by the government was a big factor. The ministries were constituted by the dominant political party and therefore did not influence the projects running. The bureaucratic policies of course played a major role but no political corruption was mentioned strongly. Bribery was mentioned, but it was more of an internal than an external trigger, and again it was mentioned very vaguely and just by one respondent, thus

it was excluded as a barrier to public sector innovation in terms of the three cases under investigation.

Other political parties and the media exerted pressures were not discovered as part of this research as well. They are not mentioned as a stumbling block in any of the respondents' interviews. In Bangladesh, the opposition party currently barely have any engagement because the ruling party has been in power for a long time.

As a result, there was no protest from them. Some international organisations have reported that the Bangladeshi government is quite tight about media presentation and is presently scrutinising all negative news very closely, which could explain why it did not come up as an issue in the interview responses. There were few private-sector competitions as well because they partnered on projects with the government and the digitalized services could not be provided by the public sector alone (for example- payment of taxes, case filing with police, weather forecasts etc.). There are some industries where private enterprises have an advantage, but this was not the case with the projects chosen for this study. As a result, there was no protest from them. Some international organisations have reported that the Bangladeshi government is quite tight about media presentation and is presently scrutinising all negative news very closely, which could explain why it did not come up as an issue in the interview responses. There were few private-sector competitions as well because they partnered on projects with the government and the digitalized services could not be provided by the public sector alone (for example- payment of taxes, case filing with police, weather forecasts etc.). There are some industries where private enterprises have an advantage, but this was not the case with the projects chosen for this study.

The main dimensions of innovations in the investigated projects were all service & process levels digital innovations hence product and organisational level innovations have not been discussed above. Lack of infrastructure came as both an external and internal catalyst although it was just thought to be an external factor.

The results of this study and the factors mentioned above, which did not act as barriers in the three cases, suggest that when conceptual frameworks are created for case study research, they should consider how the framework will change in context and that there should always be room for improvement. Following the adjustments, the revised conceptual framework is presented below, which takes into account all the elements found in the selected cases.

Figure 6.3: Revised Version of Conceptual Framework (Source: Author)

6.8 Summary of the chapter:

This chapter summarised the important findings from the data collection, which were based on repeated patterns identified by the researcher during the interviews. The themes that emerged were then analysed to find the important factors that influenced the research's chosen examples. The themes were quite helpful in obtaining answers to the research questions that were developed to achieve the study's initial purpose. The chapter concludes with a detailed examination of possible leadership strategies for promoting innovation and addressing the innovation problems. The first conceptual framework developed in Chapter 3 was a generalised framework based on secondary research and literature review, and as a result, an evaluation was carried out based on the findings. The following chapter will include final thoughts on the entire thesis, including proposed strategies and study limitations in order to pave the way for future research and to discuss how the study contributes to practice and research.

Chapter 7: Conclusion and Recommendations

7.1 Introduction:

In a developing country like Bangladesh, government innovation is critical for promoting democracy, economic growth, governance, and social development. The current research examined examples of government innovation projects and identified important barriers that hampered the projects' smooth operation and implementation, as well as a feasible leadership strategy. By summarising the major aspects of each chapter and examining contributions in the fields of study and practice, this chapter will make final statements about the research. The limitations of the current study will be presented next, followed by recommendations for future studies and practice. Following that, the researcher's perception of their journey through the research will be covered in a reflection segment, followed by concluding thoughts for the research as a closure.

7.2 Summary of the research:

The research started with the aim of thoroughly understanding the challenges of government sector innovation in Bangladesh, as well as the importance of getting the appropriate leadership in place to manage them. In chapter one, a brief background of the context of research has been discussed. An overview of Bangladesh, the state of innovation and the rationale of the study followed by the research objectives and questions were presented.

The study conducted an extensive review in chapter two, of existing works of literature to identify potential gaps and discovered that there were very few studies relating to this topic in the context of the Bangladesh public sector. Similar studies can be found in other developing countries but are very limited in Bangladesh. A study of the previous pieces of the literature identified that scholars think leadership has significance on innovation, specifically on public sector innovation.

In chapter three, a generalised conceptual framework was developed to jot down potential internal and external barriers, with leadership serving as the link between them all. The conceptual framework was an evolving one based on the literature review and secondary research. Key variables of the research have been discussed in the chapter.

In chapter four, the researcher has observed reality from an ontological assumption, which is subjective, based on the research questions and objectives; the research philosophy is pragmatism. The qualitative research was decided to be conducted using the Case study

approach to understand the situation and provide a practical contribution as well as contribute to the existing gaps in the literature. The research questions and objectives were set to be addressed via open-ended questions with respondents of three government projects- the automation project of Dhaka South City Corporation, the Online GD filing of Dhaka Metropolitan police and the Mobile-based cyclone early warning system for coastal areas.

Chapter five is a detailed description of the data gathered through semi-structured interviews. Through the voice of respondents, the cases, as well as many elements of the events that occurred throughout various phases of the projects, have been highlighted. These respondents were chosen after careful consideration of their significant role in the cases.

Following thematic analysis, some repeating themes were identified, which were then examined to see how they contributed to the answers to the study questions and the suggested leadership strategy in chapter six. The key findings were external and internal factors that impacted different parts of the projects-

- Complicated government policies
- Hierarchy issues between management and employees
- Scarcity of resources
- Reaction to change
- Consumer reception
- Lack of creative atmosphere
- Problems with leadership approaches

In light of the problems with the current leadership practices that were identified in the data analysis process, a dual leadership method has been discussed. It has been proposed that a balance of bottom-up and top-down leadership can be adapted to facilitate innovation as well as mitigate the barriers that were identified in the data analysis. In the dual role, a leader or manager works as an innovation stimulator or motivator as well as an innovation manager.

7.3 Contributions:

7.3.1 Contributions to the field of research- filling the gap:

The purpose of this study was to learn about the internal and external barriers to innovation in the public sector, how leadership influences them, and what kind of leadership strategy could be beneficial in addressing the difficulties more effectively. The subject of this research, which

is bringing leadership and innovation together in the Bangladeshi public sector, is original and needs to be explored further. As previously stated, the majority of research on Bangladesh is focused on the ready-made garment sector, political corruption, policy reforms, and tourism. However, the public sector's innovation, challenges, and impact on the entire process must be examined, and the current research has taken an approach to do so. It paves the way for future researchers to draw inspiration from the work and pursue further exploration.

The research re-established Lewis et al's three essential elements that generate innovation (2018). First and foremost, it researched and established that any organization's potential to innovate is influenced by its operating environment as well as its internal structures and processes. The current study was able to pinpoint important internal and external factors that serve as primary motivators or impediments to public sector service innovation. According to the findings, senior managers' traits and competencies have an impact on organisational change and innovation. The study also identified a collaboration or networking with other organisations to complete the innovation project, since all three initiatives studied hired employees and resources to build the systems as required.

According to the findings of the literature study, the majority of public sector innovation research was either mixed-method, entirely quantitative, looked at innovation from the perspective of citizens, or focused solely on external catalysts. The current study looked at what was going on inside the project as well as external influences that had a direct or indirect impact on the project from the perspective of the managers and internal staff. Adam et al. (2013), Azam (2007), Tahmin & Khan (2012), Sharif & Kumar (2012), Khalid (2011), and Menon (2002) all discuss policy reforms and regulations and technological transformation in a broad sense. The current study fills in the gaps by examining how innovation develops specifically at the service or product level, at three different government organisations, what internal and external barriers they face from initiation to implementation, and how leadership can influence or alleviate process and implementation challenges.

Next, the research fills a gap left by Tahrnia and Jaegal (2012), who focused on external barriers to government innovation and proposed some solutions to address them using secondary research. Internal problems and organisational culture were not addressed, however, the current study looked into both internal and external barriers to innovation and found that organisational culture is a crucial motivator of managerial approach, innovation behaviour and staff reaction to change through primary research. The current study also advised strategies

based on responses from sector managers or employees to create a more practical solution that can be adopted.

The study fills a gap in existing leadership research in the Bangladeshi public sector by performing primary research based on specific innovative projects and conducting a semi-structured open-ended interview. Most crucially, as stated in the literature review chapter, the current study was influenced by the work of Alam, Rahman, Teicher, and Van Gramber (2017), who investigated public sector leadership but did not include innovation while developing solutions. The current researcher has successfully combined innovation and public sector leadership, which will stimulate future researchers to explore deeper into the subject to develop futuristic sustainable leadership solutions to motivate public sector innovation.

By examining the three government innovation projects' leadership styles and demonstrating that a top-down leadership style is unquestionably not the best method for all the stages and issues that arose, the current research successfully advances the theory. It fills a research gap by identifying and discussing why top-down leadership is not the only significant way to generate innovation in the Bangladeshi public sector, which was a limitation of Chowdhury's study (2020). The current study complements the argument made by Franklin and Plimmer (2019) and Aravena (2019) by analysing the use of a top-down or bottom-up approach and how it adversely affected the cases under investigation when used on their own. It also adds to the literature on the impact of leadership on public section innovation in developing countries as well as Bangladesh.

This new study again fills the gap in the argument made by Abedin, Ferdaus, Shah, and Sayem (2021), who, like many earlier researchers, only discussed the user perception challenges of digitalized projects in their study and neglected to account for the challenges that the digitalized public sector face before implementation. The current research article offers a thorough overview of the challenges that affected digitised projects from creation to completion.

By gathering information through in-depth one-on-one interviews, which was thought to be the best method to capture an accurate picture of government officials working on innovative projects and the environment they operate in, the study adds to the body of literature already available on public sector innovation research. The current study succeeds in understanding the underlying causes of why some digital innovation in public sectors is successful while others are not, as well as how management style influences these outcomes in which were mentioned in the study of Kuldosheva (2021) as a potential scope of future research.

Most importantly, the suggestion of a dual leadership framework, which can be used to address essential leadership characteristics to remove barriers to innovation, is one of the most novel contributions to the field of public sector innovation and leadership research. This framework effectively fills the gap in the works of Zaman (2021), who in his policy reform paper suggested how to train public sector managers and bureaucrats to act more fervently and promote innovation, but he neglects to consider the factors that prevent innovation from being successfully delivered and whether the suggested training programme has the features to accommodate particular leadership requirements to address the challenges in various phases of innovation.

The findings generated by this research therefore not only contribute to the literature on Bangladesh but also can be utilised to further investigate issues in developing nations and check whether similar results can be generated. As all developing nations face inflexible policies, insufficient resources, hierarchy issues and a lack of creative culture in incorporating digital innovation in service delivery, they need capable management to handle challenges to make innovation sustainable. The dual leadership framework suggested can be used in similar projects in other developing nations and further investigation may be conducted to test its validity to meet country-specific requirements or elevate the framework to suit specific needs.

7.3.2 Practical implications:

The current research paper made some significant contributions in the field of management practice of the public sector to improve innovative service delivery to enhance efficiency, transparency and authenticity. One practical contribution would be a detailed descriptive analysis of barriers to three innovative projects. The study uncovered several important issues that impacted projects both internally and externally using a case study method which has not been used in a similar study in the context of Bangladesh prior to this research. The greatest way to learn about prospective challenges is to always reflect and learn from those that have gone through them and as previously addressed in the body of research, one of the most effective tools researchers utilise to obtain an in-depth understanding of the participants in the case study. This paper provides new insights into the specific barriers that impacted the different phases of three actual innovation projects as well as the overall impact rather than generalizing findings presented in previous studies. The findings generated by this study will give public sector managerial bodies valuable insight into the hurdles, empowering them to handle the innovation process more efficiently and proactively. The researcher is looking

forward to compiling key findings and recommendations into a report and distributing it to the three projects' upper-level management officials so that they can appreciate the importance of this research and use it to mitigate any future shortcomings in terms of resource management, employee motivation, and creating an innovative and supportive organisational culture that can easily accommodate changes into the workplace without resistance.

Another substantial practical contribution is the study's originality in the field of digital innovation in public sector service delivery and its connection with leadership. The novelty comes from its setting- interviewees who work for three separate public sector innovation projects were asked about leadership in the digital transformation process. The interview data is comprehensive and included perspectives from respondents included in various phases of growth. The respondent's viewpoint will be extremely useful for future projects or ventures that are currently being considered. Although the projects' levels of digital success differed, there were clear parallels in the discussions of the impact that different types of leadership had on overcoming obstacles in different phases and encouraged the researcher to present some practical recommendations.

According to the limited evidence available to date, some leadership theories appear to be better suited to enthuse and encourage followers, while others structure organisational activity, overcome resistance, and so have a good effect on implementation. The current study has found that the choice of leadership styles is related to particular innovation stages and project types, and the body of previous literature does not address this clearly. The practical implication of the current research is that the best leadership style should be determined by the precise innovation objectives to be met in each project phase. The proposed Dual Leadership framework has the potential to measure this if put into practice. The dual leadership approach suggested in this study will help advise the public sector managers and policymakers on the procedures and strategies to apply in similar situations and in creating a policy to build a framework for public sector leadership to encourage innovation in partnership with the current researcher and any potential future researchers. This framework can be included in the training programme for management candidates or civil service starters to test the validity and practicality as by understanding and analysing barriers that are specific to different phases the existing and future managers will be able to incorporate the framework and decide upon which phase requires top-down management and which phase may require a more bottom-up approach.

7.4 Limitations of the research:

Regardless of how thoroughly researchers plan and construct their study, it is unavoidable that they may encounter some limits that are not always detected before undertaking the research. This research is no exception to that reality and the researcher would like to point out some limitations which impacted the study in some way, were not anticipated beforehand and were not within the control of the researcher –

- The current study used Case Study as the research technique to comprehend a broad and ill-defined concept of a possible link between leadership styles and service innovation in public sector organisations. The study could look at three case studies and reach a limited number of people to explore the situation in detail. Although the study generated some strong findings, since Bangladesh has a significant number of public sector organisations, all of the observations provided by these three units of analysis may not be identical to those generated by other entities or reflect the same behaviour in all circumstances.
- Since the technique was solely qualitative, a quantitative angle may have been introduced as well to analyse the personality qualities of upper management to better understand leadership behaviour and recommend strategies.
- The study's completion was hampered by time constraints and the COVID-19 pandemic. Since the researcher used a case study approach to investigate the research questions, conducting the interviews face to face as intended would have been more fruitful. The global lockdown, on the other hand, limited the physical capacity to be present at government offices and comprehend the reality of the situation, and the various stages of the project, and communicate with staff face to face. The entire interview procedure took place online, over the phone, and through various social media platforms, and the researcher had to accept the respondent's point of view as is, rather than closely studying them and their working style. Because the course time was limited, the researcher was unable to return to the country and revalidate the results.
- Furthermore, because the interviews were done over the phone and through social media platforms, access was severely limited. As the offices were closed and not everyone had an internet connection at home, the researcher was unable to reach the intended number of respondents. None of the respondents who took part in the interview agreed to a video conversation. As a result, the researcher could only make a

restricted observation based on their tones and use of language, but in a case study, the researcher must experience reality from his or her point of view. It was easier for them to avoid facing the researcher and avoid more critical questions or facial expressions being noticed. This had an impact on the interview responses due to the researcher being unable to ask comprehensive questions based on their behaviour and approach when giving answers. This influenced the data collection and the study's outcome since the researcher needed more evidence to tie up some loose ends and obtain a better understanding of the problem.

Future questions arising from the thesis in accordance with the limitations can be:

- Can the observations be duplicated if the research is conducted among a large number of public sector innovation projects or include policymakers?
- With the advancement of technology and change in global/national market trends, what kind of different barriers will the future projects face?
- Can the dual leadership framework proposed in this research be implemented in public sector projects successfully?

7.5 Recommendations:

7.5.1 Recommendations for future research:

- As mentioned above in the limitations, due to a large number of public sector organisations in Bangladesh, all of the observations made by these three units of analysis may not be identical to those made by other entities or reflect the same behaviour in all scenarios. There is a need for more large-scale future studies including a wide range of government organisations to gain a better understanding of the reality and findings.
- A mixed-method approach for further studies for in-depth investigation of the manager's personality attributes, their socio-economic background and their impact on government sector innovative service delivery can be taken into consideration to generate more interesting findings. Additionally, it creates a scope for future research which can be conducted through face-to-face interviews and observations of the projects in-person to gather more detailed information.

- The dual leadership approach proposed by the researcher is a relatively new concept in terms of mitigating the challenges and needs further exploration by analysing its validity and effectiveness in practice in future research.

7.5.2 Practice recommendations:

- Developing a dual leadership framework for innovation that gives the managers the understanding of the conditions allowing innovation to thrive, determining the correct balance between the two roles, and adopting managerial attitudes that will strike a perfect harmony of the top-down and bottom-up leadership approach. This leadership strategy should be constructed in a way that will not only help the managers address the internal and external challenges discovered in this study but also eliminate potential future ones.
- Ensure that both political and administrative leaders are on board with increasing public sector innovation activities by reconstructing or reconsidering some policies. Audits to uncover particular issues with the current policies and potential policies will not only impede productivity growth but also examine ministries' and different subsidiary public sector bodies' current capabilities.
- Create a central government organisation that is in charge of leadership and managerial development. This organisation can offer a variety of fundamental leadership and management training courses and programmes, as well as more specialised development opportunities (*Mau, Xavier & Mendoza, 2018*).
- Develop a list of potential leadership champions within the organization. The first challenge is to identify individuals who already possess the requisite competencies to lead in the public sector or have the ability to develop those competencies in a timely fashion. Once the future leadership candidates have been identified, begin to provide those individuals with targeted leadership training and development.
- One of the beneficial techniques for employees to get new experiences and develop innovative skills is to allow and encourage them to work temporarily with another team or on a different project to sharpen their talents in a new setting and project, better react to changing circumstances, establish a better network, learn best practices, and potentially help them advance in their careers. Organisations can build rotational or project-based programmes where managers can post opportunities, the talents they seek, the percentage of time sought, and the duration of the project. A similar approach has been adopted by the United States successfully.

- Leaders/managers can encourage employees to engage in innovative activities across an organisation by examining how innovation occurs inside it. It can also show innovation roadblocks that leaders can eliminate, as well as teach others how to drive change in a large organisation and the skills and processes that the organisation needs to adopt and replicate so that innovation is more easily available to the rest of the organisation. The Brazilian Regional Post Office partnered with WeGov by putting members through the six-month training programme, where they received hands-on and classroom instruction in design and innovation, and then applied what they learned to problems that public employees face on the job (*OECD, 2017*).

7.6 Researcher's Reflection:

Reflective practice is a self-analysis tool that allows practitioners to gain a better understanding of the nature and impact of their work, which leads to chances for professional growth and development (*Kottkamp & Osterman, 1993*). Professionals can use reflective practice to evaluate their performance, make sense of what happened, and learn from their mistakes and experiences to grow, progress, and adapt (*Peel et al., 2012*).

There are a variety of experiences that could be considered life-changing. Each incident, for better or worse, altered the trajectory of my life. Conducting this research certainly was one of the most transforming moments of my life. As a student and as a researcher, I believed I had established self-discipline, which is critical for effective learning. I steadily gained strength and confidence in all transferable skills, such as communication, effective learning, teamwork and information technology, throughout this study. When I first started writing up my ideas about the research, I could not grasp the magnitude of work I needed to do to get to the outcome. Working with different people has given me a perspective to analyse information from different angles and observe reality as it is. Learning about government organisations, the employees, the project experience, different policies, and resource allocation were interesting points where I got a lot of information that needed to be analysed and were extremely helpful in my research findings. The COVID 19 situation and travel restrictions have definitely affected my ability to perceive the reality of my chosen cases for this research in person, but I did not lose hope and amended my way of research accordingly. I believe my time management skills in the earlier phases of the research could have been better and I have learnt from those mistakes. The constructive feedback from my peers and lead supervisors has enhanced my confidence to complete the task and carry on enhancing the skills for my future professional development.

7.7 Concluding Remarks:

The Bangladeshi government is dedicated to establishing a modern state of welfare that is fair, progressive, democratic, and insightful. Bangladesh will become a resourceful and contemporary country by 2041, according to the current democratic government's "Vision 2041." As a result, it's critical to encourage, promote, and carefully cultivate the spirit of innovation and creativity. The Bangladeshi government is attempting to deliver high-quality, far-reaching services despite its limited operational capabilities and resources; yet, the road ahead remains long and arduous. Organizations survive and grow from innovation, whether it's discovering the next great thing or improving on what's already been done. Working with top management, a further examination is needed to locate forces of change that may influence the organisation and policy area, as well as to identify opportunities within the seemingly chaotic landscape. Despite some limitations, the current research is concluding its journey hoping to encourage future researchers in Bangladesh, to generate better leadership and administrative solutions to sustain innovation in public sector organisations. It is also eager to generate the attention of public sector management officials regarding the dual leadership strategy where management can take both roles of innovation stimulators and innovation managers. The strategy needs to be put into practice on a small scale to determine the success and requirement for adjustment to the government projects it is being implied to. To keep delivering excellent innovation results, a change in governance structures, the establishment of incentives and metrics, and the implementation of learning programmes to teach innovation practice, as well as finding leadership champions and providing them with high-quality professional training are required.

Appendices

Interview Participation Form

Title: An analysis of innovation barriers in the Bangladeshi Public Sector and how leadership approaches can influence them

I would like to invite you to take part in a research study. Before you decide you need to understand why the research is being done and what it would involve for you. Please take the time to read the following information carefully. Ask questions if anything you read is not clear or if you would like more information. Take time to decide whether or not to take part.

A little bit about myself and the research:

I am a Bangladeshi student who is currently on the route of completing a DBA (Doctorate in Business Administration) research degree under the School of Business and Enterprise at the University of West of Scotland. As part of the degree, I must undertake an original research project. The research project focuses on various challenges to government innovation in Bangladesh and suggests leadership strategies for overcoming them.

What taking part in it involves:

If you give consent to take part in the study, you will be interviewed for about 45 minutes to 1 hour approximately. Due to the current COVID 19 situation, all interviews will be conducted digitally using digital media platforms like zoom, skype, or other applications. The topics of the interview will be designed to analyse the internal and external catalysts that promote or demote innovation in your project and identify current leadership and decision-making approach for overcoming them. Please be noted, that the interviews will be more like a conversation and will be focused on understanding your perspective and experience on the situation rather than accepting a direct “yes”/”no” answer.

Why have you been chosen to take part:

After conducting the initial literature and background research, your project has been selected for the case study. Every person related to the project has been included using stakeholder analysis and after careful consideration of your vital contribution to the project, you have been selected to share your valuable experience.

Do you have to take part?

Your participation is completely voluntary, and you have the right to refuse participation, refuse any question and, withdraw at any time without any consequence whatsoever.

What are the possible risks of taking part?

The study is completely harmless and no physical or any other harm is expected from taking part in the study. The interviews will be conducted digitally and if you do not feel comfortable sharing the video please let me know at the beginning of the interview. The consent of your line managers will also be taken before contacting you. You should not feel threatened or pressured to share or withhold information. If at any point, you feel that you or someone else is at risk of harm please inform me and I will report this to the relevant authorities. Please be aware, in case of any sort of the above situation, I have to report it to the authorities with or without your permission.

Will taking part be confidential:

Yes. Your contribution will be anonymous. Nowhere in the study, your name or designation will be mentioned. You can ask any questions before/during the study about confidentiality. All data will be removed and destroyed after the period stated below.

How will the information you provide be recorded, stored, and protected?

Signed consent forms and original audio recordings will be retained with the researcher, secured in password-protected electronic devices (laptop or mobile and the university's online storage system for the researcher), and only the researcher and the Director of Studies will have access to the materials. The information will be contained until the successful completion of the studies. A transcript of interviews in which all identifying information has been removed will be retained for a further two years after this. Under freedom of information legalization, you are entitled to access the information you have provided at any time.'

What will happen to the results of the study?

Currently, the researcher only aims to submit it for the doctoral thesis, if she wishes to publish any paper you will be notified, and your consent will be taken.

Who should you contact for further information?

Contact details of the researcher:

Nawreen Afreen

Banner: B00349550

Email: b00349550@studentmail.uws.ac.uk

University of West of Scotland

London Campus, Import Building, 2 Clove Crescent, East India, London, E14 2BE

Contact details of the DoS:

Dr. Steve Smithson

Email: steve.smithson@partner.uws.ac.uk

Thank You, If you are happy to take part in the study, please fill in the consent form and return it to b00349550@studentmail.uws.ac.uk.

Example of Consent Form

Title: An analysis of innovation barriers in the Bangladeshi Public Sector and how leadership approaches can influence them

Consent to take part in research

- I..... voluntarily agree to participate in this research study.
- I understand that even if I agree to participate now, I can withdraw at any time or refuse to answer any question without any consequences of any kind.
- I understand that I can withdraw permission to use data from my interview within two weeks after the interview, in which case the material will be deleted.
- I have had the purpose and nature of the study explained to me in writing and I have had the opportunity to ask questions about the study.
- I understand that I will not benefit directly from participating in this research.
- I agree with my interview being audio-recorded.
- I understand that all information I provide for this study will be treated confidentially.
- I understand that in any report on the results of this research my identity will remain anonymous.
- This will be done by keeping any details of my interview anonymous which may reveal my identity or the identity of people I speak about (if necessary or if requested).
- I understand that disguised extracts from my interview may be quoted in the published dissertation
- I understand that if I inform the researcher that I or someone else is at risk of harm they may have to report this to the relevant authorities - they will discuss this with me first but may be required to report with or without my permission.
- I understand that signed consent forms and original audio recordings will be retained in the electronic devices of the researcher and as printed copies, will be shared with the doctor of Studies and School until the exam board confirms the results of their dissertation.
- I understand that a transcript of my interview in which all identifying information has been removed will be retained for two years from the date of the exam board.
- I understand that under freedom of information legalization I am entitled to access the information I have provided at any time while it is in storage as specified above.
- I understand that I am free to contact any of the people involved in the research to seek further clarification and information.

Contact Details of the Researcher:

Nawreen Afreen

Banner: B00349550

Email: b00349550@studentmail.uws.ac.uk

The University of West of Scotland
London Campus, Import Building, 2 Clove Crescent, East India, London, E14 2BE

Contact details of the DoS:

Dr Steve Smithson

Email: steve.smithson@partner.uws.ac.uk

Signature of the research participant

.....

Date.....

Signature of researcher

I believe the participant is giving informed consent to participate in this study

.....

Date.....

Sample semi-structured open-ended questions

Ice Breaking Questions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What is your job title? • What is your professional/academic background? • How many years of experience do you have in handling public sector projects?
Theme 1- The innovation Project	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Tell me about the project • What was the intention behind the project • How were you involved in the project/what was your role • Is the project complete <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Has it reached the intended outcome - If not then what is happening • What was your professional achievement from this project
Theme 2- Internal Challenge	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Have you faced any challenges • Which phase saw the most problem-prompted with further topics e.g- budget restriction, employee motivation, organizational culture, resistance to change • how was it resolved • how did it impact the project delivery/completion/implementations
Theme 3- External Challenge	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Any external factor you think affected the project • Which phase saw the most problem-prompted with further topics e.g- political pressure, private sector competition, socio-economic background of the users, media pressure, environmental constraints • how was it resolved

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • how did it impact the project delivery/completion/implementations
<p>Theme 4- Leadership/managerial approach</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • how did you manage to resolve the challenges • do you feel the approach you have taken was appropriate • What's an area of the approach you want to improve • Do you feel like the employees are creative enough, if not what might be stopping them from being creative • What is your approach to resistance • Are there any aspects of the company culture you wish you could change • Do you support/ encourage/mentor other members of the team?

References and Bibliography

- Aspers, P. and Corte, U., (2019). What is Qualitative in Qualitative Research. *Qualitative Sociology*, 42(2), pp.139-160.
- Arfeen, M.I. and Khan, N., 2009. Public sector innovation: Case study of e-government projects in Pakistan. *The Pakistan Development Review*, pp.439-457.
- Ahmed, Z, Nawaz, A & Khan, I. (2016). Leadership Theories and Styles: A Literature Review. *Journal of Resources Development and Management*. 16.
- Ahmed, S.P. and Ahmed, M.T.Z., 2014. Qualitative research: A decisive element to epistemological & ontological discourse. *Journal of Studies in Social Sciences*, 8(2).
- Anthony, S. and Jack, S., (2009). *Qualitative case study methodology in nursing research: an integrative review*. *Journal of Advanced Nursing*, 65(6), pp.1171-1181.
- Adams, W., (2015). Conducting Semi-Structured Interviews. *Handbook of Practical Program Evaluation*, pp.492-505.
- Alberti, A. and Bertucci, G., (2006). Replicating innovations in governance: an overview. *Innovations in governance and public administration: replicating what works*, pp.1-21.
- Avermaete, T., Morgan, E.J., Viaene, J., Pitts, E., Crawford, N. and Mahon, D., (2003), June. Regional patterns of innovation: Case study of small food firms. In *DRUID summer conference* (Vol. 2003, p. 1).
- Ansell C and Gash A (2008) Collaborative governance in theory and practice. *Journal of Public Administration Research and Theory* 18(4): 543–571
- Alkindi, A.M. and Chaldler, J., (2018). The Impacts of Leadership Styles and Organizational Cultures on Public Innovations in the Emirates. *International Journal of Business and Management*, 13(7), pp.1-18.
- Aljarallah, S. and Lock, R., (2020). An Investigation into Sustainable e-Government in Saudi Arabia. *Electronic Journal of e-Government*, 18(1), pp.pp1-16.
- Amagoh, F. and Bhuiyan, S., (2010). Public sector reform in the Republic of Kazakhstan. *Central Asia Business Journal*, 3, pp.12-20.
- Amabile, T.M., Schatzel, E.A., Moneta, G.B. and Kramer, S.J., (2004). Leader behaviors and the work environment for creativity: Perceived leader support. *The Leadership Quarterly*, 15(1), pp.5-32.
- Axtell, C.M., Holman, D.J., Unsworth, K.L., Wall, T.D., Waterson, P.E. and Harrington, E., (2000). Shopfloor innovation: Facilitating the suggestion and

implementation of ideas. *Journal of occupational and organizational psychology*, 73(3), pp.265-285.

- Ahearne, M., Mathieu, J. and Rapp, A., (2005). To empower or not to empower your sales force? An empirical examination of the influence of leadership empowerment behavior on customer satisfaction and performance. *Journal of Applied psychology*, 90(5), p.945.
- Anderson, N., De Dreu, C.K. and Nijstad, B.A., (2004). The routinization of innovation research: A constructively critical review of the state-of-the-science. *Journal of organizational Behavior*, 25(2), pp.147-173.
- Amanchukwu, R.N., Stanley, G.J. and Ololube, N.P., (2015). A review of leadership theories, principles and styles and their relevance to educational management. *Management*, 5(1), pp.6-14.
- Azam, S., 2007. Internet adoption and usage in Bangladesh. *Japanese Journal of Administrative Science*, 20(1), pp.43-54.
- Ali, M.M. and Parvin, R., 2010. Strategic management of tourism sector in Bangladesh to raise gross domestic product: An analysis. *AIUB Business and Economic Paper Series, July, American International University Bangladesh*.
- Alom, S., 2019. *Bureaucratic Reform for a Bangladesh in 2041*. [online] The Financial Express. Available at: <https://www.thefinancialexpress.com.bd/views/bureaucratic-reform-for-a-bangladesh-in-2041-1571410800>
- Alvarez, J.L., Svejnova, S. and Vives, L., 2007. Leading in pairs. *MIT Sloan Management Review*, 48(4), p.10.
- Allas, T. and Hunt, V., 2018. Accelerating the diffusion of technology-enabled business practices. *The McKinsey Quarterly*.
- Burnes, B., 2004. Kurt Lewin and the planned approach to change: a re-appraisal. *Journal of Management studies*, 41(6), pp.977-1002.
- Bhuiyan, S.H. and Amagoh, F., 2011. Public sector reform in Kazakhstan: issues and perspectives. *International Journal of Public Sector Management*.
- Belk, R., Green, P. and Tull, D., 1978. Research for Marketing Decisions. *Journal of Marketing Research*, 15(4), p.658.
- Boblin, S.L., Ireland, S., Kirkpatrick, H. and Robertson, K., 2013. Using Stake's qualitative case study approach to explore implementation of evidence-based practice. *Qualitative health research*, 23(9), pp.1267-1275.
- Braun, V. and Clarke, V., 2012. Thematic analysis.
- Borins, S., 2001. Encouraging innovation in the public sector. *Journal of intellectual capital*.

- Baumol, WJ (1967) Macroeconomics of unbalanced growth: The anatomy of an urban crisis. *American Economic Review*, 57: 415-426.
- Bangladesh Bureau of Statistics (2012), Bangladesh Population & Housing Census
- Bowen, D. E., & Lawler, E. E., III. (1992). The empowerment of service workers: What, why, how and when. *Sloan Management Review*, 33(3), 31-39.
- Bhuiyan, M.S.H., 2011. Public sector eService development in Bangladesh: Status, prospects and challenges. *Electronic Journal of e-Government*, 9(1), pp.15-29.
- Bernier, Luc, Taïeb Hafsi, and Carl Deschamps. 2015. Environmental Determinants of Public Sector Innovation: A Study of Innovation Awards in Canada. *Public Management Review* 17 (6): 834 – 56.
- Barrientos, A., 2002. Health policy in Chile: the return of the public sector?. *Bulletin of Latin American Research*, 21(3), pp.442-459.
- Btrc.gov.bd. 2020. *Mobile Phone Subscribers in Bangladesh February, 2020* | BTRC. [online] Available at:<<http://www.btrc.gov.bd/content/mobile-phone-subscribers-bangladesh-february-2020>>
- Byron, R., 2020. *Widening job market a challenging prospect*. [online] The Daily Star. Available at:<<https://www.thedailystar.net/business/news/widening-job-market-challenging-prospect-1860481>>
- Bekkers, V., Edelenbos, J., & Steijn, B. (2011). *Innovation in the public sector* Palgrave Macmillan New York.
- Bossink, B.A., 2007. Leadership for sustainable innovation. *International Journal of Technology Management & Sustainable Development*, 6(2), pp.135-149.
- Bel, R., 2010. Leadership and innovation: Learning from the best. *Global business and organizational excellence*, 29(2), pp.47-60.
- Brewer, J. and Hunter, A., 1989. The multimethod approach and its promise. *Multimethod research: A synthesis of styles*, 175, pp.13-28.
- Brinkmann, S. and Tanggaard, L., 2010. Toward an epistemology of the hand. *Studies in philosophy and education*, 29(3), pp.243-257.
- Becker, S.W. and Whisler, T.L., 1967. The innovative organization: A selective view of current theory and research. *The journal of Business*, 40(4), pp.462-469.
- Boon, J., Wynen, J. and Callens, C. (2021) 'A stakeholder perspective on public sector innovation: Linking the target groups of innovations to the inclusion of stakeholder ideas', *International Review of Administrative Sciences*. DOI: 10.1177/00208523211043704.
- Mergel, I. and Desouza, K.C., 2013. Implementing open innovation in the public sector: The case of Challenge. gov. *Public administration review*, 73(6), pp.882-890.
- Sørensen, E. and Torfing, J., 2011. Enhancing collaborative innovation in the public sector. *Administration & Society*, 43(8), pp.842-868.
- Verhoest, K., Verschuere, B. and Bouckaert, G., 2007. Pressure, legitimacy, and innovative behaviour by public organizations. *Governance*, 20(3), pp.469-497.

- Hameduddin, T., Fernandez, S. and Demircioglu, M.A., 2020. Conditions for open innovation in public organizations: Evidence from Challenge. gov. *Asia Pacific Journal of Public Administration*, 42(2), pp.111-131.
- Chesbrough, H., Vanhaverbeke, W. and West, J. eds., 2006. *Open innovation: Researching a new paradigm*. Oxford University Press on Demand.
- Heeks, R., 2009. *eGovernment for Development - Case Studies: The National Data Bank Project: An Expensive Lesson for Bangladesh*. [online] Egov4dev.org. Available at: <http://www.egov4dev.org/success/case/ndb.shtml>
- Chowdhury, A., 2020. How Bangladesh is seizing the opportunities of e-governance. [online] World Economic Forum. Available at: <https://www.weforum.org/agenda/2020/11/bangladesh-and-digital/>
- Cinar, E., Trott, P. and Simms, C., 2019. A systematic review of barriers to the public sector innovation process. *Public Management Review*, 21(2), pp.264-290.
- Kusumasari, B., Pramusinto, A., Santoso, A.D. and Fathin, C.A., 2019. What shapes public sector innovation? *Public Policy and Administration*, 18(4), pp.430-446.
- Lan, M.T. and Hung, T.H., 2018. The leadership competency in Vietnam public administration. *Organizations and markets in emerging economies*, 9(1), pp.8-20.
- Khan, M.A., Ismail, F.B., Hussain, A. and Alghazali, B., 2020. The interplay of leadership styles, innovative work behaviour, organizational culture, and organizational citizenship behaviour. *Sage Open*, 10(1), p.2158244019898264.
- Aziz, A., 2020. Digital inclusion challenges in Bangladesh: The case of the National ICT Policy. *Contemporary South Asia*, 28(3), pp.304-319.
- Panir, M.J.H., Xiaolin, X. and Zijun, M., 2019. Integration of ICT with knowledge management to foster digital innovation: the case of Bangladesh public sector. *International Journal of Managing Public Sector Information and Communication Technologies (IJMP ICT)* Vol, 9.
- Abedin, M.M., Ferdous, M., Shah, A.M. and Sayem, M.A., 2021. The Role of Union Digital Centres in Reducing Social Inequalities in Bangladesh. *Bangladesh Journal of Public Administration*, 29(3).
- Hernandez, K., 2019. *Barriers to Digital Services Adoption in Bangladesh*.
- Franken, E. and Plimmer, G., 2019. Mediocre and harmful public sector leadership. *International Journal of Public Leadership*.
- Aravena, F., 2019. Destructive leadership behavior: An exploratory study in Chile. *Leadership and policy in schools*, 18(1), pp.83-96.
- Kesting, P., Ulhøi, J.P., Song, L.J. and Niu, H., 2015. The impact of leadership styles on innovation-a review. *Journal of Innovation Management*, 3(4), pp.22-41.
- Mujeri, M.K. and Mujeri, N., 2021. *Services Sector in Bangladesh: Changes and Prospects*. In *Structural Transformation of Bangladesh Economy* (pp. 205-228). Springer, Singapore.
- Kuldosheva, G., 2021. Challenges and opportunities of digital transformation in the public sector in transition economies: Examination of the case of Uzbekistan.
- Al-Saadi, H., 2014. Demystifying Ontology and Epistemology in research methods. *Research gate*, 1(1), pp.1-10.

- Kaushik, V. and Walsh, C.A., 2019. Pragmatism as a research paradigm and its implications for social work research. *Social sciences*, 8(9), p.255.
- Coy, M.J., 2019. Research methodologies: Increasing understanding of the world. *International Journal of Scientific and Research Publications*, 9(1), pp.71-77.
- Ebneyamini, S. and Sadeghi Moghadam, M.R., 2018. Toward developing a framework for conducting case study research. *International journal of qualitative methods*, 17(1), p.1609406918817954.
- Östman, L. and Wickman, P.O., 2014. A pragmatic approach on epistemology, teaching, and learning. *Science Education*.
- Kelly, L.M. and Cordeiro, M., 2020. Three principles of pragmatism for research on organizational processes. *Methodological innovations*, 13(2), p.2059799120937242.
- Godenhjelm, S. and Johanson, J.E., 2018. The effect of stakeholder inclusion on public sector project innovation. *International Review of Administrative Sciences*, 84(1), pp.42-62.
- Creswell, J.W. and Creswell, J.D., 2017. *Research design: Qualitative, quantitative, and mixed methods approaches*. Sage publications.
- CHR – Citizens Help Request (2021). Available at <http://chr.police.gov.bd>,
- Centre for Public Impact (CPI). 2016. *Using ICT for disaster management in Bangladesh*. [online] Available at:<<https://www.centreforpublicimpact.org/case-study/disaster-management-bangladesh/>>
- Coccia, M. (2017) ‘Varieties of capitalism’s theory of innovation and a conceptual integration with leadership-oriented executives: the relation between typologies of executive, technological and socio economic performances’, *Int. J. Public Sector Performance Management*, Vol. 3, No. 2, pp.148–168.
- Conger, J. A., & Kanungo, R. N. (1988). The empowerment process: Integrating theory and practice. *Academy of Management Review*, 13, 481-482
- Capozzi, M.M., 2010. Leadership and innovation. *Development Outreach*, 12(1), pp.25-28.
- Collins, C.J., and Smith, K.G. (2006), ‘Knowledge Exchange and Combination: The Role of Human Resource Practices in the Performance of High-Technology Firms’, *Academy of Management Journal*, 49, 544–560
- Cooke, R.A. and Szumal, J.L., 1993. Measuring normative beliefs and shared behavioral expectations in organizations: The reliability and validity of the Organizational Culture Inventory. *Psychological reports*, 72(3_suppl), pp.1299-1330.
- Cook, P., 1998. The creativity advantage-is your organization the leader of the pack?. *Industrial and commercial training*.
- Cao, G., Clarke, S. and Lehaney, B., 2000. A systemic view of organisational change and TQM. *The TQM magazine*.
- Coccia, M., 2015. Patterns of innovative outputs across climate zones: the geography of innovation. *Prometheus*, 33(2), pp.165-186.
- Chesbrough, H.W., 2011. Bringing open innovation to services. *MIT sloan management review*, 52(2), p.85.

- Denzin, N.K. and Lincoln, Y.S. eds., 2011. *The Sage handbook of qualitative research*. sage.
- Demircioglu, M.A. and Audretsch, D.B., 2017. Conditions for innovation in public sector organizations. *Research policy*, 46(9), pp.1681-1691.
- Drucker, P.F., 1990. Lessons for successful nonprofit governance. *Nonprofit management and leadership*, 1(1), pp.7-14.
- Drucker, P.F., 1974. Tasks, responsibilities, practices. *New Yorks Row*, pp.121-122.
- Denti, L. (2011). *Leadership and Innovation: How and When do Leaders Influence Innovation in R&D Teams?* University of Gothenburg, Sweden.
- De Vries, H., Bekkers, V. and Tummers, L., 2016. Innovation in the public sector: A systematic review and future research agenda. *Public administration*, 94(1), pp.146-166.
- De Vries, H., Tummers, L. and Bekkers, V., 2018. A stakeholder perspective on public sector innovation: why position matters. *International Review of Administrative Sciences*, 84(2), pp.269-287.
- Damanpour, F. and Schneider, M., 2009. Characteristics of innovation and innovation adoption in public organizations: Assessing the role of managers. *Journal of public administration research and theory*, 19(3), pp.495-522.
- Damanpour, F., Walker, R.M. and Avellaneda, C.N., 2009. Combinative effects of innovation types and organizational performance: A longitudinal study of service organizations. *Journal of management studies*, 46(4), pp.650-675.
- Denti, L. and Hemlin, S., 2012. Leadership and innovation in organizations: A systematic review of factors that mediate or moderate the relationship. *International Journal of Innovation Management*, 16(03), p.1240007.
- De Jong, J.P. and Den Hartog, D.N., 2007. How leaders influence employees' innovative behaviour. *European Journal of innovation management*.
- Dooley, K.J. and Van de Ven, A.H., 1999. Explaining complex organizational dynamics. *Organization Science*, 10(3), pp.358-372.
- Dess, G.G. and Picken, J.C., 2000. Changing roles: Leadership in the 21st century. *Organizational dynamics*, 28(3), pp.18-34.
- Dumay, J., Rooney, J. and Marini, L., 2013. An intellectual capital-based differentiation theory of innovation practice. *Journal of Intellectual Capital*.
- Dunleavy, P., Margetts, H., Bastow, S. and Tinkler, J., 2006. New public management is dead—long live digital-era governance. *Journal of public administration research and theory*, 16(3), pp.467-494.
- Emerson, R.M., 1983. *Contemporary field research: A collection of readings*. Little, Brown.
- Elo, S. and Kyngäs, H., 2008. The qualitative content analysis process. *Journal of advanced nursing*, 62(1), pp.107-115.
- Engida, T.G. and Bardill, J., 2013. Reforms of the public sector in the light of the new public management: A cases of Sub-Saharan Africa. *Journal of Public Administration and Policy Research*, 5(1), pp.1-7.

- Edquist, C., 1997. Systems of innovation approaches—their emergence and characteristics. *Systems of innovation: Technologies, institutions and organizations, 1989*, pp.1-35.
- Etzkovitz H. et Leydesdorff L. (2000), The dynamics of innovation from national systems and ,“Mode 2” to a triple helix of university-industry-government relations, *Research Policy*, 29, p. 109-123.
- Earl, L. (2002) *Innovation and Change in the Public Sector: A Seeming Oxymoron – Survey of Electronic Commerce and Technology* (Ottawa: Statistics Canada).
- Earl, L. (2004) *An Historical Comparison of Technological Change, 1998–2000 and 2000–2002, in the Private and Public Sectors* (Ottawa: Statistics Canada)
- Engelen, A., Schmidt, S., Strenger, L. and Brettel, M., 2014. Top management's transformational leader behaviors and innovation orientation: A cross-cultural perspective in eight countries. *Journal of international Management*, 20(2), pp.124-136.
- Fernando, R.L.S., 2016. Managerial Innovation in the Public Sector: An Exploratory Study on the State University Administration in Sri Lanka. *Vidyodaya Journal of Management*, 2(1).
- Flick, U., 2018. *Designing qualitative research*. Sage.
- Flyvbjerg, B. (2011). Case study. In: N. K. Denzin and Y. S. Lincoln (eds.). *The Sage Handbook of Qualitative Research*, 4th ed. Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage, pp. 301–316
- Fagerberg, J., 2004. *Innovation: A guide to the literature*. Georgia Institute of Technology.
- Ferdousi, F. & Qui, L. 2013. New Public Management in Bangladesh: Policy and Reality. *Business* 5:150-153.
- Faguet, J.P., 2007. To the MDGs and beyond: Accountability and institutional innovation in Bangladesh.
- Goertz, G. and Mahoney, J., 2012. *A tale of two cultures: Qualitative and quantitative research in the social sciences*. Princeton University Press.
- Glaser, G., and Strauss L., 2010. *The discovery of grounded theory. Strategies for qualitative research*. Hawthorne: Aldine
- Grix, J. (2002). Introducing students to the generic terminology of social research. *Politics*, 22, 175–186.
- Guba, E.G. and Lincoln, Y.S., 1994. Competing paradigms in qualitative research. *Handbook of qualitative research*, 2(163-194), p.105.
- Guba, E. and Lincoln, Y., 2012. Paradigmatic controversies, contradictions and emerging confluences. *Qualitative methodology manual* , 2 .
- Giorgi, A., 1992. Description versus interpretation: Competing alternative strategies for qualitative research. *Journal of phenomenological psychology*, 23(2), pp.119-135.
- George, A.L. and Bennett, A., 2005. *Case studies and theory development in the social sciences*. mit Press.
- Gill, R., Levine, N., & Pitt, D. C. (1998). Leadership and organizations for the new millennium. *The Journal of Leadership Studies*, 5(4), 46-59

- Glasbergen, P. ed., 1994. *Managing environmental disputes: network management as an alternative* (Vol. 5). Springer Science & Business Media.
- Gieske, H., van Buuren, A. and Bekkers, V., 2016. Conceptualizing public innovative capacity: A framework for assessment. *The Innovation Journal*, 21(1), p.1.
- Gago, D. and Rubalcaba, L., 2007. Innovation and ICT in service firms: towards a multidimensional approach for impact assessment. *Journal of Evolutionary Economics*, 17(1), pp.25-44.
- Garsombke, T.W. and Garsombke, D.J., 1989. Strategic implications facing small manufacturers: the linkage between robotization, computerization, automation and performance. *Journal of small business management*, 27(4), p.34.
- Gummer, B., 1989. Managing in the public sector: Privatization, policy deadlock, and the erosion of public authority. *Administration in Social Work*, 12(4), pp.103-118.
- Gallouj, F. and Zanfei, A., 2013. Innovation in public services: Filling a gap in the literature. *Structural change and economic dynamics*, 27, pp.89-97.
- Gumusluoğlu, L. and Ilsev, A., 2009. Transformational leadership and organizational innovation: The roles of internal and external support for innovation. *Journal of Product Innovation Management*, 26(3), pp.264-277.
- Goes, J.B. and Park, S.H., 1997. Interorganizational links and innovation: The case of hospital services. *Academy of management journal*, 40(3), pp.673-696.
- George, A.L. and Bennett, A., 2005. *Case studies and theory development in the social sciences*. mit Press.
- Hood, J.C., 2006. Teaching against the text: The case of qualitative methods. *Teaching Sociology*, 34(3), pp.207-223.
- Hammersley, M., 2018. What is ethnography? Can it survive? Should it?. *Ethnography and Education*, 13(1), pp.1-17.
- Harrison, H; Birks, M ; Franklin, R & Mills, J. (2017). *Case Study Research: Foundations and Methodological Orientations*. Forum: Qualitative Social Research. 18.
- Hasan, M. Mahmudul. (2012). Evaluation of Citizen Help Request (CHR) initiated by Bangladesh Police: A Case study..
- Haque, C. and Uddin, M., 2013. Disaster Management Discourse in Bangladesh: A Shift from Post-Event Response to the Preparedness and Mitigation Approach Through Institutional Partnerships. *Approaches to Disaster Management - Examining the Implications of Hazards, Emergencies and Disasters*,.
- Hyatt, L., Hyatt, B. and Hyatt, J., 2007. Effective leadership through emotional maturity. *Academic Leadership: The Online Journal*, 5(2), p.4.
- Hofman, B., Rodrick-Jones, E. and Thee, K.W., 2004, May. Indonesia: Rapid growth, weak institutions. In *World Bank Shanghai Conference*, http://www.worldbank.org/wbi/reducing_poverty/case-Indonesia-PovertyReduction.html.
- Hartley J (2014) New development: Eight and a half propositions to stimulate frugal innovation. *Public Money & Management* 34(3): 227–232.
- Hossain, M.I. (2021). COVID-19 Impacts on Employment and Livelihood of Marginal People in Bangladesh: Lessons Learned and Way Forward. *South Asian Survey*,

[online] 28(1), p.097152312199507. Available at: <https://journals.sagepub.com/doi/full/10.1177/0971523121995072>

- Hunter, Samuel & Cushenbery, Lily & Cushenbery, D & Bradley,. (2017). Why dual leaders will drive innovation: Resolving the exploration and exploitation dilemma with a conservation of resources solution. *Journal of Org. Behavior*. 38. 10.1002/job.2195.
- Hülshager, U. R., Anderson, N., & Salgado, J. F. (2009). Team-level predictors of innovation at work: A comprehensive meta-analysis spanning three decades of research. *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 94, 1128–1145.
- Hemlin, S. (2006). Managing creativity in academic research: How could creative action and management be reconciled in research? *Science Studies*, 19, 3-12.
- Halachmi , Arie . 2002 . Performance Measurement, Accountability, and Improved Performance . *Public Performance & Management Review* 25 (4): 370 – 74
- Hossain, I., 2018. *RMG exports saw 8.76% growth last fiscal year*. [online] Dhaka Tribune. Available at: <<https://www.dhakatribune.com/business/2018/07/05/rmg-exports-saw-8-76-growth-last-fiscal-year>>
- Haque, M. and Mourshed, I., 2020. *Leveraging Innovation for Bangladesh's Growth - LightCastle Partners*. [online] LightCastle Partners. Available at: <<https://www.lightcastlebd.com/insights/2020/04/leveraging-innovation-for-bangladeshs-growth>>
- Hofstede, G., Neuijen, B., Ohayv, D.D. and Sanders, G., 1990. Measuring organizational cultures: A qualitative and quantitative study across twenty cases. *Administrative science quarterly*, pp.286-316.
- House, R.J. and Aditya, R.N., 1997. The social scientific study of leadership: Quo vadis?.. *Journal of management*, 23(3), pp.409-473.
- Hunter, S.T., Thoroughgood, C.N., Myer, A.T. and Ligon, G.S., 2011. Paradoxes of leading innovative endeavors: Summary, solutions, and future directions. *Psychology of Aesthetics, creativity, and the arts*, 5(1), p.54.
- Hasu, M., Saari, E. and Mattelmäki, T., 2011. Bringing the employee back in: integrating user-driven and employee-driven innovation in the public sector. In *User-based innovation in services*. Edward Elgar Publishing.
- Hülshager, U.R., Anderson, N. and Salgado, J.F., 2009. Team-level predictors of innovation at work: a comprehensive meta-analysis spanning three decades of research. *Journal of Applied psychology*, 94(5), p.1128.
- Islam, Md.T., Talukder, A.K., Siddiqui, Md.N. and Islam, T. (2020). Tackling the COVID-19 pandemic: the Bangladesh perspective. *Journal of Public Health Research*, 9(4).
- IMF Data Mapper: Bangladesh (2021) [online] Available at: <https://www.imf.org/external/datamapper/NGDP_RPCH@WEO/OEMDC/ADVEC/WEOWORLD/BGD>
- Jovanović, G., 2011. Toward a social history of qualitative research. *History of the human sciences*, 24(2), pp.1-27.

- Jaleha, A.A. and Machuki, V.N., 2018. Strategic leadership and organizational performance: A critical review of literature. *European Scientific Journal*, 14(35), pp.124-149.
- Joffe, H., 2012. Thematic analysis. *Qualitative research methods in mental health and psychotherapy*, 1.
- Jacques, J. and Ryan, E.J., 1978. Does management by objectives stifle organizational innovation in the public sector?. *Canadian Public Administration*, 21(1), pp.16-25.
- Jamil, I., 2002. Administrative culture in Bangladesh: Tensions between tradition and modernity. *International Review of Sociology/Revue Internationale de Sociologie*, 12(1), pp.93-125.
- Kallio, H., Pietilä, A.M., Johnson, M. and Kangasniemi, M., 2016. Systematic methodological review: developing a framework for a qualitative semi-structured interview guide. *Journal of advanced nursing*, 72(12), pp.2954-2965.
- Kesting, P & Ulhøi, J & Song, J & Niu, H (2016). The impact of leadership styles on innovation - a review. *Journal of Innovation Management*. 3. 22. 10.24840/2183-0606_003.004_0004.
- Kohlbacher, F., 2006. *The Use of Qualitative Content Analysis in Case Study Research*. [online] Qualitative-research.net. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.17169/fqs-7.1.75>
- Kanter, R. M. and Summers, D. V. (1987), Doing well, while doing good: dilemmas of performance measurement in non-profit organizations and the need for a multiple-constituency approach. In Powell, W. W. (Ed), *The Non-profit Sector: A Research Handbook* (Yale University Press, Yale).
- Kickul, J. and Liao-Troth, M.A., 2003. The meaning behind the message: Climate perceptions and the psychological contract. *American Journal of Business*.
- Kamarck, E., 2004. Government innovation around the world. Available at SSRN 517666.
- Kanter, R.M., 1984. SMR Forum: Innovation--The Only Hope for Times Ahead?. *Sloan Management Review (pre-1986)*, 25(4), p.51.
- Klijn EH and Koppenjan JFM (2016) *Governance Networks in the Public Sector*. Oxon: Routledge.
- Kelman, Steven . 2008 . The “Kennedy School School” of Research on Innovation in Government . In *Innovative Governance in the 21st Century*, edited by Sandford Borins , 28 – 51 . Washington, DC : Brookings Institution Press .
- Koch, P. and Hauknes, J., 2005. On innovation in the public sector—today and beyond.
- Kahai, S.S., Sosik, J.J. and Avolio, B.J., 2003. Effects of leadership style, anonymity, and rewards on creativity-relevant processes and outcomes in an electronic meeting system context. *The Leadership Quarterly*, 14(4-5), pp.499-524.
- Kickul, J. and Liao-Troth, M.A., 2003. The meaning behind the message: Climate perceptions and the psychological contract. *American Journal of Business*.
- Kettl, D.F., 2000. Public administration at the millennium: The state of the field. *Journal of public administration research and theory*, 10(1), pp.7-34.
- Khalid, M.S., 2011, March. ICT in education: secondary technical vocational education and training institute centered diffusion of innovation in rural Bangladesh.

In *Proceedings of the 5th International Technology, Education and Development Conference* (pp. 1126-1134). International Association of Technology, Education and Development (IATED).

- Krause, D.E., 2004. Influence-based leadership as a determinant of the inclination to innovate and of innovation-related behaviors: An empirical investigation. *The leadership quarterly*, 15(1), pp.79-102.
- Krusenvik, L., 2016. Using case studies as a scientific method: Advantages and disadvantages.
- Kim, Y.H., Sting, F.J. and Loch, C.H., 2014. Top-down, bottom-up, or both? Toward an integrative perspective on operations strategy formation. *Journal of Operations Management*, 32(7-8), pp.462-474.
- Lazarsfeld, P.F., 1982. *The varied sociology of Paul F. Lazarsfeld: writings*. Columbia University Press.
- Lofland J, Snow D.A., Anderson L, Lofland L.H.; 2006. *Analyzing social settings. A guide to qualitative observation and analysis*. 4. Belmont: Wadsworth/Thomson Learning.
- Light, P.C., 1998. *Sustaining innovation: Creating nonprofit and government organizations that innovate naturally*. Jossey-Bass.
- Lee, S.M., Hwang, T. and Choi, D., 2012. Open innovation in the public sector of leading countries. *Management decision*.
- Lewis, J.M., Ricard, L.M. and Klijn, E.H., 2018. How innovation drivers, networking and leadership shape public sector innovation capacity. *International Review of Administrative Sciences*, 84(2), pp.288-307.
- Light, P.C., 1998. *Sustaining innovation: Creating nonprofit and government organizations that innovate naturally*. Jossey-Bass.
- Lundvall, B.A., 1992. National systems of innovation: An analytical framework. *London: Pinter*.
- Lemay, L., 2009. The Practice of Collective and Strategic Leadership in the Public Sector. *Innovation Journal*, 14(1).
- Lewis, P.S., Goodman, S.H. and Fandt, P.M., 2001. Management Challenges in the 21st Century. Cincinnati, Ohio.
- Reiman, T. and Oedewald, P., 2002. The assessment of organisational culture. *A methodological study. VTT Research Notes, VTT Industrial Systems, Espoo*.
- Lee, J., Lee, H. and Park, J.G., 2014. Exploring the impact of empowering leadership on knowledge sharing, absorptive capacity and team performance in IT service. *Information Technology & People*.
- McIntyre, L.J., 2004. *Need to know: Social science research methods*. McGraw-Hill Education.
- Moon, K. and Blackman, D., 2014. A guide to understanding social science research for natural scientists. *Conservation biology*, 28(5), pp.1167-1177.
- McIntosh, M.J. and Morse, J.M., 2015. Situating and constructing diversity in semi-structured interviews. *Global qualitative nursing research*, 2, p.2333393615597674.
- Merriam, B. (2009). *Qualitative research: A guide to design and implementation* (2nd ed.). San Francisco, CA: Jossey-Bass

- Morgan, D.L., 2014. Pragmatism as a paradigm for social research. *Qualitative inquiry*, 20(8), pp.1045-1053.
- Mayring, P., 2004. Qualitative content analysis. *A companion to qualitative research*, 1(2), pp.159-176.
- Marsh, D., & Furlong, P. (2002). A skin, not a sweater: ontology and epistemology in political science. In D Marsh., & G Stoker, (Eds.), *Theory and Methods in Political Science*, New York, NY: Palgrave MacMillan, pp. 17–41.
- McComas, W.F., 1998. The Principle Elements of the Nature of Science: Dispelling the Myths, from *The Nature of Science in Science Education*, pp53-70. *Netherlands: Kluwer Academic Publishers*.
- Merritt, R.L. and Merritt, A.J., 1985. *Innovation in the public sector*. Sage Publications.
- M.A. Khan, I.A. Bhuyan, M.M. Rahman (2010), Assessment of Cyclone Risk under the Changing Climatic Condition for the Coastal Areas of Bangladesh, in Northumbria University, UK
- MWR (Ministry of Water Resources) (2005) , Coastal Zone Policy, Dhaka, Bangladesh.
- Mau, T., Xavier, J. and Mendoza, M., 2018. *Public-sector Leadership for Innovation and Productivity*. [online] www.apo-tokyo.org. Available at: <<https://www.apo-tokyo.org/publications/wp-content/uploads/sites/5/Public-sector-Leadership-for-Innovation-and-Productivity.pdf>>
- Moore , Mark H. , and Jean Hartley . 2008 . Innovations in Governance . Public Management Review 10 (1): 3 – 20 .
- Moore , Mark H. 2014 . Public Value. Accounting: Establishing the Philosophical Basis . Public Administration Review 74 (4): 465 – 77 .
- Mohammad, K M, Shahriar, I. Md., (2014) "Public sector leadership development in Bangladesh: present state and future prospect", *The International Journal of Leadership in Public Services*, Vol. 10 Issue: 1, pp.17-30, <https://doi.org/10.1108/IJLPS-06-2013-0016>
- McDonald, R. E. (2007). An investigation of innovation in nonprofit organizations: The role of organizational mission. *Nonprofit and Voluntary Quarterly*, 36, 256-281.
- Martínez-Sánchez, A., Vela-Jiménez, M.J., Pérez-Pérez, M. and de-Luis-Carnicer, P., 2008. Workplace flexibility and innovation: The moderator effect of inter-organizational cooperation. *Personnel Review*.
- Murayama, M. and Yokota, N., 2009. Revisiting labour and gender issues in export processing zones: cases of South Korea, Bangladesh and India. *Economic and Political Weekly*, pp.73-83.
- Mumford, M.D., Scott, G.M., Gaddis, B. and Strange, J.M., 2002. Leading creative people: Orchestrating expertise and relationships. *The leadership quarterly*, 13(6), pp.705-750.

- McMurray, A.J., Islam, M., Sarros, J.C. and Pirola-Merlo, A., 2012. The impact of leadership on workgroup climate and performance in a non-profit organization. *Leadership & Organization Development Journal*.
- Mumford, M.D. and Licuanan, B., 2004. Leading for innovation: Conclusions, issues, and directions. *The leadership quarterly*, 15(1), pp.163-171.
- Mondal, M, Kamp L, Pachova N (2010) “Drivers, barriers and strategies for implementation of renewable energy technologies in rural areas in Bangladesh - An innovation system analysis”, *Energy Policy*, Vol. 38, Issue 8, August 2010, 4626-4634.
- Menon, M.H., 2002. Solid waste management in Dhaka Bangladesh, Innovation in community driven composting. *Analysis of community based initiative for solid waste management, 1*.
- Miles, M.B. and Huberman, A.M., 1994. *Qualitative data analysis: An expanded sourcebook*. sage.
- Makri, M. and Scandura, T.A., 2010. Exploring the effects of creative CEO leadership on innovation in high-technology firms. *The leadership quarterly*, 21(1), pp.75-88.
- Muller, E., Zenker, A. and Ramos, J.C., 2012. Knowledge angels, creative behaviors, and emerging innovation modes: observations from Alsace, Baden-Württemberg, and Catalonia. In *Exploring Knowledge-Intensive Business Services* (pp. 35-55). Palgrave Macmillan, London.
- Mau, Tim & Xavier, John & Mendosa, Magdalena. (2018). PUBLIC-SECTOR LEADERSHIP FOR INNOVATION AND PRODUCTIVITY APO FRAMEWORK AND RESOURCE GUIDE FOR PUBLIC-SECTOR LEADERSHIP. 10.13140/RG.2.2.28304.10242.
- Newcomer, K.E., Hatry, H.P. and Wholey, J.S., 2015. Conducting semi-structured interviews. *Handbook of practical program evaluation*, 492, p.492.
- Nowmi, S., 2017. *Filing GD or General Dairy online*. [online] The Financial Express. Available at: <<https://www.thefinancialexpress.com.bd/views/letters/filing-gd-or-general-dairy-online>>
- Nkohkwo, Q.N.A. and Islam, M.S., 2013. Challenges to the Successful Implementation of e-Government Initiatives in Sub-Saharan Africa: A Literature Review. *Electronic Journal of e-government*, 11(1).
- Nmadu, J.N., Sallawu, H. and Omojeso, B.V., 2015. Socio-economic factors affecting Adoption of Innovations by Cocoa Farmers in Ondo State, Nigeria.
- Nelson, R.R. ed., 1993. *National innovation systems: a comparative analysis*. Oxford University Press on Demand.
- Nadler, D.A. and Tushman, M.L., 1990. Beyond the charismatic leader: Leadership and organizational change. *California management review*, 32(2), pp.77-97.
- Nawaz, Z.A.K.D.A. and Khan_ PhD, I., 2016. Leadership theories and styles: A literature review. *Leadership*, 16(1), pp.1-7.
- Oecd-ilibrary.org. 2018. *OSLO Manual 2018*. [online] Available at: <<https://www.oecd-ilibrary.org/docserver/9789264304604-10-en.pdf?expires=1637289055&id=id&accname=guest&checksum=53B1703A9621C7890D18AB85CBD47AA7>>

- OECD (2017b), What's possible? Finding and filtering innovative ideas, OECD Public Governance Reviews, OECD Publishing, Paris.
 - Osborne, D.R., 1998. The learning organization and leadership for the college system.
 - O'reilly, C.A. and Chatman, J.A., 1996. Culture as social control: Corporations, cults, and commitment.
 - Osterman, K.F. and Kottkamp, R.B., 1993. *Reflective practice for educators: Improving schooling through professional development*. Corwin Press, Inc., 2455 Teller Road, Newbury Park CA 91320.
 - Park, S.H., Kim, J.N. and Krishna, A., 2014. Bottom-up building of an innovative organization: Motivating employee intrapreneurship and scouting and their strategic value. *Management Communication Quarterly*, 28(4), pp.531-560.
 - Panne, Gerben & Beers, Cees & Kleinkecht, Alfred. (2003). Success and Failure of Innovation: A Literature Review. *International Journal of Innovation Management*. 7. 309-337. 10.1142/S1363919603000830.
 - Pollitt, C. and Hupe, P., 2011. Talking about government: The role of magic concepts. *Public management review*, 13(5), pp.641-658.
 - Potts, J., 2009. The innovation deficit in public services: The curious problem of too much efficiency and not enough waste and failure. *Innovation*, 11(1), pp.34-43.
 - Porter, L.W. and McLaughlin, G.B., 2006. Leadership and the organizational context: like the weather?. *The Leadership Quarterly*, 17(6), pp.559-576.
 - Peel, J., Cropley, B., Hanton, S. and Fleming, S., 2013. Learning through reflection: Values, conflicts, and role interactions of a youth sport coach. *Reflective practice*, 14(6), pp.729-742.
 - Qi, L., Liu, B., Wei, X. and Hu, Y., 2019. Impact of inclusive leadership on employee innovative behavior: Perceived organizational support as a mediator. *PloS one*, 14(2), p.e0212091.
-
- Rawls, A., 2018. The wartime narrative in US sociology, 1940–1947. *European Journal of Social Theory*, 21(4), pp.526-546.
 - Rahman, S, Alam, Q, Teicher, J & Van Gramberg, B 2017, Public sector leadership in developing countries: the nature and character of leadership among mid-level managers in Bangladesh. in *The 21st International Research Society for Public Management (IRSPM) Conference in Budapest, Hungary*. 21st Annual Conference of the International Research Society on Public Management, Budapest, Hungary, 19/04/17.
 - Rahman, M., Sajib, E., Chowdhury, I., Banik, A., Bhattacharya, R. and Ahmed, H., 2021. Present scenario of COVID-19 in Bangladesh and government preparedness for facing challenges. *Journal of Advanced Biotechnology and Experimental Therapeutics*, 4(2), p.187.
 - Rafi, A., Mousumi, A.N., Ahmed, R., Chowdhury, R.H., Wadood, A. and Hossain, G. (2020). Dengue epidemic in a non-endemic zone of Bangladesh: Clinical and laboratory profiles of patients. *PLOS Neglected Tropical Diseases*, [online] 14(10),

<https://journals.plos.org/plosntds/article?id=10.1371/journal.pntd.0008567>

- Rogers , Everett M. 2003 . Diffusion of Innovation . 5th ed . New York : Free Press .
- Ricard , Lykke Margot , Erik Hans Klijn , Jenny M. Lewis , and Tamyko Ysa . 2017 . Assessing Public Leadership Styles for Innovation: A Comparison of Copenhagen, Rotterdam and Barcelona . *Public Management Review* 19 (2): 134 – 56 .
- Rainey, H.G., 1999. Using comparisons of public and private organizations to assess innovative attitudes among members of organizations. *Public Productivity & Management Review*, pp.130-149.
- Reiter-Palmon, R. and Illies, J.J., 2004. Leadership and creativity: Understanding leadership from a creative problem-solving perspective. *The leadership quarterly*, 15(1), pp.55-77.
- Rosing, K., Frese, M. and Bausch, A., 2011. Explaining the heterogeneity of the leadership-innovation relationship: Ambidextrous leadership. *The leadership quarterly*, 22(5), pp.956-974.
- Ryan, J.C. and Tipu, S.A., 2013. Leadership effects on innovation propensity: A two-factor full range leadership model. *Journal of Business Research*, 66(10), pp.2116-2129.
- Razzaue, A., Eusuf, A. and Shamannay, U., 2007. Trade, Development and Poverty Linkage: Case Study of Ready Made Garment Industry in Bangladesh. *Unnayan Shamannay*, pp.4-8.
- Scupola, A. and Zanfei, A., 2016. Governance and innovation in public sector services: The case of the digital library. *Government Information Quarterly*, 33(2), pp.237-249.
- Snow, D.A. and Morrill, C., 1995. New ethnographies: review symposium: a revolutionary handbook or a handbook for revolution?. *Journal of contemporary ethnography*, 24(3), pp.341-348.
- Stake, R. (2006). Multiple case study analysis. New York, NY: Guilford.
- Stewart, D.W. and Shamdasani, P.N., 2014. *Focus groups: Theory and practice* (Vol. 20). Sage publications.
- Smith, J., Glor, E. and Brodrick, O., 2001. Some thoughts on definitions of innovation. *The Innovation Journal*.
- Sabatier, P.A., 1987. Knowledge, policy-oriented learning, and policy change: An advocacy coalition framework. *Knowledge*, 8(4), pp.649-692.
- Steinheider, B. and Wuestewald, T., 2008. From the bottom-up: sharing leadership in a police agency. *Police Practice and Research: An International Journal*, 9(2), pp.145-163.
- Sauermann, H., & Cohen, W. M. (2010). What makes them tick? Employee motives and firm innovation. *Management Science*, 56, 2134-2153. doi:10.1287/mnsc.1100.1241
- Saari, E., Lehtonen, M. and Toivonen, M., 2015. Making bottom-up and top-down processes meet in public innovation. *The Service Industries Journal*, 35(6), pp.325-344.

- Sarker, A.E., 2006. New public management in developing countries: An analysis of success and failure with particular reference to Singapore and Bangladesh. *International Journal of Public Sector Management*.
- Sarker, M.N.I., Wu, M., Liu, R. and Ma, C., 2018, August. Challenges and opportunities for information resource management for E-governance in Bangladesh. In *International Conference on Management Science and Engineering Management* (pp. 675-688). Springer, Cham.
- Schein, E.H., 1990. Organizational Culture: What it is and How to Change it. In *Human resource management in international firms* (pp. 56-82). Palgrave Macmillan, London.
- Siegel, S.M. and Kaemmerer, W.F., 1978. Measuring the perceived support for innovation in organizations. *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 63(5), p.553.
- Stoker, J.I., Looise, J.C., Fisscher, O.A.M. and Jong, R.D., 2001. Leadership and innovation: relations between leadership, individual characteristics and the functioning of R&D teams. *International Journal of Human Resource Management*, 12(7), pp.1141-1151.
- Somech, A., 2006. The effects of leadership style and team process on performance and innovation in functionally heterogeneous teams. *Journal of management*, 32(1), pp.132-157.
- Simmons, P., 2011. Spirit, opportunity, and innovation: science education for a smarter planet. *Journal of College Science Teaching*, 41(1), p.10.
- Sims, R.R. and Quatro, S.A., 2015. *Leadership: Succeeding in the Private, Public, and Not-for-profit Sectors: Succeeding in the Private, Public, and Not-for-profit Sectors*. Routledge.
- Sarker, M.N.I., Bingxin, Y., Sultana, A. and Prodhan, A.S., 2017. Problems and challenges of public administration in Bangladesh: pathway to sustainable development. *International Journal of Public Administration and Policy Research*, 3(1), pp.16-25.
- Saunders, M., Lewis, P. & Thornhill, A. (2012) "Research Methods for Business Students" 6th edition, Pearson Education Limited
- Schoemaker, P., Krupp, S. and Howland, S. (2013). *Strategic Leadership: The Essential Skills*. [online] Harvard Business Review. Available at: <https://hbr.org/2013/01/strategic-leadership-the-essential-skills>
- Shin, J., & McClomb, G. E. (1998). Top executive leadership and organizational innovation: An empirical investigation of nonprofit human service organizations (HSOs). *Administration in Social Work*, 22(3), 1-21.
- Sperandio, J., 2005. Social Entrepreneurs and Educational Leadership in Bangladesh. *Current Issues in Comparative Education*, 8(1), pp.18-30.
- Stewart, J., 2006. Transformational leadership: An evolving concept examined through the works of Burns, Bass, Avolio, and Leithwood. *Canadian Journal of Educational Administration and Policy*, 54, pp.1-29.
- Samad, S., 2012. The influence of innovation and transformational leadership on organizational performance. *Procedia-Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 57, pp.486-493.

- Shamir, B., House, R.J. and Arthur, M.B., 1993. The motivational effects of charismatic leadership: A self-concept based theory. *Organization science*, 4(4), pp.577-594.
- Stanwick, P.A. and Stanwick, S.D., 2003. CEO and ethical reputation: visionary or mercenary?. *Management Decision*.
- Shaheen, N., Halima, O., Akhter, K.T., Nuzhat, N., Rao, R.S.P., Wilson, R.S. and Ahsan, N., 2019. Proteomic characterization of low molecular weight allergens and putative allergen proteins in lentil (*Lens culinaris*) cultivars of Bangladesh. *Food chemistry*, 297, p.124936.
- Sperandio, J., 2005. Social Entrepreneurs and Educational Leadership in Bangladesh. *Current Issues in Comparative Education*, 8(1), pp.18-30.
- Swan, J. and Scarbrough, H., 2005. The politics of networked innovation. *Human relations*, 58(7), pp.913-943.
- Sundbo, J., 1996. The balancing of empowerment. A strategic resource based model of organizing innovation activities in service and low-tech firms. *Technovation*, 16(8), pp.397-446.
- Steinheider, B. and Wuestewald, T., 2008. From the bottom-up: sharing leadership in a police agency. *Police Practice and Research: An International Journal*, 9(2), pp.145-163.
- Tuli, F., 2010. The basis of distinction between qualitative and quantitative research in social science: Reflection on ontological, epistemological and methodological perspectives. *Ethiopian Journal of Education and Sciences*, 6(1).
- Teegavarapu, S & Summers, J. (2008). *CASE STUDY METHOD FOR DESIGN RESEARCH*. Available at : <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/228360044>
- Takahashi, A.R.W. and Araujo, L. (2019), "Case study research: opening up research opportunities", *RAUSP Management Journal*, Vol. 55 No. 1, pp. 100-111. <https://doi.org/10.1108/RAUSP-05-2019-0109>
- Tashakkori, A. and Teddlie, C., 2003. Issues and dilemmas in teaching research methods courses in social and behavioural sciences: US perspective. *International journal of social research methodology*, 6(1), pp.61-77.
- Todres, L. and Holloway, I., 2005. Qualitative research in health care. *Berkshire, England: Open University*.
- Tidd, J., 2001. Innovation management in context: environment, organization and performance. *International journal of management reviews*, 3(3), pp.169-183.
- Taylor, Jeanette . 2013 . Goal Setting in the Australian Public Service: Effects on Psychological Empowerment and Organizational Citizenship Behavior . *Public Administration Review* 73 (3): 453 – 64 .
- Tahrima, S. and Jaegal, D., 2012. Challenges for government innovation in Bangladesh. *Korean Journal of Policy Studies*, 27.
- Terry, L.D., 1993. Why We Should Abandon the Misconceived Quest to Reconcile Public Entrepreneurship with Democracy: A Response to Bellone and Goerl's"

- Reconciling Public Entrepreneurship and Democracy". *Public Administration Review*, 53(4), pp.393-395.
- Tan, C.S.L., Smyrnios, K.X. and Xiong, L., 2014. What drives learning orientation in fast growth SMEs?. *International Journal of Entrepreneurial Behavior & Research*.
 - Tybout, J.R., 2000. Manufacturing firms in developing countries: How well do they do, and why?. *Journal of Economic literature*, 38(1), pp.11-44.
 - Ullah, M., 2016. *Tax System in Bangladesh: Efficiency and Fairness*. [online] Excluded Voices. Available at: https://excludedvoices.wordpress.com/2016/01/21/tax-system-in-bangladesh-efficiency-and-fairness/#_ftn42
 - Vaismoradi, M., Turunen, H. and Bondas, T., 2013. Content analysis and thematic analysis: Implications for conducting a qualitative descriptive study. *Nursing & health sciences*, 15(3), pp.398-405.
 - Vigoda-Gadot, E. and Kapun, D., 2005. Perceptions of politics and perceived performance in public and private organisations: a test of one model across two sectors. *Policy & Politics*, 33(2), pp.251-276.
 - Velnampy, T., 2008. Job attitude and employees performance of public sector organizations in Jaffna district, Sri Lanka. *GITAM journal of management*, 6(2), pp.66-73.
 - Von Hippel, E., 1976. The dominant role of users in the scientific instrument innovation process. *Research policy*, 5(3), pp.212-239.
 - Van Wart, M., 2003. Public-sector leadership theory: An assessment. *Public administration review*, pp.214-228.
 - Verkijika, S.F. and De Wet, L., 2018. Quality assessment of e-government websites in Sub-Saharan Africa: A public values perspective. *The Electronic Journal of Information Systems in Developing Countries*, 84(2), p.e12015.
 - Von Treuer, K. and McMurray, A.J., 2012. The role of organisational climate factors in facilitating workplace innovation. *International Journal of Entrepreneurship and innovation management*, 15(4), pp.292-309.
 - Van de Ven, A.H., 1986. Central problems in the management of innovation. *Management science*, 32(5), pp.590-607.
 - Van der Panne, G., Van Beers, C. and Kleinknecht, A., 2003. Success and failure of innovation: a literature review. *International Journal of Innovation Management*, 7(03), pp.309-338.
 - Von Hippel, E., 1976. The dominant role of users in the scientific instrument innovation process. *Research policy*, 5(3), pp.212-239.
 - Windrum, P. 2014. Third sector organisations and the co-productions of health innovations. *Management Decisions*, 52 (6): 1046-1056.
 - Walker RM, Damanpour F and Devece CA (2011) Management innovation and organizational performance: The mediating effect of performance management. *Journal of Public Administration Research and Theory* 21(2): 367–387.
 - Welch, E.W. and Wong, W., 2001. Global information technology pressure and government accountability: the mediating effect of domestic context on website openness. *Journal of Public Administration Research and Theory*, 11(4), pp.509-538.

- Walker, R.M. and Boyne, G.A., 2006. Public management reform and organizational performance: An empirical assessment of the UK Labour government's public service improvement strategy. *Journal of Policy Analysis and Management: The Journal of the Association for Public Policy Analysis and Management*, 25(2), pp.371-393.
- Walker, R.M., Damanpour, F. and Devece, C.A., 2011. Management innovation and organizational performance: The mediating effect of performance management. *Journal of public administration research and theory*, 21(2), pp.367-386.
- Wang, P., Rode, J.C., Shi, K., Luo, Z. and Chen, W., 2013. A workgroup climate perspective on the relationships among transformational leadership, workgroup diversity, and employee creativity. *Group & Organization Management*, 38(3), pp.334-360.
- Wilson, W.J., 1989. The underclass: Issues, perspectives, and public policy. *The Annals of the American Academy of Political and Social Science*, 501(1), pp.182-192.
- Waterman, R.H. and Peters, T.J., 1982. *In search of excellence: Lessons from America's best-run companies* (p. 360). New York: Harper & Row.
- Wright, P.M., McMahan, G.C., Snell, S.A. and Gerhart, B., 2001. Comparing line and HR executives' perceptions of HR effectiveness: Services, roles, and contributions. *Human Resource Management: Published in Cooperation with the School of Business Administration, The University of Michigan and in alliance with the Society of Human Resources Management*, 40(2), pp.111-123.
- Wilson, A.M., 2001. Understanding organizational culture and the implications for corporate marketing. *European Journal of Marketing*.
- Worley, C.G., Bowen, D.E. and Lawler III, E.E., 1992. On the relationship between objective increases in pay and employees' subjective reactions. *Journal of Organizational Behavior*, 13(6), pp.559-571.:
- Yin, R. (2014). *Case study research: Design and methods*. Los Angeles, CA: Sage
- Yvonne Feilzer, M., 2010. Doing mixed methods research pragmatically: Implications for the rediscovery of pragmatism as a research paradigm. *Journal of mixed methods research*, 4(1), pp.6-16.
- Youndt, M.A., Snell, S.A., Dean Jr, J.W. and Lepak, D.P., 1996. Human resource management, manufacturing strategy, and firm performance. *Academy of management Journal*, 39(4), pp.836-866.
- Yassin, F., Salim, J. and Sahari, N., 2013. The influence of organizational factors on knowledge sharing using ICT among teachers. *Procedia Technology*, 11, pp.272-280.
- Yukl, G., 1989. Managerial leadership: A review of theory and research. *Journal of management*, 15(2), pp.251-289.
- Yin, R.K., 2003. Designing case studies. *Qualitative Research Methods*, 5, pp.359-386.
- Zhang, X., & Bartol, K. M. (2010). Linking empowering leadership and employee creativity: The influence of psychological empowerment, intrinsic motivation, and creative process engagement. *Academy of Management Journal*, 53, 107-128.
- Zhou, Y., Liu, G., Chang, X. and Hong, Y., 2021. Top-down, bottom-up or outside-in? An examination of triadic mechanisms on firm innovation in Chinese firms. *Asian Business & Management*, 20(1), pp.131-162.

- Zafarullah, H. and Huque, A.S., 2001. Public management for good governance: reforms, regimes, and reality in Bangladesh. *International Journal of Public Administration*, 24(12), pp.1379-1403.
- Zafarullah, H. and Siddiquee, N.A., 2001. Dissecting public sector corruption in Bangladesh: issues and problems of control. *Public Organization Review*, 1(4), pp.465-486.
- Zohir, S., 2007. Estimating the number of MFI clients moving above US \$1 a day threshold. *Economic Research Group*.
- Zhou, J. and Shalley, C.E., 2003. Research on employee creativity: A critical review and directions for future research. *Research in personnel and human resources management*.
- Zaman, H., 2015. Service delivery process innovation: insights from Digital Bangladesh. *Innovation and Development*, 5(1), pp.165-168.
- Zafarullah, H.M. and Huque, A.S., 1998. Public management in South Asia: Dimensions and directions of change. *International Journal of Public Administration*, 21(10), pp.1473-1510.
- Zaman, H., 2021. Policy design: Perspectives of innovation from Digital Bangladesh.
- Zaman, K.A.U. and Sarker, T., 2021. Demographic dividend, digital innovation, and economic growth: Bangladesh experience (No. 1237). ADBI Working Paper Series.